
Experimental and Crystal Plasticity Simulation Study on the Deformation Behavior of Liquid Phase Sintered Tungsten Heavy Alloys

*A thesis submitted in fulfilment of the requirements
for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy*

by

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Certificate

It is certified that the work contained in this thesis entitled “**Experimental and Crystal Plasticity Simulation Study on the Deformation Behavior of Liquid Phase Sintered Tungsten Heavy Alloys**” by **Mirtunjay Kumar** has been carried out under my supervision and that it has not been submitted elsewhere for a degree.

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To the best of my knowledge, it is an original work, both in terms of research content and narrative, and has not been submitted elsewhere, in part or in full, for a degree. Further, due credit has been attributed to the relevant state-of-the-art and collaborations with appropriate citations and acknowledgments, in line with established norms and practices.

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Abstract

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Tungsten heavy alloys (WHA) are typical two-phase composites that include a near-spherical b.c.c. structured tungsten phase dispersed in a ductile f.c.c. Ni-Fe-W solid-solution matrix phase. Owing to the outstanding combination of the properties such as high strength, good wear and corrosion resistance, WHA are widely used in defence and civil industries. Conventionally, WHA are usually fabricated through liquid-phase sintering within the temperature range of 1450-1550 °C, and the obtained tungsten grain size is usually about 40–50 μm . The present thesis aims to decipher the governing deformation mechanisms in the ductile two-phase WHA to provide a way forward for improving the performance of WHA to fulfil the global demand for high-end defence related applications. In this regard, crystallographic texture has been used as a tool in the present dissertation to identify and estimate the contribution from the various deformation micro-mechanisms. Till date, the studies on WHA have focused primarily on alloy development by tailoring the tungsten content or alloying addition, with a few studies on mechanical properties. The systematic investigation of the deformation behaviour of two phase WHA is missing in the literature. In particular, the role of Ni-Fe-W solid-solution matrix on deformation behaviour has only been analyzed to a very limited extent in previous studies.

Tungsten is isotropic in the elastic regime, but there is high degree of anisotropy in the plastic properties of tungsten in the quasistatic and dynamic strain rate regime with a strong dependence on crystallographic texture. In the current work, the evolution of texture during plastic deformation is systematically analysed by performing both postmortem and *in situ* studies using neutron diffraction, x-ray diffraction, and electron back scatter diffraction (EBSD). Furthermore, texture simulations have been conducted to supplement the experimental microstructure and texture measurements using mean field and full field crystal plasticity frameworks. The Eshelby inclusion based viscoplastic self-consistent simulations (VPSC) was employed for mean field simulations while the fast Fourier transform (FFT) based DAMASK (Düsseldorf Advanced Material Simulation Kit) was used for carrying out full field simulations. These simulations also provided information about key parameters such as slip activity, an average number of slip systems, stress and strain partitioning between the two phases, micro-mechanical Taylor factor and equivalent Von Mises stress and strain maps which shed light on the operative mechanisms of deformation of the WHA.

In the first part of the thesis, deformation behaviour was analysed using axisymmetric compression tests using five model WHA with different tungsten content ranging from 80 to 98% by weight. Compression tests to a strain of ~ 0.69 showed a slight increase in yield strength with increase in tungsten content and similar strain hardening behaviour. The flow behaviour of the WHA during compression was analysed based on experimental evidence of shear band formation and failure of W-W interface. A double fiber texture $\langle 111 \rangle$ and $\langle 100 \rangle$ parallel to compression direction was observed in the tungsten phase whereas in f.c.c. matrix phase $\langle 110 \rangle$ fiber evolved. The effect of relative content of matrix was manifested in terms of increase in relative proportion of $\langle 100 \rangle$ fiber over the $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber. Texture simulation using mean field VPSC suggested that lattice co-rotation scheme considering the role of neighbouring orientations needs to be invoked to correctly replicate the experimental textures. The physical interpretation of the role of neighbours in increasing the $\langle 100 \rangle$ fiber is provided in terms of increasing contiguity of tungsten phase with increase in tungsten content, which in turn causes higher fluctuation

in lattice rotation path. Microstructural observation from EBSD indicated an increase in intragranular misorientation in the tungsten phase indicating stress and strain partitioning in the tungsten phase with increase in volume fraction. Strengthening of the matrix phase due to solid solution strengthening by tungsten followed with high strain hardening enables similar hardness of the matrix and tungsten phase that facilitates co-rotation leading to unique texture evolution in the tungsten and matrix phase.

In the second part of the work, deformation behaviour of WHA was analysed by changing the strain path from axisymmetric uniaxial compression to plane strain compression. A model WHA with composition 90W-10M (M-Matrix, Ni-Fe-W solid solution) was unidirectionally rolled to 90% rolling reduction corresponding to a true strain (ϵ) of -2.3 at room temperature. Samples were retained after 30%, 50%, 75% and 90% rolling reduction to perform comprehensive microstructural and textural characterisation. Neutron diffraction was used to measure the texture of both tungsten and matrix phase, while microstructural characterisation was performed using EBSD. At low to intermediate stages of deformation (30%-50% reduction), a strong α -fiber ($\langle 110 \rangle \parallel \text{RD}$) was observed in the tungsten phase, while a Copper type texture comprising of Copper ($\{11\bar{2}\}\langle 111 \rangle$), Brass ($\{1\bar{1}0\}\langle 112 \rangle$) and S ($\{12\bar{3}\}\langle 634 \rangle$) components were observed in the f.c.c. matrix phase. With the increase in rolling reduction beyond 75%, the evolution of γ -fiber and rotated cube was observed in the b.c.c. tungsten phase, while a systematic decrease in the intensity of Copper component and the simultaneous increase in the intensity of brass component was observed in the f.c.c. matrix phase. The microstructural analysis illustrated the presence of strong orientation gradients (heterogeneous slip) at intermediate rolling reductions and widespread occurrence of micro and macro shear bands at higher rolling reductions. Local texture analysis inside the shear bands highlighted the presence of texture components such as Goss and Brass along with significant dislocation activity manifested in terms of higher intragranular misorientation in both the phases. The texture evolution at different rolling reductions was analysed using both mean field (VPSC) and full field FFT based model (DAMASK), which in turn enabled the determination of stress and strain partitioning as well as the local plastic work in the two phases.

Based on the insights from the first two chapters where a substantial role of the matrix was observed on the deformation response of WHA, the subsequent chapters of the present thesis were focused on the deformation behaviour of relatively lesser-known f.c.c. matrix which is a concentrated ternary solid solution with a nominal composition of Ni-24W-22Fe solid solution. Like the previous chapters, the deformation behaviour was analysed along axisymmetric and plane strain compression strain paths. Axisymmetric deformation behaviour captured via real-time *in situ* EBSD studies provided crucial information about the role of neighbouring orientations on the deformation response of similarly oriented grains. It was observed that based on the characteristics of neighbours, the local velocity gradient of the individual grains deviated strongly from the externally imposed global velocity gradient, which in turn caused large scatter in lattice rotation path and the final stable end position in the orientation space. The experimental observation of the neighbour's role on the choice of slip systems and the resulting lattice rotation path was elegantly captured using full field model by using the real EBSD microstructure of the undeformed sample as input. Based on DAMASK simulations, the regimes in orientation space that are most susceptible to the effect of neighbours were determined.

In the last part of the thesis, deformation behaviour of the matrix was studied in the plane strain compression mode. A thorough characterisation of microstructure and texture was performed by retaining samples after 30%, 50%, 75% and 90% rolling reduction. It was observed that texture evolution in the matrix is quite rapid with a fully developed Copper type texture after 30%-50% rolling reduction. Subsequently, a texture transition from Copper type to Brass type was observed at higher rolling reductions (75%). EBSD analysis illustrated the occurrence of micro shear bands as well as macroscopic shear bands cutting across several grains through-thickness at higher rolling reductions. Local texture analysis was performed by partitioning the orientations present within the shear bands, which in turn highlighted the role played by shear bands in causing the texture transition from Copper type to Brass type. Full field simulations were also performed to determine the distribution of shears on the individual slip systems to identify the possible mechanisms such as slip localisation to determine the susceptibility of shear band formation in different

orientations.

Thus, a thorough understanding of deformation behaviour of WHA with particular emphasis on that of Ni-Fe-W solid solution matrix using mechanical testing, processing along with comprehensive microstructural and textural characterisation coupled with a full field and mean field crystal plasticity simulations has been developed. The critical role of slip localisation in the formation of shear bands and micro shear bands in the composite and matrix alloy has been established that is expected to shed light on strain localisation and failure in ductile two-phase alloys.

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Abbreviations

EBSD	electron backscatter diffraction
SEM	scanning electron microscope
WHA	tungsten heavy alloys
SPS	spark plasma sintering
ND	normal direction to the rolling plane
CD	compression direction
RD	rolling direction in a rolled plate
LD	Loading direction
TD	transverse direction in a rolled plate
XRD	X-ray diffraction
ODF	orientation distribution function
OM	optical microscope
IQ	image quality
IPF	inverse pole figure
FESEM	field emission scanning electron microscopy
f.c.c.	face centred cubic

b.c.c.	body centred cubic
EPMA	electron probe microanalyser
EDS	energy dispersive spectrometer
LPS	liquid phase sintering
FFT	fast Fourier transform
HEM	homogeneous effective medium
RVE	representative volume element
CRSS	critical resolved shear stress
PF	pole figure
VPSC	viscoplastic self-consistent
STECA	Stress Texture Calculator
DAMASK	Düsseldorf Advanced Material Simulation Kit
KAM	kernal average misorientation
GND	geometry necessary dislocation
GROD	grain reference orientation deviation
CAD	computer-aided design
AVACS	average number of active systems per grain
SRO	short range ordering
TWIP	twinning induced plasticity
TRIP	transformation induced plasticity
h.c.p.	hexagonal close packed
YS	yield strength

UTS	ultimate tensile strength
MSBs	micro-shear bands
DB	deformation bands
TB	transition bands
SFE	stacking fault energy
SHPB	split-Hopkinson pressure bar
ppm	parts per million
CES	Cambridge Engineering Selector
DBTT	ductile-to-brittle transition temperature
mrd	multiples of a random distribution
FWHM	full width at half maximum
CPFEM	crystal plasticity finite element methods
CPFFT	crystal plasticity fast Fourier transform-based
CMM	coordinate measuring machine
FEM	Finite element method
M^{micro}	micromechanical Taylor factor
M^{macro}	macromechanical Taylor factor
w.r.t	with respect to
S.D.	standard deviation
GBAZ	Grain boundary affected zone
CMWP	Convolution Multiple Whole Profile Fitting
LPA	Line profile analysis
OIM	orientation imaging microscopy

Symbols

γ_{ss}	solid-solid grain boundary energy
γ_{sl}	solid-liquid interfacial energy
\bar{L}	mean intercept length
V	Volume fraction
N_L	number of grain intercepts per unit length
R	true grain radius
C_g	contiguity
S_{ss}	solid-solid interfacial area
S_T	total solid surface area
N_{ss}	solid-solid intercept on N test lines
N_{sl}	solid-matrix intercept on N test lines
σ_{ij}	stress tensor
ε	strain tensor
b	Burgers vector
τ_{c0}	initial slip stress
ρ	dislocation density
μ	shear modulus of the material
θ	work hardening rate
θ_0	initial work hardening rate
θ	work hardening rate
ϕ_d	Dihedral angle

List of Publications

Publications from Thesis

1. Mirtunjay Kumar, N. P. Gurao, and Anish Upadhyaya. “Evolution of microstructure and crystallographic texture during cold rolling of liquid phase sintered tungsten heavy alloy.” *International Journal of Refractory Metals and Hard Materials* 105 (2022): 105849 [10.1016/j.ijrmhm.2022.105849](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrmhm.2022.105849).
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5. Mirtunjay Kumar, *et al.* “Incorporating latent hardening in visco-plastic self-consistent framework for performing texture simulations.” *Materials Science and Technology* 37.8 (2021): 752-764 [10.1080/02670836.2021.1946949](https://doi.org/10.1080/02670836.2021.1946949).
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7. Mirtunjay Kumar, and Sumeet Mishra. “Revisiting Taylor Factor Using Fast Fourier Transform Based Model and its Implications on Work Hardening.” Available at SSRN 4125910 [10.2139/ssrn.4125910](https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4125910).

This thesis is dedicated to my mother and late father, who both gave me the foundation for something that they could not avail: education.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background

Tungsten is an attractive and fascinating metal for designers, engineers and scientists because of its extraordinary and rare combination of physical properties, which includes high density (19.28 g/cm^3), high elastic modulus (400 GPa) and high melting temperature (3420 °C). Tungsten alloys occupy the upper right corner of Ashby's materials selection charts, which are plotted against young's modulus vs density in Figure 1.1. Cambridge Engineering Selector (CES), a commercially available computer programme, was used to build the diagram. It is important to note that the majority of charts used for material selection use logarithmic scales. This is due to the fact that material properties frequently cover large value ranges, and it is necessary to display the entire range of properties on one chart in order to make comparisons more easily. The specifics of material screening and the application of Ashby's chart or CES software can be found elsewhere [7]. When it comes to tungsten metal, processing difficulties and properties of pure tungsten [8], such as very low ductility at room temperature and poor weldability [9], have led researchers to conduct extensive research in an effort to develop a method of making tungsten alloys that will allow them to take advantage of most of its unique properties in a more simple and feasible manner. Consequently, modern powder metallurgical processing techniques have been used to produce mass product of tungsten and tungsten-based alloys since the early 1930s. Combining tungsten with nickel and copper allowed Price *et al.* [10] to be the first person to discover a way to produce tungsten-based alloys at temperatures that were astonishingly lower than the melting point of pure tungsten. This processing strategy was described by the formation of a liquid phase at a particular point of the heat treatment

FIGURE 1.1: Ashby plot for young's modulus vs density plotted using the CES.

cycle that was adopted; this process is referred to as liquid phase sintering. Following the success of this study, the researchers started focusing their efforts on the mechanical properties of these alloys [11, 12, 13]. Further studies resulted in the development of alloys based on tungsten with nickel and iron (W-Ni-Fe), and these alloys had improved mechanical properties [14].

The investigation of tungsten heavy alloys (WHA) has been focused mainly into two categories. One area of interest has been the sintering behaviour and microstructural evolution of W-Ni-Fe alloys. The mechanics of densification are well understood, and the effects of microstructural coarsening have been thoroughly investigated [15]. The mechanical behaviour of the alloy has been the subject of second area of investigation. There has been a wide range of strength and ductility values published for alloys that have similar compositions and which were processed by similar techniques. Almost all recent work in the field of mechanical properties has been focused on identifying the factors that are responsible for the observed variations in properties. In addition, current efforts have been directed at optimising and increasing the mechanical characteristics of the materials.

1.2 Motivation

The purpose of this thesis is to develop a foundational understanding of the deformation behaviour of the WHA and its matrix alloy for various deformation paths. This understanding will be useful in the fabricating the WHA with better performance in different applications. In order to achieve this goal, various heavy alloy composed of W-Ni-Fe was considered, and the deformation behaviour of these alloys was studied. The most reasonable alloy was further investigated for very high strain using cold rolling, and the critical role that binder composition plays in the onset of shear band formation was observed. Because of this finding, It was decided to look into the deformation behavior further. In order to get a better grasp on how the matrix behaves when subjected to deformation, matrix alloy was cast, without any tungsten particles. The matrix/binder alloy displayed several distinctive properties, including the restoration of work hardening, the onset of the formation of micro-shear bands (MSBs), and the presence of a new type of MSBs in the microstructure. This showcases that the WHA's performance in terms of penetrating obstacles and its mechanical behaviour have room for improvement. This suggests that the WHA may have a potential application for kinetic energy penetrators and, as a result, warrants further investigation.

1.3 Organization of the Thesis

This dissertation is structured into eight chapters, with the first chapter, [Introduction](#), provides a brief summary about the issues with WHA during the deformation and reasons the need for better mechanical properties. The justification for investing in the WHA and its matrix is another topic that is covered in this chapter. The chapter concludes with an explanation of the thesis' structure. The second chapter, [Literature review](#), is dedicated to a detailed literature review of the work's reference materials. This section provides an in-depth introduction to the alloy, including information on its fabrication as well as its properties and the constitution of the W-Ni-Fe system. There is also a discussion of the microstructure description and the mechanical behaviour that was reported by a community of researchers. In this section, we will also discuss the mechanisms of binder alloy deformation that have been reported up until this point. The third chapter, [Materials and Methods](#), provides information on the as-received starting powders, as well as the fabrication of WHA and matrix alloy, the experimental methods that were used during the course of the study, and the characterization techniques that were utilised,

such as scanning electron microscope (SEM), electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD), and X-ray diffraction (XRD), etc. In addition, the chapter describes the simulation of crystal plasticity and the visualisation techniques used to present the results.

In the fourth chapter, [Effect of Tungsten Content and Compression on Microstructure and Texture Evolution in WHA](#), the crystallographic texture development in uniaxial compression tests of WHA was systematically investigated by varying the tungsten content of the alloys. It was observed that the $\langle 100 \rangle$ fiber strengthens with increasing tungsten content, although the $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber remained as the strongest fiber in all the five compositions considered in the present work. The strengthening of $\langle 100 \rangle$ fibers with an increased tungsten content was understood by performing self-consistent texture simulations in combination with a lattice corotation scheme to account for the role of neighboring grain orientations in texture evolution. A physical justification of the role of the neighbors is given by the shift of the orientations around the $[110]$ - $[411]$ divergent line. The random fluctuations that originate from the neighbors displace the orientation from the above of divergent downwards, which in turn leads to the displaced grains rotating in the direction of the $\langle 100 \rangle$ corner.

In the fifth Chapter, [Texture and microstructure evolution during plane-strain compression of WHA](#), the evolution of microstructure and crystallographic texture of two-phase WHA during cold rolling was investigated systematically. EBSD analysis have revealed that the matrix phase is able to take on greater strain in the early stages of deformation. However, as the deformation process continues, the matrix phase exhausts its work hardening ability, which leads to the beginning of the development of MSBs. The tungsten phase on the other hand showed the presence of large orientation gradients accompanied with significant flattening and elongation of grains. At higher rolling reductions ($\varepsilon_{vm} = -2.66$), extensive shear bands spanning across several tungsten particles and the matrix were observed in microstructure, which in turn had implications on the evolution of the crystallographic texture. It was observed that weak $\alpha_{b.c.c.}$ ($\langle 110 \rangle \parallel$ RD) and γ fiber ($\langle 111 \rangle \parallel$ normal direction to the rolling plane (ND)) emerge in tungsten at low to intermediate rolling reductions, and that $\alpha_{b.c.c.}$ fiber strengthens much more than γ fiber at higher rolling reductions with prominent intensity at rotated cube position. For the matrix phase, a weak β fiber (fiber connecting the brass $\{011\}\langle 211 \rangle$, copper $\{112\}\langle 111 \rangle$, and S $\{123\}\langle 634 \rangle$ orientations in the Euler space) was observed at low to intermediate rolling reductions, followed by strengthening of Goss and Brass orientations at higher rolling reductions.

The sixth chapter, [Microstructure and texture evolution of matrix alloy during tensile test](#), investigates the microstructure, texture, and work hardening behavior of the hot rolled

and homogenized Ni-24W-22Fe alloy. This alloy has a single f.c.c. phase microstructure with some annealing twins. Upon tensile test, the alloy showed unconventional strain hardening behavior which was determined to occur due to transition from single slip to multiple slips. The bulk texture measurement also confirmed the evidence of planar slip during the early stage of deformation. To further ensure the transition in slip modes, i.e., single slip to multiple slips, *in-situ* electron backscatter diffraction was performed, and evidence of the occurrence of slip transition was shown by grains having rotation path toward $\langle 112 \rangle$ direction. Grains of similar orientation were picked and found to rotate in different directions. Some grains rotate toward $\langle 112 \rangle$, while others rotate toward $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction. The matrix alloy was further investigated in seventh chapter, [Microstructure and texture evolution of matrix alloy during Plain strain deformation](#). This chapter shows the onset of MSBs at 50% rolling reduction and its volume fraction increases rapidly upon further reduction. The texture transition from copper to Goss/Brass was observed at 50% to 75% rolling reduction. The experimental findings were explained with crystal plasticity simulation to emphasize the underlying micro-mechanisms that are operating in the matrix during deformation process. Finally, the last chapter, [Conclusions and future work](#), summarises and brings conclusion to the work, and it is followed by a discussion of the potential for future work.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Tungsten Heavy alloys

Even though metallic tungsten was first separated in 1783 [16], it wasn't until the early 1900s that it was widely used as an engineering material [17]. At that time, specialized processing methods were used to increase the tungsten's formability and, more often, its ductility. The sintering temperature for tungsten turned out to be 2800 °C or higher [18]. Sintering densification had been induced at that time with the application of a direct electrical discharge, which is also known as self-heating [18]. During the process of developing structures to contain radiation, it was discovered that tungsten can be sintered at a lower temperature. By 1938, the sintering temperature for W-Ni and W-Ni-Cu alloys had reached one 1450 °C when liquid phase sintering (LPS) was used. In contrast with pure tungsten, these materials can be conventionally machined and are cheaper [19].

2.2 Heavy Alloy Production and Properties

Price *et al.* (1938) [10] published the first detailed description of the manufacturing procedures and unique combination of attributes of WHA. They sintered compositions of tungsten, nickel, and Copper powders at temperatures high enough to cause the formation of a liquid phase, and the liquid phase caused fast densification and grain growth in the sintered materials. Despite the fact that the W-Ni-Cu alloy received little attention owing to its poor mechanical properties but still in production when ferromagnetism is to be avoided in the alloy, this discovery opened the door to a new class of materials: WHA,

which can be manufactured at temperatures far lower than those necessary to sinter pure tungsten. A series of W-Ni-Fe alloys comprising 75 to 97 weight% tungsten were developed by Green and coworkers [14] in the 1950s, and their production techniques and characteristics were documented in a paper published in 1954. The W-Ni-Fe alloys exhibited superior mechanical properties because (i) W-Ni-Fe alloys consolidate in a small temperature range, which prevents microsegregation in the final product, and (ii) High interfacial strength of the tungsten-matrix as a result of the solid solution strengthening provided by the dissolved tungsten; however, this can be affected by impurities. These findings were validated by Jones and Munnery [20]. The W-Ni-Fe alloys exhibited potential for elongations up to 20% and tensile strengths close to 900 MPa. With these mechanical properties combined with densities of 19.3 g/cm³ (theoretical density of tungsten), heavy alloys are well suited for a variety of applications, including radiation shields, counterweights, kinetic energy armour piercing penetrators, vibration dampeners, and heavy-duty electrical connections [21, 22, 23]. Tungsten content in usable heavy alloys typically varies from 80 to 98% by weight. Using alloys with greater tungsten content is typically favourable due to their increased density and radiation absorption capabilities. With high tungsten contents, processing challenges are often experienced; they were recently highlighted by German *et al.* [24]. In carefully processed alloys, tensile strengths of almost 1000 MPa and elongations of more than 30% have been achieved at room temperature [25].

2.3 Constitution of the W-Ni-Fe System

Raynor and Rivlin [26, 27] contributed to the understanding of the W-Ni-Fe system's composition. The liquidus projection of the W-Ni-Fe system is shown in Figure 2.1. In this figure, α represents the Fe-rich body centred cubic (b.c.c.) solid solution, γ represents the Ni-Fe-rich face centred cubic (f.c.c.) solid solution, and μ represents the binary Fe_7W_6 phase compound. At 1448 °C, a saddle point occurs with a composition of 40% Fe, 20% W, and 40% Ni. It melts around 1435 °C with a Ni:Fe weight ratio close to 7:3.

The tungsten phase hardly dissolves 0.1-0.4% by weight nickel and iron [2, 28]. Figure 2.2 shows isothermal sections of the W-Ni-Fe phase diagram at temperatures of 1450 °C, 1100 °C, and 800 °C. In this figure, the binary compound NiW_2 is referred to as δ and the compound Ni_4W is referred as ϵ . The liquid phase is stable at 1435 °C, although higher temperatures are required if the Ni:Fe ratio deviates significantly from the minimum melting composition of 7Ni:3Fe. If the ratio Ni:Fe is smaller than the ratio 3:7, the formation of the iron rich intermetallic Fe_7W_6 is possible. At this temperature, no

FIGURE 2.1: The liquidus projection in the W-Ni-Fe system (Adapted with permission [1]).

intermetallic phases are stable in high tungsten content alloys with a Ni:Fe ratio higher than about 7:3. The only binary Fe-W compound expected to form in equilibrium below around 1100 °C is Fe_7W_6 , which can form when the ratio of Ni to Fe is less than about 2:3. For larger Ni/Fe ratios, there is an equilibrium between W and γ solid solution. Tungsten solubility in the γ phase is strongly influenced by the Ni/Fe ratio; solubility increases with increased Ni concentration. The binary NiW compound is stable below 1050 °C and forms solid solutions with Fe_7W_6 . The phase diagram indicates that intermetallic precipitation occurs at 800 °C for all Ni/Fe ratios. Ni_4W may also be formed in addition to Fe_7W_6 and NiW.

In the case of heavy alloys having more than 80% tungsten by weight, it seems that intermetallic phase formation beyond 1050 °C is unlikely to occur for Ni:Fe ratios greater than 2:3. W-Ni-Fe heavy alloys with a Ni/Fe ratio of 7:3 have been shown to have the best

FIGURE 2.2: Isothermal sections of the W -Ni-Fe phase diagram at 1450 °C, 1100 °C and 800 °C (Adapted with permission [1]).

mechanical properties when this ratio is used [29, 30, 31]. The phase diagram explains these observations based on the intermetallic phase formation.

Figure 2.3 shows the isopleth of the W-Ni-Fe phase diagram with a Ni:Fe ratio of 7:3. Gurwell [3] developed this diagram after studying the ternary phase diagrams. This plot indicates that solidification would occur over a temperature range of approximately 20 °C, supporting discovery of the absence of microsegregation in these alloys by Green *et al.* [14]. Tungsten solubility in the matrix varies with temperature, reaching 32 weight% at 1450 °C and falling to 20 weight% at 1100 °C. This reduction in solubility shows that tungsten may precipitate in the matrix following cooling or heat treatment. Some researchers have seen tungsten precipitation following particular ageing treatments [28, 3, 32], although this has not been found in most experiments. The small diffusion distance between tungsten grains in the normal microstructure most likely causes the tungsten to precipitate onto the surface of existing tungsten grains. For this Ni to Fe ratio, no intermetallic phases are stable beyond 1050 °C, however the synthesis of (Ni,Fe)W is feasible on cooling below this temperature. It has been shown that this intermetallic compound can form when the sintering temperature is not cooled quickly enough or when heat treatment is done below 1050 °C [29, 33, 34, 35]. Other researchers, even after thorough heat treatment, have been unable to detect any evidence of the formation of this intermetallic [3, 36, 37, 38].

FIGURE 2.3: Isopleth of the W-Ni-Fe phase diagram for a nickel to iron ratio of 7:3 (Adapted with permission [1]).

2.4 Microstructure Description

The microstructure of b.c.c. tungsten particles embedded in a f.c.c. solid solution matrix is characteristic of liquid-phase sintered WHA. A typical microstructure of the WHA obtained during the study is shown in Figure 2.4. The microstructural features such as tungsten content, grain size, aspect ratio of grains, connectivity, contiguity and dihedral angle plays an important influence in the mechanical properties of the alloy.

2.4.1 Volume Fraction

Traditionally, the volume fraction is the most critical microstructural parameter influencing the behaviour of two-phase materials. In most cases, volume fraction measurements on a metallographic cross section are performed using point counting or area fraction analysis

FIGURE 2.4: Typical microstructure of liquid phase sintered tungsten heavy alloy.

techniques. Various discussions regarding the various techniques for estimating volume fraction may be found in the literature [39, 40].

The alloy composition and manufacturing conditions influence the tungsten volume fraction. Tungsten content ranging from 80 to 98% by weight often results in a volume fraction of the tungsten phase in the range of approximately 0.7 to 0.95% by volume. Figure 2.5 illustrates some of the volume fractions reported in the literature for several heavy alloys as a function of the tungsten content [2, 30, 3, 34]. While all of the reported values are reasonably consistent, the data form a broad scatter band. Variations in the Ni to Fe ratio, sintering temperature, cooling rate from the sintering temperature, and post-sintering heat treatment may all cause differences in the volume fractions. Unfortunately, due to the low amounts of information available, it is difficult to determine the relative weight that should be given to each of these parameters, particularly given the significant variations in processing between the studies that have been conducted. It has yet to be established how volume fraction influences properties, although variances like those seen in Figure 2.5 might be responsible.

FIGURE 2.5: Reported values for the volume fraction of tungsten as a function of tungsten content. (Adapted with permission [2, 3]).

2.4.2 Dihedral Angle

The dihedral angle, ϕ_d , is defined as the angle between the two connecting solid-solid grains, and it is responsible for maintaining a balance between the solid-solid and solid-liquid interfacial energies. When it comes to the liquid phase sintered microstructure, it is a critical variable since it influences the shape of the solid grains as well as the numbers and dimensions of grain-to-grain interactions. The ϕ_d of monosized spherical grains is defined as the ratio of the solid-solid grain boundary energy, γ_{ss} , to the solid-liquid interfacial energy γ_{sl} .

$$\phi_d = 2 \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\gamma_{ss}}{2\gamma_{sl}} \right) \quad (2.1)$$

FIGURE 2.6: Variation in the ϕ_d with respect to the critical solid content that is necessary for the retention of structural rigidity (Adapted with permission [4])

The ϕ_d formed at the sintering temperature cannot be determined; instead, it is measured using the microstructure of the sintered alloy. Although there is no direct way to measure the ϕ_d on a two-dimensional cross section, it has been shown that the median ϕ_d calculated from micrographs is the most reasonable approximation [41, 42].

Figure 2.6 illustrates the change in the ϕ_d that occurs when the amount of critical solid content that is necessary to preserve the structural integrity is increased. In addition, it was discovered that low solid solubility, small grain size, and a high ϕ_d and connectivity restrict distortion, and that the critical solid content required to maintain structural rigidity is related to particular combinations of ϕ_d and grain connectivity [4, 43]. According to the figure, compacts that have a high ϕ_d ($>30^\circ$) are structurally stable and do not distort during the sintering process.

2.4.3 Grain Size and Shape

2.4.3.1 Grain Size

The mechanisms of microstructural coarsening and grain shape accommodation that occur during the phase sintering of WHA have been extensively studied [44, 45, 46]. The coarsening of the microstructure is attributable to the solution-precipitation and coalescence processes. During LPS, a stable grain size distribution is typically achieved; however, for a given temperature and amount of time, the average grain size grows in proportion to the volume percent of solid phase.

2.4.3.2 Grain Shape

The surface energy anisotropy and volume fraction of solid all play a role in determining the shape of the grains. The grains become flatter as a result of interactions with their adjacent grains. The effect is felt most strongly when there is a relatively low amount of liquid present. When tungsten content is low, the single crystal grains of tungsten in the heavy alloys have a rounded form, which is close to a spherical shape. Higher volume fractions of solid tend to have flattened faces where neighbouring grains have made contact [47, 48, 49]. The change in grain shape promotes solid phase packing and minimizes porosity for low ϕ_d and large solid volume fractions. When there is a significant amount of solid solubility in the liquid, the solution-precipitation process is able to accommodate grain shape more easily. The equilibrium grain shape has been investigated by a number of researchers [50, 51, 52]. With an increase in the volume fraction of solid approaching one, solid grains begin to resemble the grains of a single-phase polycrystal. In general, for large volume fractions of solid and ϕ_d greater than 60° , the liquid phase is confined to grain edges and does not permeate across the solid phase. Alternatively, with low volume fractions of solid and/or lower ϕ_d , it is anticipated that a continuous liquid network will form.

For grains with isotropic solid-liquid surface energy (γ_{sl}) and liquid contents higher than 30% by volume, all surfaces besides the contact faces are spherical. The grains will assume a prismatic structure when there is a relatively low volume of liquid available, and the liquid will fill up the spaces that are present between the grains when this occurs. When liquid levels are low, there is not enough liquid to fill all of the pores because there is insufficient liquid present. Because of this, the grains need to go through a process called "shape accommodation" in order for the densification to take place. Because of the coarsening

FIGURE 2.7: (a) Grain shape of tungsten at full density forming flat face but rounded shape, but matrix forming rounded polyhedron (b) Variation in grain shape associated with anisotropic surface energy (c) Shape of the liquid and its connectivity as a function of the liquid content and the dihedral angle (Adapted with permission [5]).

that occurs during the LPS process, the particle form that existed before the process has no major influence on the grain shape that is produced by the sintered product.

2.4.4 Contiguity

The contiguity and connectivity of the tungsten heavy alloys are extremely important for the mechanical properties due to the nature of the brittle fracture and the weak tungsten-tungsten interface. These interfaces are often the first point of failure. The term “contiguity” refers to the area of solid-solid contact in a material [53]. The contiguity, abbreviated C_g , is defined as follows:

$$C_g = \frac{S_{ss}}{S_T} \quad (2.2)$$

Where S_{ss} denotes the solid-solid interfacial area and S_T denotes the total solid surface area. Metallographically, contiguity is determined by counting the number of intercepts per unit length of test lines, N , where:

$$C_g = \frac{2N_{ss}}{2N_{ss} + N_{sl}} \quad (2.3)$$

the solid-solid and solid-liquid interfaces are denoted by subscript *ss* and *sl*, respectively.

German [54] estimated the contiguity of liquid phase sintered microstructures as a function of the volume fraction of solids and the ϕ_d in a liquid phase sintered structure. The measure of contiguity rises as the volume fraction of solids increases and the ϕ_d increases. At a certain ϕ_d , the contiguity with solid content increases slowly as the volume fraction of solids decreases. Contiguity grows rapidly with increasing volume fractions, reaching the limiting value of 1 for a single-phase solid.

So far, contiguity values for heavy alloys have only been published for certain microstructures [24, 53, 55, 56, 57, 58]. The reported values are compared in Table 1. O’Neil and Salyer [59] reported the contiguity as a function of volume fraction under a given processing conditions; however, comparing their findings to those of others is challenging since these authors fail to show a correlation between the alloy’s tungsten content and the volume fraction. Additionally, direct comparisons of the other data are complicated by the unreported variation in the ϕ_d and volume fraction. Contiguity is believed to be influenced by the same factors that could affect the ϕ_d and volume fraction, such as composition, impurities, and sintering temperature.

2.4.5 Connectivity

Another key microstructural characteristic is connectivity, which is defined by the number of solid-solid contacts per solid grain. The presence of a non-zero ϕ_d during the LPS results in the formation of solid-solid contacts. The development of these contacts results in the formation of a rigid solid skeleton. Connectivity, like contiguity, increases with solid volume fraction and is affected by ϕ_d . Niemi [60] reported that the volume fraction was the sole factor that influenced the number of two-dimensional contacts for each grain. German [61], on the other hand, has recently estimated the two-dimensional connectivity as a function of ϕ_d and volume fraction. If a ϕ_d of around 30° is considered, the experimental results by Niemi are in good agreement with the German predictions.

2.5 Mechanical Behavior of WHA

2.5.1 Processing Effects on Properties

The mechanical behavior of WHA have been extensively researched over the past few decades. When properly manufactured, the alloys can achieve tensile strengths of close to 1000 MPa and elongations of more than 30% in the material. In addition, it has been shown that inadequate processing can lead to a material with poor strength and ductility properties. During a tensile test, for example, highly embrittled alloys often break in the clamps in the elastic zone due to their embrittlement. Because of the sensitivity of the traits to processing variability, the majority of studies have focused on isolating and mitigating adverse effects on the traits. The processing paths that have to be followed in order to achieve high strengths and, above all, sufficient ductility, are now better known [62]. Figure 2.8 and Figure 2.9 shows the effect of different sintering atmosphere and cooling rates for 95W-(7:3)Ni-Fe alloy on ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and ductility of the Variations in strength and ductility documented in the literature have been associated with residual porosity, segregation of impurities, hydrogen embrittlement, intermetallic phase formation, brittle-to-ductile transition temperature, tungsten precipitation in the matrix, and insufficient oxide reduction. During the sintering process, a reducing atmosphere provided by H_2 contributes to the removal of O_2 content. Because the reducing power of H_2 is significantly higher at the sintering temperature than it is at the pre-reduction temperature, the majority of the oxygen is eliminated during this stage of the process [63].

FIGURE 2.8: Effect of processing parameter of a 95 wt.% WHA with various atmosphere and cooling rate (Adapted with permission [6]).

It is now clear that each of the attribute listed above can have an influence on the properties of heavy alloys. The full densification of the alloy is one of the most important criteria for satisfactory mechanical properties. The ductility of heavy alloys is dramatically reduced by residual porosity, even at values on the order of 0.5%. A gas trapped in the pores can cause final porosity for long sintering time due coarsening of the pores. Microporosity can also be caused by solidification shrinkage if cooling occurs too rapidly during solidification above the solidification temperature range. The pore closure is supported by vacuum sintering or the integration of pore degassing into the sintering cycle. The solidification shrinkage is reduced to a minimum by slow cooling over the entire solidification temperature range [64].

The sulfur and phosphorus segregation at the tungsten-matrix interface is detrimental. These elements, which are present in concentrations on the order of 50 parts per million (ppm), embrittle the tungsten-matrix interface and provide a low-energy fracture path. The segregation of contaminants can be reduced by controlling the quality of the powder supplied and rapidly cooling it through the intermediate temperature range when segregation is most prone to occur. Impurity can be further reduced further by vacuum sintering

FIGURE 2.9: Effect of processing parameter of a 95 wt.% WHA with various atmosphere and cooling rate (Adapted with permission [6]).

or heat treatment. The influence of hydrogen embrittlement in heavy alloys has been shown by various researcher. Hydrogen, like other detrimental impurities, has a tendency to segregate at the tungsten-matrix contact, resulting in a low energy fracture path. The removal of hydrogen from the sample during the sintering cycle or during the heat treatment after the sintering must take place under vacuum or inert gas since heavy alloys must always be sintered in a hydrogen atmosphere [65]. With certain heavy alloys, it has been shown that intermetallic phase precipitations occur in the matrix phase and at the tungsten-matrix interface. The strength and ductility of the alloy are significantly reduced due to the presence of brittle phases at the tungsten-matrix interface. Precipitations have been discovered in W-Ni-Cu alloys as well as W-Ni-Fe alloys with Ni to Fe ratios less than or equal to about 1:1. It has been shown that the use of high Ni-Fe ratios, such as 7:3, and rapid cooling from temperatures above 1050 °C, prevents the formation of intermetallic phases [66].

The ductile-to-brittle transition temperature (DBTT) for heavy alloys is around room temperature. This transition occurs at a temperature far below that of pure tungsten. Since the transition from ductile to brittle behaviour takes place over a wide temperature

range, it is unlikely that slight temperature variations near room temperature will have a significant influence on the properties. The mechanical behaviour would be drastically affected if the tests were carried out at low temperatures or at temperatures above about 200 °C [67].

Finally, the role of oxygen in the properties of heavy alloys has lately been questioned. WHA can be affected by oxygen in a number of ways. For example, the presence of oxygen during LPS in dry hydrogen environments can lead to the formation of water vapour. Water vapour is insoluble in the liquid matrix and can therefore precipitate as tiny gas bubbles, which ultimately become coarser and lead to low sintered densities. Incomplete oxide reduction, on the other hand, can lead to the formation of interfacial oxide films, which can weaken the interface. After all, it is known that oxygen influences the wetting behaviour in solid-liquid metal systems. Due to changes in the solid-liquid interfacial energy, changes in the ϕ_d are inevitable, which lead to differences in the microstructure and properties [68].

Fine-grained WHA were manufactured using spark plasma sintering (SPS) technique, a method of sintering powder materials at a rapid rate that involves exerting mechanical pressure to the powder compact and heating it with a pulsed direct current, by various researcher [69, 70]. The SPS products are reported to have inhomogenous properties in the radial direction due to radial temperature fluctuations [71] and thus inferior properties. Li *et al.* [72] showed the SPS can lead to improved bending strength and yield strength (YS) as W-W contact area viz. contiguity, can be increased significantly up 53% of contiguity. However, due to high contiguity leads to brittle fracture. Senthilnathan *et al.* [73] studied the effect of cobalt addition in W-Ni-Fe WHA system fabricated through SPS process. They showed that cobalt addition can result in good W-matrix interface and enhanced tensile strength upto 1508 MPa. The influence of various alloying elements like as hafnium carbide (HfC) [74], rhenium (Re) [75], and molybdenum (Mo) [76] on WHA consolidation is a topic under research.

2.5.2 Deformation Behavior

Several researchers have studied on the deformation of WHA. Krock and Shepard [30] and Krock showed that the flow stress of the composite was independent of the tungsten content and the mean free path of the matrix for tungsten contents ranging from 58 to 80% by volume. The flow stress was found to be temperature dependent in the same way as b.c.c. tungsten. The authors concluded that if the matrix phase could be strengthened

to an extent sufficient for the deformation of the tungsten without failure by the additional hydrostatic stress component, the composite deformation can be determined solely by the deformation of the harder tungsten phase.

It has been shown that the flow stress at low strains depends on the tungsten content, but according to O'Neil and Salyer [59] it becomes independent of the volume fraction after a few percent strains. The matrix phase was found to undergo a rapid initial work hardening which increased its flow stress to the same level as the tungsten phase, whereupon both phases deformed simultaneously.

Gurland and Parikh [77] observed that the YS of the composite increased as the amount of tungsten in the composite increased. The microhardness of the matrix along with the tungsten content, and the authors hypothesised that this was due to a decrease in tungsten particle separation in the matrix. WHA were deformed to 0.1% strain, and it was discovered that the deformation occurred primarily within the matrix at 85% by weight tungsten, while the deformation occurred within the tungsten grains as well as the matrix at 94% by weight tungsten.

Votava [78] showed that the deformation began in the matrix and then subsequently propagated throughout the composite. The appearance of undulating slip lines within the tungsten grains indicated the presence of triaxial stress conditions that promoted cross slip in the tungsten grains. The unexpected ductility of individual tungsten grains was attributed to the existence of a radial compressive stress component perpendicular to the tensile axis. Radial compressive stresses around an elastically deforming particle within a plastically deforming matrix were expected. Because of the significant plastic deformation that occurs in both phases of heavy alloys, the presence and magnitude of any radial compressive stress component are unclear. Kiran *et al.* [79] examined the increase in microhardness in each phase according to different degrees of deformation. After 6% strain, the matrix reached its maximum value, and after 12% strain, the tungsten reached its maximum value. These results suggest that at low stresses the deformation was confined to the matrix, but homogenous deformation was observed at higher strains. Gero *et al* [80] showed in their investigations that the deformation of individual tungsten grains comes close to that of the composite material. In addition, these authors concluded that the initial strain was mainly localized within the matrix, which was subsequently work-hardened to a level sufficient to deform the tungsten. The behaviour of the composite phase then began to resemble that of the tungsten phase.

In addition to the investigations that were carried out directly on heavy alloys, there were attempts to investigate the deformation behaviour of coarse two-phase structures. Studies on a variety of two-phase materials have shown that the empirical rule of mixtures can in many cases accurately predict the strength of the composite. In their review of the deformation of two-phase microstructures, behaviour of most of two-phase alloys can be satisfactorily described by an empirical mixture rule which distributes both stresses and strains in the ratio of the volume fractions of the phases present in the alloy. The studies [81] showed that Finite element method (FEM) computations using actual microstructures can correctly describe the phase and composite deformation. The researchers concluded that the load transfer between the phases was the most important aspect in determining properties of the aggregate. Increases in the excess of strain in the soft phase (and in the stresses in the hard phase) were observed when the ratio of flow stresses increased, while decreases were observed when the volume fraction of the hard phase decreased.

It was found that W-Cu composites materials with a continuous skeleton and those with fiber-reinforced skeletons have similar properties. The skeletonized W-Cu composites have a microstructure that is remarkably comparable to the microstructure of heavy alloys. Krock [82] discovered that the ultimate tensile strength of the alloys followed a rule of mixtures. It was also found that the work hardening coefficients were quite high, especially at the beginning of the deformation process. This indicated that the Cu matrix yielded first, followed by the gross yield of the composite. Based on this explanation, it is not known why a similar trend was not observed in the WHA; earlier authors have shown that the flow properties beyond a few percent strain are independent of the tungsten content. It is possible that the *in-situ* flow curves for the tungsten and the matrix are quite similar, making it difficult to see the small variation that result from a typical volume fraction variation.

The deformation of two-phase alloys has been studied by a number of authors. In most cases the focus has been put on alloys that contain small volume fractions (less than 50%) of elastically deforming particles that are embedded in a ductile matrix. In contrast to heavy alloys, the microstructure and mechanical properties of these alloys differ significantly; hence, the result of these research are not very applicable. In the past, the deformation of alloys containing large volume percentages of hard phase has mostly been explored in terms of so-called hard metals such as WC-Co. There are numerous reviews on this subject [83, 84, 85]. In general, the relationships between microstructure and properties in cemented carbides are well understood. Plotted against binder volume percent or carbide particle size, for example, the transverse rupture strength of cemented carbides usually

shows a maximum. The origins of the strength maxima are still puzzling, although they are often associated with a transition in the fracture behaviour. In spite of the fact that cemented carbides and heavy alloys have very similar microstructures in terms of the distribution of binder and reinforcement, and the shape of the major phase in each alloy is very different from the other, there are distinct differences in the deformation behaviour of the two alloy. The ductile matrix phase of cemented carbides is limited by the carbide grains, which mainly deform elastically. The amount of plastic constraints present and the associated increase in the flow strength of the matrix were significantly investigated. In contrast to heavy alloys, cemented carbides often only experience a few percent plastic strain before tensile failure occurs. While there are differences in terms of microstructures and fracture mechanisms, there are some similarities.

Hafizoğlu *et al.* [86] used Taylor impact experiments at various impact velocities to investigate the effect of sintering temperature on the dynamic behavior of WHA. To compare their results, Taylor impact simulations were also done according to the FEM and the Smooth Particle Hydrodynamics method, and revealed the accurate description of the fracture behavior of the materials during impact testing. Hafizoğlu *et al.* in another study [87] used Johnson-Cook failure model to predict the deformation at the impact and rear surfaces of the target during perforation. Zhou *et al.* [88] numerically analyzed the shear band development in WHA. They showed that Experiments and the numerical calculations show that the two phase alloy is more susceptible to shear banding than either of the constituent phases. Krátká [89] performed a simulation based on the Haensel-Spittel relation to anticipate the behaviour of the W-Ni-Co WHA during rotary swaging. They revealed that material flow throughout the process is quite complicated and it flows in both the directions from neutral plane positioned in the reduction zone of dies. Tand *et al.* [90] investigated the static and dynamic mechanical properties of W-Ni-Fe-Co system and simulated with Khan–Huang–Liang phenomenological based constitutive model. The flow stress behavior of these alloys was studied using Sharma’s *et al.* [91] processing map, which incorporates the effects of applied strain (ε_{vm}), strain rate $\dot{\varepsilon}$, and temperature (T). Four constitutive models, namely, modified Johnson-Cook, modified Zerilli-Armstrong, modified Arrhenius and modified Khan-Huan-Liang models was taken into consideration to predict the flow behavior. They concluded that temperature range of 427 - 627 °C and for higher strain rates (2500 - 4000 s^{-1}) efficiency was maximum at $\varepsilon_{vm} = 0.16$. Kocich *et al.* [92] studied the deformation behaviour of cold rotary swaged W-Ni-Co alloy. They were able to able the high swagging force requirement and development of <110> fibers. Gong *et al.* [93] did a short study on the microstructure and texture evolution during rapid hot extrusion and showed the evolution of <110> fiber even in single pass. Li *et*

al. [94] evolution of microstructure and texture in warm-rolled fine-grained tungsten with different rolling reduction. A clear texture γ fiber and θ fiber with elongated grains were obtained following warm rolling of WHA. The texture types continue to vary because of the continual change in rolling reduction. Strong θ fiber texture was seen in tungsten after 50% rolling reduction, and strong γ fiber texture was observed in tungsten after 60% and 70% rolling reduction, respectively.

Jinglian *et al.* [95] examined the WHA with fine particle size and showed better mechanical properties and the development of early shear band formation during ballistic impact. Das *et al.* [96] showed that these alloys can withstand up to 70% of deformation without cracking even at 400 °C. The deformation behavior also depends on the strain rate and the temperature and flow stress increases with increasing strain rate and decreasing test temperature [97, 98]. Significant flow softening was a characteristic observation when the grain size of the alloy was reduced to a few micrometers [99]. Yu *et al.* [100] and Zhang *et al.* [101] investigated the hot extrusion of WHA alloys, which led to an improvement in ultimate tensile strength and hardness but a decrease in ductility. In practice, the WHA alloys are mainly subjected to compression deformation. Therefore, most of the work in earlier studies has focused on understanding the deformation behavior under compression in relation to the mechanical properties (work hardening rate, strain rate sensitivity) [100]. However, the evolution of the crystallographic texture during uniaxial compression tests was not taken into account. It is known that the mechanical properties are considerably dependent on the crystallographic texture [102]. It was shown that an improvement in the mechanical properties can be achieved through suitable texture engineering. The relationship between processing, texture and mechanical properties is also missing in WHA for different phase fractions of tungsten. Therefore, it is of the utmost importance to systematically study the texture evolution during the uniaxial compression of WHA in order to understand the governing deformation mechanism. The texture evolution of single-phase b.c.c. has been extensively investigated by many researchers in the past [103, 104]. However, very little information is available for two-phase alloys, particularly for WHA.

In terms of studying the deformation behaviour of WHA, the spectrum spans from the dynamic strain ageing [105], residual stresses due to swaging [106], dynamic deformation behaviour [107], compression behaviour at different temperatures and strain rates [58], tensile properties [58] and brittle to ductile transition phenomena [108]. However, with respect to understanding the mushroom head formation, flow behaviour and work hardening are of paramount importance. In the recent work of Panchal *et al.* [109], true stress versus

true strain curves of sintered WHA shows the existence of two slope on $\log - \log$ scale and found to follow Ludwigson constitutive equation while cold worked WHA displays single slope and adheres to typical Swift constitutive equation. A recent study by Sharma *et al.* [91] analysed the various constitutive models for WHA and found that modified Zerilli-Armstrong model performs significantly better compared to other empirical models such as Swift, Ludwigson and Hollomon.

Apart from cold deformation, the deformation behaviour of WHA has also been studied at elevated temperatures and varying strain rates. Lee *et al.* [97] studied the hot flow behaviour of W-Ni-Fe heavy alloy. The flow behaviour was modelled using Arrhenius equation allowing the prediction of plastic response of the WHA. Dummer *et al.* [110] subjected the polycrystalline tungsten to different strain rates and showed that the flow stress can be described by Mechanical Threshold Stress model. It was also observed by Dummer *et al.* [110] that the increase in strain rate from 10^{-3} to 10^3 s^{-1} causes ductile to brittle transition due to strong strain rate sensitivity.

Lennon and Ramesh [111] carried out dynamic compression tests on pure tungsten by systematically varying temperature, strain rate and microstructure and obtained the parameters for Johnson-Cook and Zerilli-Armstrong models. Wang *et al.* [112] established the stability and instability domains of the pure polycrystalline tungsten in hot plastic deformation. The stability domain was observed to be around a temperature $1300 - 1450 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and strain rate of $10^{-3} - 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Lee *et al.* [98] carried out the compression split-Hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB) test in order to gain a better understanding of the effects that strain rate and temperature have on the dynamic impact deformation behavior of WHA. It was observed that there is a linear dependence of flow stress with $\log(\text{strain})$ in the temperature range of $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $1100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Apart from empirical mechanical behaviour of WHA and alloying strategy, the evolution of crystallographic texture has also been explored by few researchers. Zhang and Mao [113] and Bonk *et al.* [114] studied texture evolution during cold rolling of polycrystalline tungsten. Zhang and Mao [113] showed that reaction stress model provides a reasonable explanation of the cold rolling texture of tungsten plates. Further analysis of texture evolution was done by Bonk *et al.* [114] by analysing the evolution of rotated Cube component $\{001\} \langle 110 \rangle$ at higher rolling reductions at high temperature. It was observed that dynamic recovery was the governing parameter behind the evolution of rotated Cube component. It should be noted that the increase in rotated Cube component comes at the expense of $\{111\} \langle 112 \rangle$ component along the γ fiber [115]. Texture evolution has also been investigated under extreme conditions such as high pressure of $>35 \text{ GPa}$. It

was observed that a strong $\langle 001 \rangle$ fiber developed during compression at high pressure, whereas normal $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber forms at low pressure (<35 GPa) [116].

As can be observed in the previous paragraphs, most of the works has been done in an empirical framework with little consideration of the operative slip systems and the mode of deformation. Therefore, there is a need to further explore the deformation and texture evolution of WHA and interpret the results in the framework of crystal plasticity. Crystal plasticity can provide a clear picture of the mode of deformation in the WHA which is crucial for designing new generation WHA with enhanced properties. In this regard, a systematic experimental study based on measurement of pole figure (PF) and EBSD was carried out after different levels of rolling reduction to decipher the operative deformation micromechanisms in terms of slip system and development of microstructural features. The experimental study is also suitably complemented by self-consistent texture simulations via viscoplastic self-consistent (VPSC) package. In order to perform the the second chapter, 90W-7Ni-3Fe WHA was chosen as a model material.

2.5.3 Fracture Behaviour

2.5.3.1 Processing Effects

Several studies have examined at the fracture behaviour of W-Ni-Fe composite alloys [117, 118, 119]. There are four different fracture paths for the microstructure of a heavy alloy. Figure 2.10 shows a schematic representation of them. In general, all four types of failure can be found on the fracture surfaces of tensile specimens. It has been shown that the preferred type of failure, as assessed by the percentage of area that each fracture type occupies on the fracture surface, depends essentially on the circumstances under which the material is processed. In the case of alloys with low strength and ductility, a significant interfacial separation between tungsten-matrix can be measured. This condition occurs when the interface is weak, and this weakness is often related to impurity segregation, hydrogen embrittlement, or the precipitation of intermetallic phase precipitates.

However, all alloys with high strength and ductility show no evidence of interfacial separation between the tungsten and matrix. These fracture surfaces are characterized by a high proportion of transgranular tungsten cleavage and ductile rupture of the matrix. There is evidence of intergranular failure in tungsten on all fracture surfaces, indicating that these interfaces fail easily under all of the alloying conditions evaluated. In general, processing variables have the greatest impact on the fracture behaviour of heavy alloys because they

FIGURE 2.10: Schematic heavy alloy microstructure showing the four possible fracture paths (1) grain failure (2) matrix failure (3) grain-matrix separation (4) Grain-grain separation.

change the strength of their tungsten-matrix interface, which is the most important factor to consider when designing heavy alloys.

2.5.3.2 Microstructural Effects

German *et al.* [24] recently illustrated the effect that tungsten contiguity has on mechanical properties by using the highest recorded values of strength and elongation values for several different heavy alloys. German *et al.* [24] did this to show how tungsten contiguity affects mechanical properties. The ultimate tensile strength and elongation were both diminished as the contiguity of the material was increased. At temperatures up to about 150 °C, pure polycrystalline tungsten typically exhibits a brittle behaviour. When exposed to temperatures at or below room temperature, tungsten will fail in an intergranular manner. This failure will involve very little or no plastic deformation. The fracture

strengths for this kind of failure range from approximately 550 MPa to approximately 620 MPa; these values are most indicative of the strength of the tungsten-tungsten grain boundaries. The intergranular fracture of tungsten has been linked to impurity segregation at the grain boundaries. For instance, research has shown that a phosphorus concentration of approximately 50 parts per million (ppm) at the grain boundaries is enough to raise the DBTT temperature by approximately 150 °C.

Ductile behaviour of tungsten is observed at temperatures above the DBTT temperature of tungsten. In these cases, the fracture is caused by transgranular tungsten cleavage. Crack initiation is often associated with a grain boundary source in these circumstances when dislocation pileups resulted in a stress concentration high enough to cause the grain boundary failure. The crack propagation can be discontinuous, which in certain cases leads to significant plastic deformations near the crack tip [120].

2.6 Mechanical Behaviour of Matrix alloy

The manufactured WHA is a pseudoalloy composed of a ductile matrix and high-strength tungsten reinforcements [121]. A significant amount of alloy development has established that the composition and processing of WHA influence their mechanical properties [122, 123, 25, 13]. For Ni-W-Fe alloy system, the composition with a ratio of about 7:3 (by weight) between Ni and Fe has been found to be the base alloy for the different studies. The formation of some undesired intermetallic phases, which rely on the cooling rate and adversely influence mechanical performance, can be avoided by using these compositions, presumably because they are close to a freezing point minimum [124]. The ductility, toughness, and impact strength of WHA are all directly related to the microstructure of the contiguous Ni-W-Fe matrix alloy that surrounds the tungsten phase. Strain partitioning between the Ni-W-Fe matrix alloys and tungsten phase occurs early in the deformation of these alloys, leading Ekbohm *et al.* [125] to infer that the Ni-W-Fe matrix alloy experiences a accelerated work hardening rate than the tungsten phase during deformation. At a high strain rate, Coates and Ramesh [126] assessed the hardness of both matrix phase and tungsten phase. It was found that the matrix phase is more strain rate sensitive than the tungsten phase. Rabin *et al.* [126, 127] correlated the mechanical property and flow behavior of WHA with the interface between tungsten and matrix. However, the crystallographic interaction between the matrix and tungsten phase remains unexplored. Gero *et al.* [80] examined the fracture of a variety of alloy variants and explained the role of matrix in the processes that lead to fracture. Instead of the typical WHA structure,

the properties of the ductile matrix phase were deduced from the behavior of the MMCs in every single one of the studies that were presented.

The size and valency differences are two key parameters determining the amount of solid solubility of certain components in a solid solution. The differences in size and valency between Fe and Ni are 0.4% and 0.2, respectively, whereas the differences in size and valency between W and Ni are 9.7% and 3.0. As a result, it is anticipated that a significant amount of iron and tungsten will be soluble in the nickel metal. Due to the difference in atomic size, the lattice parameter of the Ni-Fe-W matrix phase, and consequently the mechanical properties of the matrix phase, are significantly increased [128]. There have only been a handful of studies that have investigated how the matrix phase responds to deformation in the absence of tungsten particle, and the findings of those studies will be discussed in the paragraph.

Ekbohm *et al.* [125] and Woodward *et al.* [129] first to give the uniaxial tension and compression data for Ni-W-Fe matrix phase compositions in absence of tungsten phase. Nenno *et al.* [130] studied the annealing of a Ni-Cr-Fe alloy. They identified the precipitation of an intermediate phase at the grain boundary, which may have been a phase with a b.c.c. or hexagonal close packed (h.c.p.) crystal structure depending on the alloy composition. Agababova and Chaporova [131] studied the solubility of tungsten in Ni-Fe alloys and determined that alloys with 70-80% Ni and 20-30% Fe have the highest tungsten dissolution. Clément *et al.* [132] investigated the deformation behavior of Ni-Cr alloys in detail. Their studies show that alloys with a Cr concentration of greater than 20 wt% have dislocations that violate the intersection mechanism, which leads to an activation volume (100 b^3) that is unaffected by strain. With an increase in the concentration of Cr to 30%, short range ordering (SRO) exhibits a heterogeneous deformation mode and displays evidence of a glide softening mechanism. Wakashima and Kawai [133] showed that strength at high temperatures is dependent on the precipitates of tungsten with alpha fiber texture. Knippling *et al.* [134] studied the influence of tungsten content on the deformation behavior of nickel-iron alloy. They observed that increasing the tungsten concentration in Ni-30Fe alloy leads to simultaneous improvement in YS, tensile strength, and ductility. Deformation characteristics such as the strain-hardening exponent (n) and strain rate sensitivity (m) were also nearly invariant with tungsten content. Mehta *et al.* [135, 136] investigated the Ni-16MO-16Cr, Ni-16Cr-4W, and Ni-16Cr-8Fe alloys and showed that these concentrated alloys have two slopes in the true plastic stress-strain curve. The first slope corresponds to the formation of uniformly spaced slip lines within the grains, whereas the second slope corresponds to the penetration of coarse slip lines across grain boundaries, as well as the

formation of large deformation twins and strain localization. Rao *et al.* [137, 138, 139, 140] investigated the in-plane anisotropy and low anisotropic index of Ni-Fe-W and Ni-Fe-W-Co alloy in two different orientations, longitudinal and transverse direction, and in three different conditions, namely as-cast, hot rolled, and well-annealed. The strain hardening curves obtained under all three conditions revealed three stages of deformation in both orientations. Ravi Kiran *et al.* [141] correlated the microstructure and mechanical properties of sintered Ni-Fe-Co-W alloy and showed poor mechanical performance.

As previously mentioned, the matrix phase of the WHA is formed during the LPS and is analogous to the cast materials. To assess the characteristics of the alloy, it is reasonable to melt it in the conventional way of ingot metallurgy to a composition comparable to that of the matrix phase. These findings may be effectively used to improve the characteristic of WHA with equivalent matrix compositions. This study is conducted to fully comprehend the deformation behavior of the WHA as it provides a deeper insight into the relationship between microstructure, texture, and mechanical characteristics of the Ni-W-Fe, which is currently lacking in the literature. When a matrix phase is investigated in depth in isolation from tungsten particles, it will yield a complete and unambiguous understanding of how the matrix, in this case, a Ni-W-Fe alloy, reacts to mechanical tests.

2.7 Ideal texture in b.c.c. and f.c.c. metals

2.7.1 Texture development due to Uni-axial deformation

When subjected to uniaxial tension, the crystal axis of single crystals of f.c.c. metals rotates towards the slip direction, and when subjected to compression, the crystal axis rotates towards the slip plane. Because of the restricted amount of strain that can be induced in a tensile test, there has been minimal investigation into uniaxial deformation texture in the past. Axissymmetric textures may be seen in polycrystalline b.c.c. or f.c.c. metals under tension and compression.

The tension texture in f.c.c. metals is characterized by the presence of double texture $\langle 100 \rangle + \langle 111 \rangle$ fiber. The $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber is widely regarded to be the stable end orientation, whereas the $\langle 100 \rangle$ fiber is generated after recrystallisation or twinning. on contrary, the compression texture of f.c.c. is characterized by the presence of the $\langle 101 \rangle$ fiber. The detailed studies by Dillamore and Chin [142, 143] provide a good description of the deformation texture in f.c.c. metals and alloys subjected to axisymmetric deformation. It is worth noting that the nature of fiber texture in b.c.c. metals and alloys is exactly the

FIGURE 2.11: The position of the ideal orientations of f.c.c. metal rolling texture

reverse of that in f.c.c. metals and alloys; that is, $\langle 101 \rangle$ fiber develops during tension and double fiber $\langle 100 \rangle + \langle 111 \rangle$ fibers evolves during compression. This is due to the swap of slip planes and direction from the f.c.c. case to the b.c.c. case. All of the b.c.c. metals, such as molybdenum, tantalum, tungsten, and so on, are thought to have comparable fiber textures regardless of their composition or purity. Changes in processing conditions are often related to minor texture differences [102].

2.7.2 Rolling texture

When subjected to high rolling reductions, the f.c.c. metals are known to produce a distinct crystallographic texture. Since the early 1950s, much research has been conducted on the development of rolling texture in f.c.c. metals and alloys. f.c.c. metals and alloys have two distinct rolling textures (i) Copper type and (ii) Brass type. Copper-type texture is found in medium/high stacking fault energy (SFE) materials and is composed of strong S $\{123\} \langle 634 \rangle$, Brass $110 \langle 112 \rangle$, and Copper $\{112\} \langle 111 \rangle$. Low SFE materials have a Brass-like texture, which is characterised by a prominent Brass component and a lack of Copper component. Brass texture may also be found in different location on the α fiber, such as Goss orientation. It is possible to view the typical rolling textures observed in f.c.c. alloy by looking at the $\phi_1 = 0^\circ$, $\phi = 45^\circ$ and $\phi_2 = 65^\circ$ orientation distribution function (ODF) sections. Figure 2.11 shows where ideal orientations are located in these sections. While the method by which Copper-type texture develops is quite well known and accepted, the same cannot be said for Brass-type texture growth. In a recent publication, Leffers and Ray provide a comprehensive study of the issue of Brass-type texture development [144].

The cold rolling texture of b.c.c. materials show two common features: (a) The formation of strong but incomplete α fiber between $\{001\} \langle 110 \rangle$ and $\{111\} \langle 110 \rangle$ (b) γ fiber from $\{111\} \langle 110 \rangle$ to $\{111\} \langle 112 \rangle$.

FIGURE 2.12: The position of the ideal orientations of b.c.c. metal rolling texture.

TABLE 2.1: Texture components for rolled f.c.c. metals and alloys.

Component	$\{\mathbf{hkl}\} \langle \mathbf{uvw} \rangle$	(ϕ_1, ϕ, ϕ_2)
Cu	$\{112\} \langle 111 \rangle$	90, 35, 45
Bs	$\{110\} \langle 112 \rangle$	35, 45, 0
R	$\{124\} \langle 21\bar{1} \rangle$	59, 29, 63
S2	$\{123\} \langle 41\bar{2} \rangle$	47, 37, 63
S3	$\{123\} \langle 63\bar{4} \rangle$	59, 37, 63
Goss	$\{110\} \langle 001 \rangle$	0, 45, 0
Taylor/Dilliamore	$\{4\ 4\ 11\} \langle 11\ 11\ \bar{8} \rangle$	90, 27, 45

TABLE 2.2: Texture components for rolled b.c.c. metals and alloys.

Component	$\{\mathbf{hkl}\} \langle \mathbf{uvw} \rangle$	(ϕ_1, ϕ, ϕ_2)
Cube (C)	$\{100\} \langle 001 \rangle$	45, 0, 45
Rotated Cube (H)	$\{001\} \langle 110 \rangle$	0, 0, 45
E1	$\{111\} \langle 110 \rangle$	0, 55, 45
E2	$\{111\} \langle 110 \rangle$	60, 55, 45
F1	$\{111\} \langle 112 \rangle$	30, 55, 45
F2	$\{111\} \langle 112 \rangle$	90, 55, 45
I	$\{112\} \langle 110 \rangle$	0, 35, 45
Goss (G)	$\{110\} \langle 001 \rangle$	90, 90, 45

2.8 Scope of the Thesis

Using experimental investigations and computational modelling approaches, the present study attempts to investigate the deformation behaviour of two-phase WHA and their matrix. The following aim was accomplished with the aid of excellent metal-processing and metalworking techniques, as well as the characterisation of structure on various length scales, followed by an analysis of its mechanical behaviour. The following objective was accomplished with the aid of excellent metal-processing and metalworking techniques, as well as the characterisation of structure on various length scales, followed by an analysis of its mechanical behaviour.

1. During the compression of W-Ni-Fe-based WHA, the microstructure and texture development were investigated, and the results were supplemented by a mean-field crystal plasticity simulation to determine the underlying micro-mechanisms.
2. The second aim of this study is to investigate the deformation behaviour of two-phase W-7Ni-3Fe under large strain obtained by cold rolling. A mean and full-field simulation were used to supplement the results to reveal the underlying mechanisms that occurred during the deformation.
3. The purpose of this study is to determine the tensile deformation of the W-Ni-Fe based matrix alloy, namely Ni-22Fe-24W of WHA. The *in-situ* tensile deformation and the full-field simulation carried out on the specimen additionally supported the results and revealed the underlying deformation mechanism.
4. The objective of this last study was to evaluate the microstructure and texture evolution of the matrix (Ni-22Fe-24W) of WHA under large strain, which was achieved using cold rolling. The results of the investigation were bolstered by the results of the full-field simulation.

Chapter 3

Materials and Methods

This section provides a thorough discussion of the various experimental approaches that were used in the present study. A detailed description of the powder metallurgy process used in the production of WHA, followed by the fabrication of Ni-alloy, is presented. Different processing routes, such as compression tests and cold rolling, will be discussed, and the structural, microstructural, and mechanical characterisation techniques that were used in the current dissertation is also presented in this section. A brief review of synthetic microstructure production using Dream3D, as well as crystal plasticity simulations using the VPSC and fast Fourier transform (FFT), will be presented at the end of this section.

3.1 Starting Material

3.1.1 Tungsten Powder

Tungsten powder for the study was supplied by Global Tungsten Powders Corp. (Towanda, PA, USA). The powder was produced by reduction method and had rounded morphology with average particle size of $6 \pm 0.2 \mu m$.

3.1.2 Nickel Powder

The carbonyl nickel powder (INCO 123) was supplied by INCO. The powder was of spiky morphology and average particle size was $6 \pm 1 \mu m$.

FIGURE 3.1: (a) Top view of the Die (b) Side view of the Die (c) Green sample after compaction.

3.1.3 Iron Powder

The iron powder (grade: 180/2.6), prepared by water atomization process, was supplied by Pometon. The average particle size was $19 \pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$. The particle size of the powders was measured using laser scattering analyser (Model: Economy, laser Klasse 1; supplier Fritsch, Germany)

3.2 Fabrication of WHA

Samples of WHA was prepared with a constant composition of matrix 7Ni:3Fe ratio. The W-Ni-Fe premix was dry blended in turbula mixer (Supplier: - Bachofen AG, Switzerland) for two hours.

3.2.1 Compaction

A cuboidal green compact of $32 \text{ mm} \times 13 \text{ mm} \times 10 \text{ mm}$ were made from the blended powders in a single action hydraulic press. Manually operated hydraulic machine (Apex construction Ltd, UK) of 100 KN capacity was used at pressure of 200 MPa. The die was cleaned and lubricated with zinc stearate to reduce die wall friction prior to each powder fill. Lubrication facilitates easy compaction and subsequent removal of the compacted samples. The setup of Die and punch along with the green sample is shown in Figure 3.1.

FIGURE 3.2: Photograph of as-sintered WHA.

3.2.2 Sintering

The green compact was sintered at 1500 °C for 30 minutes under commercially pure hydrogen in horizontal tubular furnace (70T-7, Bysakh, Kolkata, India) equipped with MoSi₂ heating element. The heating rate of furnace was maintained at 5 °C. During the heating process, there was an intermittent isothermal hold performed for 10 minutes at a temperature of 1000 °C. This was done to guarantee that the temperature was distributed uniformly. The sample was cooled from 1500 °C to 1000 °C at heating rate of 5°C and later it was furnace cooled till room temperature. A picture of as-sintered sample are shown in Figure 3.2.

3.3 Fabrication of Matrix of WHA

The alloy with matrix composition 54Ni-24W-22Fe was melted in a vacuum arc-melting furnace. The arc melting furnace was evacuated and purged with argon three times prior to melting, and the final melting was conducted in an argon environment. In order to assure consistency and homogeneity of composition, the alloy buttons were melted five times, each time with the button flipped upside down. The different buttons were melted together again to make a bigger cylinder block.

3.4 Experimental Methods

3.4.1 Hardness test

3.4.1.1 Vickers Macro hardness

Vickers macro hardness of the polished samples was measured on Universal Hardness Testing Machine (Model: FH-10; Tinius-Olsen Ltd.). The indentation dwell time was

pre-programmed for 10 s, and 1 Kg of the load was applied. The diagonals of indent were measured, and hardness was calculated using the following equation:

$$VHN = 1.854 * \frac{P}{\left(\frac{d_1+d_2}{2}\right)^2} \quad (3.1)$$

where,

P is the load applied (in kgf)

d_1 and d_2 are the diagonals of indentation (in mm).

3.4.1.2 Vickers Micro hardness

Instrumented Micro-Indentation supplied by CSM International was used to perform the microhardness test. Indents were made on W particle and the matrix phase. The load used for indentation was 50 grams in each case. A diamond pyramid indenter was used and, it was programmed to dwell for 10 seconds. The square shape indents were observed and used for the calculation of Vickers hardness. Average of five readings is reported.

3.4.2 Uniaxial compression test

The as-sintered alloys were then cut into sub-standard cylindrical samples ($\text{Ø}6 \text{ mm} \times 4.8 \text{ mm}$) having length to diameter ratio of 0.8 for performing uniaxial compression tests using a Universal testing machine (Biss India Pvt Ltd). The strain rate employed during compression tests was kept at 10^{-3} s^{-1} . The compression tests were carried out till a true strain of 0.693 viz. 50% reduction in height. The compression tests were repeated three times to ensure reproducibility. The stearic acid was applied on both end of the sample to minimize the friction between compression anvil and sample.

3.4.3 Uniaxial Tensile Test

Tensile tests were carried out at room temperature on matrix alloy using 50 kN Instron universal testing machine at a cross head velocity of 0.5 mm/min corresponding to nominal strain rate of 10^{-3} . Schematic of tensile specimen used in the present investigation is shown in 3.3 It was ensured that gauge section of the tensile specimens was properly grounded and polished before carrying out tensile tests.

FIGURE 3.3: Schematic of tensile test sample (All dimensions are in mm).

FIGURE 3.4: Schematic of *in-situ*-tensile test sample as per Gatan specifications (All dimensions are in mm).

The GATAN 2 kN tensile stage was put in the JEOL field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM), and the Oxford Channel 5 EBSD attachment was used to conduct *In-situ* EBSD experiments during the tensile deformation. The tensile stage features top and front grips to mount samples. The front grip is meant for at 70° in order to carry out *In-situ* EBSD measurements, whilst the latter is employed for SEM observations of tensile deformation. Schematic of *in-situ* specimen is shown in 3.4.

3.4.4 Rolling

The as-sintered WHA and homogenized matrix alloy were unidirectionally rolled in a two-roll mill machine (FENN) with roll-diameter of 127 mm and roll speed of 72 rpm. The samples were subjected to 90% rolling reduction corresponding to true strain of $\varepsilon = -2.3$ at room temperature. The entirety of the rolling process was completed in 46 steps, with each step equivalent to a true strain (ε) of 0.05. For the purpose of investigating texture and microstructure, samples were kept after each of the following percentages had been attained: 30%, 50%, 75%, and 90%. The contact length (Λ) to mean thickness (h) ratio (equation 3.2) was kept at greater values ($\frac{\Lambda}{h} \approx 1$) in order to ensure that the through-thickness strain distribution was homogeneous, as well as to resemble the features

FIGURE 3.5: Schematic representing the planes for bulk texture by XRD and microtexture by EBSD measurement.

of compression with a plain strain. This ratio was achieved by carrying out rolling in multiple steps, where a small reduction of 10% was given in each step.

$$\frac{\Lambda}{h} = \frac{2 \times \sqrt{R(h_i - h_f)}}{h_i + h_f} \quad (3.2)$$

Here, h_i is initial thickness, h_f is final thickness and R is roll radius.

The entire rolling process was carried out in 46 steps with each step corresponding to effective true strain (ε) of -0.05 . The samples were retained after 30% ($\varepsilon = -0.41$), 50% ($\varepsilon = -0.8$), 75% ($\varepsilon = -1.6$) and 90% ($\varepsilon = -2.66$) rolling reduction to perform texture and microstructure investigation.

3.5 Characterization techniques

3.5.1 Sample Preparation for Metallography

For EBSD analysis, the compressed samples were sectioned along the compression direction while rolled samples were sectioned along ND-rolling direction in a rolled plate (RD) plane, but for Bulk texture analysis, the compressed samples were sectioned along the normal of compression direction while rolled samples were sectioned along RD-transverse direction in a rolled plate (TD) plane. The sectioned samples were initially polished to mirror finish using the standard silicon carbide grit papers and alumina suspension. However, for EBSD, samples were additionally subjected to polishing via $0.04 \mu\text{m}$ colloidal silica for thirty minutes in Vibromet (Buehler, USA) to obtain a strain-free surface.

3.5.2 SEM and EBSD

The JEOL JSM-7100F Field Emission SEM coupled with an Oxford EBSD detector was used to conduct the microstructural examination. The operating voltage was set at 20 kV, and the probe current was set at 20 pA for imaging and 10 nA for EBSD. For EBSD scanning of sample, the specimen stage mounted with sample was tilted by 70° relative to normal incidence of the electron beam. An Oxford NordlysMax² detector was used for collecting EBSD data. The step size during EBSD was kept at 0.5 μm with 2×2 binning mode. The EBSD data were analyzed using commercially available TSL-OIM v8.0 software (TSL, USA).

3.5.3 Elemental Analysis

The JEOL JXA-8230 electron probe microanalyser (EPMA) was used to do an analysis on the both the phases viz tungsten particles and matrix phase. In order to conduct the EPMA analysis, pure elemental standards were utilized, and the accelerating voltage was set at 25 kV while the beam current was set at 20 nA. The $K_{\alpha 1}$ x-ray intensities of each element were used in the analysis, and these readings were then subjected to ZAF correction before being interpreted. Scanning electron microscopy coupled with energy dispersive X-ray spectrometry (SEM-EDS) was utilized in order to carry out the elemental mapping of the microstructures (model: X-max, Supplier: Oxford Instruments, UK).

3.5.4 Bulk texture measurement

3.5.4.1 X-ray Diffraction

The Rigaku four circle goniometer (Ultima IV) was utilized in order to conduct the crystallographic bulk texture measurements. In order to minimize the background radiation and defocussing of X-ray beam, a maximum tilt angle of 70° was used to measure 4 incomplete PF of the tungsten b.c.c. phase and matrix phase f.c.c.. These PFs were (110), (200), (211), and (220) in b.c.c. and (111), (200), (220) and (311) in f.c.c.. After that, the incomplete PF were used to obtain the ODF using MTEX Matlab toolbox. The ODF's were then used to calculate the inverse pole figure (IPF) parallel to the loading direction for uniaxial deformation and in ND for plane strain compression. It should be noted that owing to the lesser volume fraction of matrix in WHA, the XRD peaks corresponding

to the f.c.c. matrix were very weak. Hence, Neutron diffraction was used to capture the matrix texture evolution in two phase WHA alloy for the case of plane strain compression.

3.5.4.2 Neutron Diffraction

Owing to the large grains of tungsten and matrix phases in WHAs, neutron diffraction is an efficient tool for bulk texture analysis. The major distinction between neutron diffraction and other approaches is that the interaction between neutrons and matter is very weak, resulting in 100-10,000 times greater penetration depth than X-rays. This large penetration depth also overcomes the problem of low intensity of minority phases in XRD. The usual test volume in this particular case of bulk texture analysis was $10 \times 10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^3$. This technique also delivers the complete PF and therefore the neutron PF is the best quality data and normalization can be made directly through the integration across the complete PF. The rolled WHAs were subjected to neutron diffractometer STRESS-SPEC at FRM-II in Garching, Germany. The diffraction data was collected in transmission mode with a monochromatic neutron beam of 1.68 Å wavelength, vertical focussing of Ge monochromator and Vanadium as reference material for instrumental error correction. A setup of neutron diffraction during experiment is shown in Figure 3.6. A software package Stress Texture Calculator (STECA) was used to extract PF data for intensity PF (crystallographic texture), for peak position PF (macro strain) and for peak broadening PF (micro strain). The data was further plotted using MTEX.

3.6 Crystal Plasticity Simulation

3.6.1 Visco plastic self consistent model

VPSC simulation predicts the texture evolution and the operative deformation mechanisms for different loading conditions, temperature, strain rates. Complete details about the VPSC model can be found in the manual. However, a brief explanation of the basics of the VPSC model and the simulation strategy adopted in the present work is provided in the following paragraph. VPSC crystal plasticity framework was developed by Lebensohn and Tome based on an Eshelby–Hill approach. It ignores the effects of elasticity and makes the assumption that the stress equilibrium is controlled by a viscoplastic interaction rather than an elastoplastic one. Each grain is treated as an ellipsoidal viscoplastic inclusion embedded in a homogeneous effective medium (HEM). The HEM represents the average environment

FIGURE 3.6: Neutron diffraction setup at FRM-II Labs Munich, Germany.

that each grain interacts with the viscoplastic strain rate at the grain level (ε_{ij}^g) is related to the local stress through a well-established constitutive law proposed by Hutchinson.

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^g = \sum_s m_{ij}^s \gamma^s = \gamma_0 \sum_s m_{ij}^s \left(\frac{m_{kl}^s \sigma_{kl}^s}{\tau^s} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (3.3)$$

Here, γ_0 is the reference shear rate, m is the strain rate sensitivity, τ^s is the critical resolved shear stress (CRSS) of the s^{th} slip system and m_{ij}^s is the symmetric Schmid tensor which can be written as

$$m_{ij}^s = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{n}_i^s \mathbf{b}_j^s + \mathbf{n}_j^s \mathbf{b}_i^s) \quad (3.4)$$

Here, \mathbf{n} is the slip plane normal and \mathbf{b} is the Burgers vector. The linearization form of above equation in the domain of a grain is expressed as

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^g = M_{ijkl}^g \sigma_{kl}^g + \varepsilon_{ij}^{0,g} \quad (3.5)$$

Here M_{ijkl}^g and $\varepsilon_{ij}^{0,g}$ are the visco-plastic compliance modulus and the back-extrapolated term for grain g , respectively.

The macroscopic strain-rate $\bar{\varepsilon}$ and stress $\bar{\sigma}$ can be expressed in a similar manner

TABLE 3.1: Value of n^{eff} and their corresponding nature of Grain-Matrix interaction.

Value of n^{eff}	Nature of Grain-Matrix Interaction
0	Taylor Interaction
1	Secant Interaction
$1 < n^{eff} < n$ (generally, 20)	Tangent Interaction
∞	Sachs Interaction

$$\bar{\varepsilon} = \bar{M} : \bar{\sigma} + \varepsilon_0 \quad (3.6)$$

The macroscopic modulus \bar{M} that results from a secant or tangent local linearization, can be called \bar{M}^{sec} and \bar{M}^{tan} , respectively. The interaction between the ellipsoidal grain and HEM is defined by

$$\left(\varepsilon_{ij}^g - \bar{\varepsilon} \right) = -\tilde{M} (\sigma_{kl}^g - \bar{\sigma}) \quad (3.7)$$

Where

$$\tilde{M} = n^{eff} (I - s^{-1}) : S : \bar{M}^{sec} \quad (3.8)$$

Here, I and S represent the Identity and Eshelby tensor for a given grain. An adjustable parameter n^{eff} describes the nature of linearization for the compliance of the grain-matrix interactions. The different values of n^{eff} supported by the VPSC 7d code are summarized in Table 3.1.

In the VPSC model, the hardening is included via the extended Voce hardening law. This law is based on the evolution of work hardening as function of accumulated shear strain in the grain.

$$\tau_c^\alpha = \tau_0^\alpha + (\tau_1^\alpha + \theta_1^\alpha \Gamma) \left[1 - \exp \left(-\frac{\theta_0^\alpha \Gamma}{\tau_1^\alpha} \right) \right] \quad (3.9)$$

Here, $\Gamma = \sum_s |\Delta\gamma^s|$ is the total cumulative shear deformation by each active system s belonging to a slip mode α . τ_0^α , θ_0^α , τ_1^α , and θ_1^α are the initial CRSS, initial hardening rate, back extrapolated CRSS and the asymptotic hardening rate, respectively.

As the present work deals with two phase materials, the widely popular 1-site approach, where the inclusion problem is solved for a single grain is not applicable. Therefore, a

TABLE 3.2: Parameters for extended Voce hardening fitting.

Phase	Slip system family	τ_0	τ_1	θ_0	θ_1
Tungsten	$\{\bar{1}10\} \langle 111 \rangle$	τ_0	235	355	0
	$\{11\bar{2}\} \langle 111 \rangle$	$1.3\tau_0$	350	100	20
	$\{12\bar{3}\} \langle 111 \rangle$	$1.5\tau_0$	200	100	10
Matrix	$\{111\} \langle \bar{1}10 \rangle$	$0.6\tau_0$	200	100	0

two site viscoplastic self-consistent (VPSC-2S) model [145, 146], which solves the inclusion problem for a pair of grains embedded in the HEM was used in the present work. A two-phase polycrystal is defined as a collection of pairs of sites. Each site may represent a grain or a representative area within a grain. In the current study, the VPSC-2S model was utilized with no preferential orientation between neighboring grains. The Voce hardening parameters for each of the alloy is obtained by trial and error method. The set of parameters which gave the best match with experimental stress-strain curve and texture was selected. Table 3.2 summarizes the Voce hardening parameters for tungsten heavy alloy.

The initial texture of the material was taken as input and simulations were performed till a strain of 0.69 via 69 steps. Each simulation step corresponds to a strain increment of 0.01. It should be noted that the initial texture was discretized to obtain 10000 single orientations to be used as input in VPSC. The velocity gradient (L) used for the simulations was

$$L = \dot{\epsilon} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.10)$$

Since the microstructures of both phases in all four alloys exhibited equiaxed grains, an aspect ratio of one was adopted for both phases. Taylor isotropic hardening is assumed during the simulation. Only 12 dominant slip systems of $\{110\} \langle \bar{1}11 \rangle$ were taken in consideration for texture evolution.

3.6.2 Düsseldorf Advanced Material Simulation Kit

Düsseldorf Advanced Material Simulation Kit (DAMASK) is an integrated, multi-physics simulation software suite for crystal plasticity modeling. A constitutive response that

relates deformation and stress at each material point is necessary for the solution of continuous mechanical boundary value problems. DAMASK solves this problem utilizing crystal plasticity and a range of constitutive models and homogenization techniques. To investigate newly discovered advanced high-strength materials, however, it is no longer adequate to investigate mechanics on its own. Deformation, displacive phase transition, considerable heating, and the potential for damage evolution all occur simultaneously in these materials. Consequently, DAMASK is able to solve issues involving several physics. A short summary of the basic formulations focused toward plasticity is presented in the next section.

3.6.2.1 Crystal plasticity model in DAMASK

In this analysis, the standard constitutive assumptions are taken into account. In particular, a local multiplicative decomposition of the deformation gradient known as:

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_e \mathbf{F}_p \quad (3.11)$$

where \mathbf{F}_e refers to the elastic component, and \mathbf{F}_p refers to plastic component. The equation 3.12 governs the evolution of deformation gradients relating the macroscopic velocity gradient, \mathbf{L} , with elastic velocity gradient (\mathbf{L}_e), plastic velocity gradient (\mathbf{L}_p) and elastic component of deformation gradient (\mathbf{F}_e).

$$\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{L}_e + \mathbf{F}_e \mathbf{L}_p (\mathbf{F}_e)^{-1} \quad (3.12)$$

The plastic deformation can be attributed to slip over N number of slip systems. Each slip system is defined by the slip direction (unit slip vector, $(\mathbf{b}^{(s)})$) and the normal of the slip plane (unit normal of the slip plane, $(\mathbf{n}^{(s)})$). Schmid tensor (\mathbf{M}^s) is the dyadic product of $\mathbf{b}^{(s)}$ and $\mathbf{n}^{(s)}$. It is used to capture salient features of slip-based plastic deformations, especially in close-packed crystals and mathematically expressed as in Equation 3.13.

$$\mathbf{M}^s = \left(\mathbf{b}^{(s)} \otimes \mathbf{n}^{(s)} + \mathbf{n}^{(s)} \otimes \mathbf{b}^{(s)} \right) / 2 \quad (3.13)$$

The plastic velocity gradient in terms of Schmid tensor can be expressed as follow

$$\mathbf{L}_p = \dot{\mathbf{F}}_p \mathbf{F}_p^{-1} = \sum_s^N \dot{\gamma}^s \mathbf{M}^s \quad (3.14)$$

where, $\dot{\gamma}^s$ is the plastic shear rate on slip system s . This evolution of plastic shear rate, known as the flow rule, can be expressed as a power law in terms of applied shear stress (τ^s) and strain rate sensitivity (n).

$$\dot{\gamma}^s = \dot{\gamma}_0 \left| \frac{\tau^s}{R^s} \right|^n \text{sign}(\tau^s) \quad (3.15)$$

The R^s in Equation 3.15 is known as slip resistance. The evolution of slip resistance consists of hardening rule and yield condition and it is expressed in terms of plastic shear rate and dependency matrix. The resistance can be mathematically expressed as follow,

$$\dot{R}^\alpha = \sum_{\beta=1}^{N_{\text{slip}}} \dot{\gamma}^\beta h_0 \left| 1 - \frac{R^\beta}{R_\infty^\alpha} \right|^m \text{sign} \left(1 - \frac{R^\beta}{R_\infty^\alpha} \right) h^{\alpha\beta} \quad (3.16)$$

where, R_∞^α is the saturation resistance of slip system α .

$h^{\alpha\beta}$ is the dependency matrix or latent hardening parameter. For co-planar slip system 1 otherwise 1.4

$h_{0,m}$ is the materials constant.

N_{slip} is the total number of slip system.

The Cauchy stress tensor (σ) and the applied shear stress (τ) are related by the following mathematical expression.

$$\tau_\alpha = \sigma : (\mathbf{F}_e \mathbf{S}_0^\alpha \mathbf{F}_p^{-1}) = (\mathbf{F}_e^T \mathbf{F}_e \mathbf{S}) : \mathbf{S}_0^\alpha \quad (3.17)$$

where \mathbf{S}_0^α represents the second-order Piola-Kirchhoff stress that was determined by applying the assumption of a small elastic strain:

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{C} : \mathbf{E}_e \text{ with } \mathbf{E}_e = (\mathbf{F}_e^T \mathbf{F}_e - \mathbf{I}) / 2 \quad (3.18)$$

where \mathbf{C} represents the elasticity matrix in the sample coordinate system. This matrix for the case of a cubic crystal is fully specified by three material constants, C11, C12, and C44.

Shanthraj *et al.* [147] contains information that can be used to learn more about the numerical spectral method that makes use of the crystal plasticity fast Fourier transform-based (CPFFT).

3.7 Map Visualization: DREAM.3D and ParaView

DREAM.3D is an open source program consisting of data analysis tool (known as filters here). It allows user to import the ASCII data and helps in building a flexible and extensible data structure using variety of filters available in filter library. Dream.3D allows to construct an image file from ASCII data after arranging the data in rectilinear grid form. The reconstructed/derived data can be visualized using another open source software ParaView. ParaView quickly builds the visualizations and helps in analyzing the data qualitatively and quantitatively. With the help of these package IPF, Stress-strain states and other derived maps have been generated and shown in the dissertation.

Chapter 4

Effect of tungsten content and compression on microstructure and texture evolution in WHA

4.1 Background

The literature review indicated that a systematic investigation of the mechanical behaviour of WHA in terms of crystallographic texture is required. This chapter deals with the evolution of crystallographic texture during uniaxial compression. It has been established that mechanical properties can be enhanced through the application of suitable texture engineering [102]. Additionally, there is no processing-texture-mechanical property linkage for WHA for various tungsten phase fractions. As a result, it is of the utmost importance to conduct systematic research on the evolution of the texture of WHA while they are being subjected to uniaxial compression in order to gain an understanding of the governing deformation mechanism. In contrast to the extensive research conducted on single-phase b.c.c., very little is known about two-phase alloys, and even less about WHA. In light of this, the purpose of the present chapter is to conduct texture measurements on WHA following uniaxial compression tests in order to comprehend its behaviour during deformation. In addition, microstructural characterization and simulation studies employing VPSC simulations are carried out to complement the texture measurements.

TABLE 4.1: Grain size and phase fraction of sintered WHA.

Sample	Apparent Grain Size of tungsten (μm)	Phase Fraction of Matrix
80W-20M	21 ± 8	0.30
85W-15M	20.7 ± 8.4	0.23
90W-10M	22 ± 7.2	0.19
95W-5M	20.2 ± 7.3	0.13
98W-2M	20 ± 5	0.08

4.2 Experimental Results

4.2.1 Initial microstructure and texture

The as-sintered microstructures of two representative WHA are presented in Figures 4.1(a) and 4.1(b), respectively. The grain size of the tungsten, as well as the phase fraction of the matrix, are both listed in Table 4.1 after the sintering process. As a result of the Ostwald ripening phenomenon that occurred during sintering, a large standard deviation in grain size was observed. The matrix's phase fraction was calculated using the stereological area fraction method.

The 80W-20M and 98W-2M alloys were chosen to represent the extreme conditions. Both of these microstructures can be identified by the presence of coarse tungsten particles that are surrounded by a matrix that is completely wetting. It can also be observed that contiguity, the tungsten-tungsten contact fraction, and connectivity increase with increasing tungsten content. energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS) was also used to obtain elemental distribution maps, which can be seen in Figures 4.1(c), (d), and (e), to confirm the composition of both the particles and the matrix. The darker phase was composed of a solid solution of Ni-24W-22Fe, while the brighter phase was composed entirely of pure tungsten. The relatively sharp peaks with a small broadening in the XRD pattern shown in Figure 4.1(f) confirm that the sample is free of any strain heterogeneity or size effects (full width at half maximum (FWHM)). In addition to the b.c.c. phase peaks, a few small peaks corresponding to the f.c.c. phase can be observed. A bulk texture measurement was performed on the initial sample, and the results suggest that the initial sample has a random texture. This is indicated by the crystal orientation or IPF map along the compression direction (CD), which is shown in Figure 4.1 (g). It should be noted that texture measurements were taken for each of the five samples. However, in the interest of brevity, the IPF||CD of only 80W-20M is shown. The texture of the other compositions was also observed to be random.

FIGURE 4.1: (a) Backscattered electron images for 80W-20M alloy (b) Backscattered electron images for 98W-2M alloy (c-e) elemental distribution maps by EDS (f) x-ray diffractogram for 80W-20M alloy (g) IPF plotted parallel to the compression direction for 80W-20M alloy.

4.3 Texture evolution during uniaxial compression

Figure 4.2 (a) shows the true stress - true strain curve and Figure 4.2 (b) work hardening rate ($d\sigma/d\varepsilon$) vs $(\sigma - \sigma_0)$ for all the alloys. All the sample behaved in similar manner and the dominance of the stage III deformation [148] was evident as a straight line in work hardening curve. There were three different sites where the hardness measurements were taken (i) only on the tungsten phase, (ii) only on the matrix phase, and (iii) as the bulk composite. It should be emphasized that the load used during the hardness measurement

FIGURE 4.2: (a) True stress-true strain plot of WHA (b) Work hardening rate vs $\sigma - \sigma_0$ of WHA (c) Vickers hardness number of compressed samples.

for individual phases was 100 g, but the load applied during the hardness measurement for bulk material was 1 kg. Figure 4.2 (c) shows the hardness of 90W-10M as a function of compression. All of the alloys had a similar pattern, thus for the sake of brevity, just the hardness of 90W-10M has been shown.

The stress-strain diagram also shows the softening behaviour, negative slope after yielding, instead of the hardening behaviour. Since tungsten cannot undergo any dynamic recrystallization, the deformed sample was cut and microscopic examination was carried out. Figure 4.3 shows the occurrence of flow localization under the uniaxial compression. A broad band of localized area at a 45° angle was observed. Upon further examination at higher magnification, it was found that the localised grains had shear marks at the interface. In order to get a better insight into the shear formation, the matrix was leached and

FIGURE 4.3: Secondary electron images of deformed 90W-10M alloy showing flow localization.

the sample was taken with an inclination of 50° angle in the electron microscope. The unlocalized grains show the facets on tungsten and no shear was observed, while the localized area showed high shear.

Figure 4.4 (a) shows the IPF \parallel CD for all the five alloy compositions considered in the present work. As can be observed, the classical double-fiber texture with weak $\langle 100 \rangle$ fiber and major $\langle 111 \rangle \parallel$ CD fiber is obtained after uniaxial compression. This is the typical texture found in many b.c.c. metals and alloys after uniaxial compression. However, a closer look at the IPF's suggests that there is a systematic influence of the composition on the texture evolution, mainly with regard to the relative proportion of $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ fibers. This behavior is elegantly shown in Figure 4.4 (b) where the ratio of the volume fraction of $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ fibers for b.c.c. tungsten is plotted. The volume fraction of a component can be determined by first multiplying the ODF by the volume increment of each small cell, and then adding the products of this multiplication across the set of cells that are associated with the component [149]. It can be clearly seen that the volume fraction ratio increases with increasing tungsten content. The volume fraction of the individual fibers is also shown in Figure 4.4 (c). Although the $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber is the strongest for all of the present compositions, it is apparent that the volume fraction of $\langle 100 \rangle$ fiber increases steadily with an increase in the tungsten content.

As already mentioned, texture measurements via XRD were not possible for the f.c.c. phase because of very weak peaks (Figure 4.1 (f)). Therefore, the texture measurement of the matrix phase was carried out via EBSD. Figure 4.4 (d) shows inverse pole figure

FIGURE 4.4: (a) IPF plotted parallel to compression direction for different composition of tungsten measured from XRD after 50% compression (true strain = -0.69) (b) volume fractions of $\langle 111 \rangle$ and $\langle 100 \rangle$ fibre for different composition (c) volume fraction ratio of $\langle 100 \rangle$ to $\langle 111 \rangle$ fibre as a function of tungsten content (d) IPF plotted parallel to compression direction for different composition of matrix measured from EBSD after 50% compression (true strain = -0.69).

for the f.c.c. phase in the compression direction. It can be seen that the classical $\langle 110 \rangle \parallel \text{CD}$ texture evolves after uniaxial compression up to a height reduction of 50%. The texture of the f.c.c. phase is quite weak (2.5 multiples of a random distribution (mrd)) compared to the main tungsten phase (8.0 mrd). This weak texture can be attributed to the relatively lower volume fraction of the f.c.c. phase compared to the b.c.c. phase. Therefore, in the following we will concentrate entirely on the texture development of the b.c.c. tungsten phase, with reference to the f.c.c. matrix phase wherever this is required.

4.4 Microstructural evolution during uniaxial compression

The inverse pole figure maps and phase maps of the deformed WHA are shown in Figure 4.5 (a) and (b), respectively. The CD is marked in the IPF maps. The maps clearly show the orientation gradient in the microstructure, which means a heterogeneous deformation. Intragranular orientation gradients are prevalent in deformed microstructures and depend on the initial orientation as well as the orientations of adjacent grains. In addition, deformation banding can be observed in the microstructures which can lead to fragmentation of grains. Apart from these general characteristics, there is also a systematic influence of the composition on the development of the microstructure. As can be observed, the extent of the strain heterogeneity of the tungsten phase increases with increasing tungsten content. This heterogeneity can be attributed to the strain partitioning effect between the soft matrix phase and the hard tungsten phase. With an 80W-20M alloy, the matrix can accommodate a significant amount of imposed deformation compared to the 98W-2M alloy, where the matrix volume fraction is minimal. With the 98W-2M alloy, the tungsten phase must accommodate most of the deformation imposed. This is elegantly captured by the aspect ratio of the tungsten particles, where the particles in the 80W-20M alloy are relatively equiaxed compared to 98W-2M alloy, where the particles have developed a pancake shape and are elongated in the radial direction. This is also confirmed by the kernel average misorientation (KAM) plot (Figure 4.5 (c)), which was calculated using a 3×3 kernel. The KAM represents the average misorientation of a pixel with its neighboring pixels and is therefore ideally suited for estimating the strain heterogeneity. Figure 4.5 (c) also indicates that the KAM distribution of tungsten particles shifts to higher angles with increasing tungsten content. This confirms our argument that the dislocation activity and strain heterogeneity of the tungsten particles is a strong function of the matrix content. Additional evidence of this behavior is obtained from the Feret diameter of the particles. The Feret diameter corresponds to the greatest distance between the two parallel lines on the opposite side of randomly oriented particles. Therefore, a reduction in the Feret diameter is an indication of a reduction in grain size and grain fragmentation of tungsten particles. As can be seen in Figure 4.5 (d), the Feret diameter is the smallest for the 98W-2M alloy. Figure 4.5 (e) shows the aspect ratio of tungsten grains in all of the various alloys at 50 percent compression, which reveals that aspect ratio reduces as tungsten content increases, but that this reduction was not seen in 98W-2M owing to grain fragmentation. After analyzing the phase-dependent deformation, we now shift our attention to the orientation-dependent deformation of tungsten particles. The tungsten particles constitute the major portion of these alloys and therefore require further investigation of

FIGURE 4.5: (a-b) IPF maps plotted parallel to compression direction and phase maps for different compositions, respectively. (c) Kernel average misorientation distribution profiles. (d) Feret diameter as a function of tungsten content at 50% compression. (e) Aspect ratio as a function of tungsten content at 50% compression.

their deformation behavior. In this regard, the two orientations correspond to the major texture components i.e., $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle \parallel \text{CD}$ were partitioned with a tolerance angle of 10° .

Figure 4.6 (a) and (b) highlights some representative grains of the $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ orientations, and Figure 4.6 (c) and (d) shows the KAM and geometry necessary dislocation (GND) histogram calculated over EBSD map shown in Figure 4.5 (a) for various tungsten content alloys. As before with the strain partitioning between the phases, we call up the KAM again to analyze the deformation behavior of $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ oriented

FIGURE 4.6: (a-b) Set of grains representing $\langle 111 \rangle$ and $\langle 100 \rangle$ fibers with their KAM map for 80W-20M and 98W-2M, respectively. (c-d) KAM and GND histogram as the function of tungsten content calculated over whole EBSD map.

grains. As can be observed in Figure 4.6 (c), the average KAM for $\langle 111 \rangle$ oriented grains compared $\langle 100 \rangle$ oriented grains is higher regardless of the alloy composition. However, the difference between the KAM values increases as the tungsten content increases. This can be explained by the higher strain accommodation of tungsten particles with increasing tungsten content. A simplified explanation of the higher KAM value of $\langle 111 \rangle$ oriented grains compared to $\langle 100 \rangle$ oriented grains can be provided with regard to the Taylor factor. As calculated for axisymmetric deformation, the Taylor factor is 3.67 for $\langle 111 \rangle$ oriented grains compared to 2.44 for $\langle 100 \rangle$ oriented grains. Therefore, more work or plastic shearing is required in the $\langle 111 \rangle$ grains in order to achieve the same equivalent strain compared to $\langle 100 \rangle$ grains. This also increases the dislocation activity in $\langle 111 \rangle$ grains higher compared to $\langle 100 \rangle$ grains on the microscopic length scale, which leads to the formation of dislocation boundaries, which in turn lead to a higher KAM. The geometrically necessary dislocation density (Figure 4.6 (d)) for the two grain families also confirms our arguments.

4.5 Simulation results

As mentioned earlier, VPSC was used to perform texture simulations. It is known that the texture evolution in b.c.c. metals and alloys can be attributed to pencil glide on $\{110\}$, $\{112\}$ and $\{123\}$ slip planes with the common $\langle 111 \rangle$ slip direction [150]. Therefore, we also selected pencil glide in VPSC for performing texture simulations. Based on a comparison between experimental and simulated texture, it was found that another important aspect to decide before executing the VPSC code is the deformation mode. The VPSC code allows the n^{eff} parameter to be tuned to mimic the two extremes of plastic deformation viz. the upper bound Taylor type and the lower bound Sachs type. As can be seen from equation 3.8, $n^{eff} = 0$ corresponds to a Taylor type deformation, while ∞ corresponds to Sachs type deformation. Since the mode of deformation is unknown in advance, we performed texture simulations taking into account the different modes and based on the agreement between experimental and simulation results, the mode of deformation is determined. It should be noted that $n^{eff} = 100$ is enough to simulate the Sachs-type deformation behavior as it is physically impossible to use infinity in the VPSC code. Other key parameters required to run the VPSC simulations such as the velocity gradient, total strain imposed, and strain increment are specified in section 3.6.1. It has been observed that secant type deformation with simultaneous rotation of adjacent grains adequately reproduces the experimental results. This can be justified physically with the requirement of strain compatibility at the tungsten-tungsten and tungsten-matrix interface and the equiaxed nature of the tungsten particles. It is also generally accepted that strain compatibility is a more important criterion than stress compatibility (Sachs mode) during plastic deformation. In Figure 4.1 (a) and (b), it can be observed that the contact between tungsten-tungsten particles is much more prevalent in the 98W alloy than in 80W alloy. It is known that neighboring orientations can significantly change the local velocity gradient compared to the macroscopically imposed velocity gradient, which in turn can lead to completely different rotation paths and thus final texture [151]. In the VPSC model, the influence of neighbors can be taken into account in an empirical way by randomly pairing the grains, which are then caused to co-rotate. The co-rotation scheme was used in the VPSC 7D model by Tomé *et al.* [152]. This scheme leads to a different rotation path for similarly oriented grains based on the chosen neighbor. The solid volume fraction (V_s) and dihedral angle (φ_d) were used to calculate a 3D coordination number, which was calculated with the aid of the following equation [5]:

$$V_S = -0.83 + 0.81N_C - 0.056N_C^2 + 0.0018N_C^3 - 0.36A + 0.008A^2 \quad (4.1)$$

Where, $A = N_C \cos\left(\frac{\varphi_d}{2}\right)$, The value of φ was obtained as median value of 400 tungsten pairs. The angle was calculated using image processing module in MATLAB. The equation was solved in MATLAB to obtain the value of N_c and hence, a coordinate number of five was obtained for 98W-2M alloy and two for 80W-20M alloy. Therefore, random pairs of five and two particles were taken for performing texture simulations of 98W and 80W alloy, respectively.

It should be noted that the Figure 4.7 (a) shows the simulated IPF together with the comparison between the experimental and the simulated volume fraction ratio, shown in Figure 4.7 (b). It can be said that the agreement between experimental and simulation results matches significantly in agreement when the grains are paired and rotated together. The intensity near the $\langle 100 \rangle$ corner is clearly high for the 98W-2M alloy compared to the 80W-20M alloy. The simulated volume fraction ratio of the two alloys also follows a trend similar to that observed experimentally. Although this is a simplified way of looking at the effect of neighboring particles, it underlines their role in plastic deformation and the resulting texture development. It should be noted that all of these VPSC simulations were performed with considering the two-phase scenario i.e., VPSC-2S model. The phase fraction was suitably set in VPSC depending upon the alloy composition. Thus, in addition to the texture of the tungsten particles, the simulated texture of the matrix was also obtained.

Figure 4.8 (a) and (b) shows the inverse pole figure in the compression direction, the classic $\langle 110 \rangle$ fiber texture during f.c.c compression is satisfactorily reproduced by VPSC simulations. The activity diagrams showing the strain partitioning and the average number of active systems per grain (AVACS) between the two phases are shown in Figure 4.8 (b). On average, six slip systems were active and showed a deformation close to the upper bound model in all the alloy. The tungsten particles, which are the dominant phase, bear most of the externally imposed deformation compared to the matrix phase, so that the relative activity (shown in Figure 4.8 (c)) of tungsten is always higher than that of the matrix.

4.6 Discussion

The texture evolution during compression can be fully understood by showing the lattice rotation behavior in an inverse pole figure. A schematic representation of the lattice rotation is shown in Figure 4.9 (a). The lattice rotation path was obtained by Rosenberg and Piehler [153] by implementing the pencil-glide hypothesis. As can be seen, the

FIGURE 4.7: (a) Predicted IPF parallel to compression direction by Secant model for the two extreme compositions considering the connectivity of the tungsten particles. (b) Comparison between experimental and simulated ratios of volume fraction of $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ fibres.

grains tend to rotate in direction $\langle 111 \rangle$ or $\langle 100 \rangle$ depending upon the orientation of the compression axis. All the grains lying above the $[110]$ - $[411]$ line would rotate towards $\langle 111 \rangle$, whereas the grains lying below the $[110]$ - $[411]$ line would rotate in the direction of $\langle 100 \rangle$. The $[110]$ - $[411]$ line is generally known in the literature as ‘divergent line’ [154]. For an initial random texture, a majority of the grains would be lying above the divergent line compared to the one below. As a result, a large proportion of the grains would come close to $\langle 111 \rangle$ compared to $\langle 100 \rangle$. Rosenberg and Piehler [153] calculated using simulations that for an initial random texture 74% of the grains would rotate in the direction of $\langle 111 \rangle$, compared with 26% in the direction $\langle 100 \rangle$. This explains the experimental observation of the relative dominance of $\langle 111 \rangle$ fibers compared to $\langle 100 \rangle$ fibers, regardless of alloy composition. It should be noted that the above rotational paths

FIGURE 4.8: (a) IPF parallel to compression direction predicted by Secant model for matrix for the two-extreme composition. (b) Strain partitioning represented by the relative activity of the slip systems as a function of true strain. (c) Predicted average active slip systems per grain as a function of true strain.

were predicted without considering the influence of neighboring grains. As has been discussed by several researchers in the past, the deformation behavior of individual grains depends heavily on their neighborhood. The local state of stress within the individual grains can, depending on the environment, deviate significantly from the macroscopic imposed deformation, which in turn influences the selection of active slip systems and thus the lattice reorientation. Nevertheless, determining local stress state is a difficult process that requires high-precision EBSD measurements of elastic strains and internal stresses.

The elastic strain tensor of several individual grains can only be measured by performing three-dimensional *in-situ* diffraction experiments using high-energy X-rays and neutrons that can penetrate deep into crystals. Even with such high-end experiments, the best approach to determining the exact state of stress is still being discussed in the literature. Therefore, we will only make a qualitative attempt to understand the role of the local

neighborhood in the texture evolution. In the present work the effect of the local neighborhood manifests itself in the form of an increasing volume fraction ratio of $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ fibers with increasing tungsten content. As previously demonstrated via VPSC, running Secant simulations without considering the neighboring orientations did not provide a satisfactory match to the experimental texture, particularly for the 98W-2M alloy. Only when texture simulations were performed by pairing five randomly oriented grains, a reasonable match was reached. A clear picture of the role of the neighbors can be obtained from the lattice rotation schematic in Figure 4.9 (a). It can be considered that the orientations that are close to the deviation line follow rather unpredictable rotation paths compared to orientations that are far away from the deviation line. A slight fluctuation due to the local neighborhood can lead to the orientation being shifted from above the divergence line downwards and vice-versa. As a result, the grain will now follow completely new rotation path compared to the path it should take based on its initial orientation. On the other hand, the grains that are far from the divergent line can pick up small random fluctuations due to the neighbors and continue to follow the predicted path of rotation, albeit at reduced speeds. Looking at the initial random texture in the present case, where a large proportion of grains lie above the divergent line, it can be said that a greater number of grains make the transition from above the divergent line to the bottom and not vice versa. Subsequently, these grains then rotate in direction $\langle 100 \rangle$ compared to $\langle 111 \rangle$. The rotation in the $\langle 100 \rangle$ direction is also energetically favourable since the Taylor factor is steadily decreasing [155]. It is known that grains with a lower Taylor factor are considered to be ‘soft grains’ in which the imposed deformation can be easily accommodated, compared to “hard grains” with a higher Taylor factor. The hard grains develop more deformation heterogeneities compared to the soft grains and are therefore more sensitive to the local neighborhood. For a 98W-2M alloy, where contact between tungsten-tungsten particles is significant, the fluctuations are more frequent than for an 80W-20M alloy, where the contact between tungsten-tungsten particles is limited. As a result, the 80W-20M alloy will follow the predicted lattice rotation paths and develops a significantly stronger $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber compared to the $\langle 100 \rangle$ fiber. On the other hand, the 98W-2M alloy develops a stronger $\langle 100 \rangle$ fiber with high probability of fluctuations. Further confirmation of our arguments can be obtained from EBSD measurements.

As previously shown, the deformation heterogeneity is significantly higher for the 98W-2M alloy compared to the 80W-20M alloy. The amount of grain fragmentation, shown in terms of Feret diameter, is also higher for the 98W-2M alloy. All of these effects can be attributed to unforeseen rotation paths in the 98W-2M alloy due to the local neighborhood, which prevents homogenous deformation of the grain as a whole. Different parts of the same grain

FIGURE 4.9: (a) Schematic of lattice rotation during uniaxial compression for b.c.c. (b) Representative grains showing the orientations lying on both side of divergent line in a single grain.

deform via different slip systems, which leads to the development of a strong orientation gradient and ultimately to fragmentation. Some representative grains are shown in Figure 4.9 (b) where it can be observed that one part of the grain is above the divergence line while the other is below it. This supports our argument that a higher probability of fluctuations could be the determining factor for a stronger $\langle 100 \rangle$ fiber in the 98W-2M alloy. Other theories of texture evolution such as the changing the mode of deformation from Taylor-type to Sachs-type to explain the strengthening of $\langle 100 \rangle$ fiber is not applicable since Sachs deformation results in an inappropriately strong $\langle 100 \rangle$ fiber, this is not observed experimentally. The overall texture is still dominated by $\langle 111 \rangle$ fibers, although the random fluctuations slightly increase the volume fraction of $\langle 100 \rangle$ fibers. Also, the role of strain rate sensitivity, which is sometimes used in the texture community, is limited here because the deformation was performed at room temperature and at nominal strain rates. Therefore, it can be said that the shift in orientations along the divergent line due to local neighborhood provides a reasonable explanation for the texture evolution of b.c.c. tungsten particles. The texture evolution of the matrix phase can again be understood by the schematic shown in Figure 4.9 (a). Since the slip systems in f.c.c. have their planes and directions interchanged with respect to (w.r.t) b.c.c., one can say that the direction of rotation is opposite to that shown in the schematic diagram. In this case, the grains aggregate in the vicinity of $\langle 110 \rangle$ and the divergent line behaves like a convergent line. Since the grains tend to rotate in direction $\langle 110 \rangle$ regardless of their initial orientation, the role of local neighborhood or random fluctuations during f.c.c. compression is limited.

Several authors have attempted to discover the critical conditions that lead to the development of adiabatic shear banding. In fine-grained WHA with $\langle 100 \rangle$ texture, adiabatic shear banding is shown to be important for promoting the “self-sharpening effect” [122]. When softening mechanisms outweigh all other hardening effects, a shear band is more

likely to form. The formation of shear bands is expedited for composites because smaller particles cause a greater strain gradient. The crack does not propagate continuously along the shear band, but instead deviates to the tungsten-tungsten interface as a result of the small shear strain within the shear band [156]. According to the findings, a high tungsten content results in an increase in $\langle 100 \rangle$ texture and fine particle size, which may result in increased penetration performance.

4.7 Summary

In this chapter a uniaxial compression test was carried out in order to understand the deformation mechanisms and the texture evolution of WHA. The most important findings of the present work are summarized below.

1. The texture evolution of the b.c.c. tungsten particles can be characterized by the development of $\langle 111 \rangle + \langle 100 \rangle$ double fiber texture, whereas a $\langle 110 \rangle$ fiber evolved in the f.c.c. matrix phase. The effect of composition is manifested in terms of relative proportion of $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ fibers where the volume fraction ratio of $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ fibers increase with increasing tungsten content.
2. Texture simulations via VPSC suggested that a secant type deformation pattern was followed in the WHA instead of the Sachs-type deformation. However, Secant-type deformation combined with the lattice co-rotation scheme to include the effect of neighboring orientations was essential to correctly reproduce the experimental textures. A five-grain pair was used for the 98W-2M alloy, while a two-grain pair was used for the 80W-20M alloy to run the simulations.
3. The physical interpretation of the role of neighbors in increasing the $\langle 100 \rangle$ fiber is provided in view of a high probability of fluctuations in the 98W-2M alloy leading to a shift in orientations from above the $[110] - [411]$ divergent line to below it and the subsequent rotation in the direction of the $\langle 100 \rangle$ corner.

Chapter 5

Texture and microstructure evolution during plane-strain compression of WHA

5.1 Background

In the previous [Chapter 4](#), we analysed the effect of tungsten content and uniaxial compression loading on different WHA. The evolution of microstructure and crystallographic texture was complemented with VPSC simulation. In the [chapter 2](#), it was shown that the majority of the research has been conducted within an empirical framework, with little consideration given to the operative slip systems and the mode of deformation. In this chapter, 90W-7Ni-3Fe alloy will be used, and a high strain of up to $\varepsilon_{vm} = -2.66$ in plane strain compression will be applied in order to further investigate the deformation behaviour. The goal of this investigation is to better understand how the WHA behave when subjected to high strain. The result was investigated further, and its interpretation was made in terms of crystal plasticity. In order to get a better understanding of the operative deformation micro-mechanisms, a systematic experimental study was carried out after various levels of rolling reduction. This study was based on measurements of PF and EBSD. The experimental study is also appropriately supplemented by self-consistent texture simulations carried out with the help of VPSC and CPFPT.

The as-sintered samples were rolled upto 90% rolling reduction. The samples were retained after 30% ($\varepsilon = -0.41$), 50% ($\varepsilon = -0.8$), 75% ($\varepsilon = -1.6$) and 90% ($\varepsilon = -2.66$)

FIGURE 5.1: Schematic of the planes for bulk texture by neutron diffraction and microtexture by EBSD measurement.

rolling reductions to perform texture and microstructure investigation. The sintered and deformed samples were sectioned and subjected to metallography for data collection of EBSD and bulk texture. The microstructure of as-sintered sample was done using an optical microscope with digital image acquisition capability. For EBSD analysis, the samples were sectioned in TD and the scan was performed on RD-ND plane. For macro texture measurement, samples were stacked along ND to form a 1 cm^3 Cube. Figure 5.1 shows the schematic of planes where the EBSD and texture measurements were carried out.

Neutron diffraction of deformed samples were conducted using neutron diffractometer STRESS-SPEC located at Germany's neutron source "Forschungsneutronenquelle Heinz Maier-Leibnitz" (FRM II) in Garching. The Germanium monochromator was selected using the $\{511\}$ reflection yielding a wavelength (λ) of 1.68 \AA for neutron diffraction. The slit on the incident beam side was $5 \text{ mm} \times 10 \text{ mm}$. The take-off angles (2θ) were varied from 35° to 90° allowing to capture the three-PF of each phase. A coordinate measuring machine (CMM) laser scanner was used to ensure the centre of beam remains at the middle of the sample. The tilt and rotation of the sample was performed by Stäubli-6-axis robotic arm. This robotic arm was also used to change the samples automatically for texture measurement. Vanadium standard sample was used to compensate the instrumental errors. For tungsten phase 110, 200 and 211 incomplete PF were measured, while 111, 200 and 220 PF were measured for Ni-W-Fe phase. All the incomplete PF were used to calculate the ODF using MTEX toolbox of MATLAB[®] [157].

5.2 Results and discussion

5.2.1 Starting material

Figure 5.2 shows the initial characteristics of as sintered WHA. Figure 5.2(a) shows the optical microscope (OM) indicating the spherical nature the tungsten grain surrounded by contiguous matrix phase in as-sintered condition. The phase fraction after sintering, based on area fraction, was 0.84 and 0.16 for tungsten and matrix phases, respectively. The increase of phase fraction in matrix phase can be associated to the dissolution of tungsten element during the LPS. Figure 5.2(b) and (c) show the IPF map and its corresponding phase map of the WHA, respectively. The IPF map shows the presence of random orientation of tungsten grain, and single orientation of matrix due to large grain size of matrix phase. Both phases have a very low orientation gradient, indicating a strain-free microstructure with tungsten grains with an average grain size of $28 \pm 1.2 \mu m$ and matrix phase with $175 \pm 13 \mu m$. The texture data is represented in terms of important ODF sections namely $\varphi_2 = 45^\circ$ for b.c.c. and $\varphi_2 = 0^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 65° for f.c.c. materials. In Figure 5.2(d), the bulk texture data shows that the tungsten phase had a weak texture in the as-sintered state. The texture of both the phases, tungsten and matrix, can be characterized by the mrd of crystallites with a maximum intensity of 1.6 and 1.4 mrd, respectively. It should be noted that, due to the large grain size of the matrix phase, the PF measurement was performed on three different samples and the data collected were combined to obtain the texture for the matrix phase.

5.2.2 Evolution of rolling texture in tungsten phase

The rolling textures in b.c.c. materials are conveniently illustrated via the $\varphi_2 = 45^\circ$ section and the two main fibers $\alpha_{b.c.c}$ and γ in the Euler space. The $\alpha_{b.c.c}$ fiber can be described by the line connecting $\{001\}\langle 110 \rangle$ with $\{111\}\langle 110 \rangle$ which is the $\langle 110 \rangle \parallel$ RD, while the γ fiber runs from $\{111\}\langle 110 \rangle$ to $\{111\}\langle 112 \rangle$ equivalent to $\langle 111 \rangle \parallel$ ND. These two fibers are illustrated schematically in Figure 5.3(a). Based on intensity variation across these two fibers, texture evolution of tungsten particles will be interpreted. Figure 5.3(b-e) shows the $\varphi_2 = 45^\circ$ section after different rolling reductions. At low to intermediate levels of reduction (30% and 50%), the texture of tungsten particles can be characterized by the presence of a weak and incomplete $\alpha_{b.c.c}$ fiber. The γ fiber is also weak with an intensity of $\sim 2-3$ mrd. The $\alpha_{b.c.c}$ fiber shows intensity maxima's near $\{001\} \langle 110 \rangle$ rotated Cube position and $\{112\} \langle 110 \rangle$ position, respectively, while the γ fiber shows a maximum at

FIGURE 5.2: Different maps of as-sintered 90W-7Ni-3Fe alloy (a) Optical Micrograph (b) IPF map (c) Phase map (d) ODF of the starting texture of tungsten phase.

$\{111\} \langle 112 \rangle$ position along with some intensity at $\{111\} \langle 110 \rangle$. Upon increase in rolling reduction to higher levels, several changes were observed in the crystallographic texture. Firstly, there is a considerable increase in the sharpness of texture, which is depicted via a texture index in the ODF sections. The texture index increases from ~ 1.14 at low strain levels to ~ 3.25 at higher strain levels. This type of behavior is characteristic of slip-based deformation where texture evolution occurs by gradual change in lattice orientation. Apart from texture sharpening, it can also be observed that $\alpha_{b.c.c}$ fiber strengthens significantly compared to γ fiber. Distinct intensity maxima's can be observed at rotated Cube position and $\{112\} \langle 110 \rangle$ position along the $\alpha_{b.c.c}$ fiber with intensity of nearly 11 times random after 90% rolling reduction. On the other hand, γ fiber remains weak with maximum intensity of 3-4 mrd. The maxima position along the γ fiber also shifts from $\{111\} \langle 112 \rangle$ to $\{111\} \langle 011 \rangle$ after 90% rolling reduction. The evolution of $\alpha_{b.c.c}$ and γ fiber can be understood in a simple manner by comparing the intensity variation across these fibers at different levels of plastic strain (Figure 5.4(a) and (b)). The governing factors behind evolution of strong rotated Cube in the $\alpha_{b.c.c}$ fiber and the shift in the maxima position

from $\{111\}\langle 112\rangle$ to $\{111\}\langle 011\rangle$ along γ fiber has been discussed in Section 5.3.

5.2.3 Evolution of rolling texture in the matrix

A complete representation of texture evolution of the f.c.c. matrix at different levels of strain is done by showing $\varphi_2 = 0^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 65° sections of ODF (Figure 5.5(a-e)). Firstly, it can be observed that texture of the f.c.c. matrix is relatively weak compared to b.c.c. tungsten particles even after 90% rolling reduction. This can be attributed to smaller volume fraction of f.c.c. matrix compared to tungsten particles. Apart from texture intensity, there are several other interesting features which can be observed in the ODF sections. After 30% rolling reduction, the characteristic Copper type texture comprising of $\{112\} \langle 11\bar{1} \rangle$ Copper / $\{4\ 4\ 11\} \langle 11\ 11\ 8 \rangle$ Dillamore, $\{123\} \langle 6\bar{3}\bar{4} \rangle$ S and $\{110\} \langle 1\bar{1}2 \rangle$ Brass evolves in the f.c.c. matrix. The Copper type texture further consolidates after 50% rolling reduction. It should be noted that intensity maxima in the $\varphi_2 = 45^\circ$ section after 30% and 50% rolling reduction is at the Dillamore position ($\varphi_1 = 90^\circ, \phi = 27^\circ, \varphi_2 = 45^\circ$) instead of the Copper position ($\varphi_1 = 90^\circ, \phi = 30^\circ, \varphi_2 = 45^\circ$). This is shown clearly by plotting the τ fiber (Figure 5.4(c)) which runs from rotated Cube to Goss position via the Dillamore and Copper position. The intensity maxima at Dillamore position instead of Copper position is an important observation as this confirms the deformation mode in the f.c.c. matrix to be close to upper bound model [158]. With further increase in rolling reduction, it can be observed that the intensity maxima shift from Dillamore position and moves towards the Copper position (Figure 5.3(c)). This is again a key observation as several deformation mechanisms which can cause this transition that have been reported in the literature [159, 160]. The first mechanism is the grain geometry-based lath model where ε_{13} shear is relaxed at higher strains owing to elongated nature of grains which in turn reduces the incompatibility issues near the grain boundaries [161]. This model has been applied in the past to shift the intensity maxima from Dillamore to Copper position [162, 163]. The other mechanism is based on slip localization on the co-planar slip systems which causes a negative rotation about TD and hence increase the ϕ angle [164]. The localization of slip on co-planar slip systems is also known to be followed by appearance of shear bands which also cause large rotations about TD.

Similar to observations in the previous paragraphs, the intensity maxima in the $\varphi_2 = 65^\circ$ section appears at $\varphi_1 = 65^\circ, \phi = 27^\circ, \varphi_2 = 65^\circ$ instead of the ideal S position $\varphi_1 = 59^\circ, \phi = 37^\circ, \varphi_2 = 63^\circ$. However, with increase in rolling reduction, the position of intensity maxima in the $\varphi_2 = 65^\circ$ section shifts towards the ideal S position. This behavior has also been observed in the past and can be attributed to relaxation of ε_{23} shear [165, 166].

FIGURE 5.3: (a) Schematic of ODF key showing relevant fibers (b-e) ODF ($\varphi_2 = 45^\circ$ sections) for 30%, 50%, 75% and 90% rolled alloys.

FIGURE 5.4: (a-b) b.c.c. and γ fiber for tungsten phase of 30%, 50%, 75% and 90% rolled WHA, respectively (c) τ fiber of matrix phase of 30%, 50%, 75% and 90% rolled WHA.

The observed shift in positions of texture components with increase in rolling reduction suggests transition from upper bound models to relaxed constraint pancake model where both ε_{13} and ε_{23} shears are relaxed. Further verification of the applicability of relaxed constraint model is shown via texture simulations in Section 5.3. The strengthening of the Goss and Brass component at rolling deformations as high as 90 percent is an additional important aspect of the evolution of the texture. It is important to note that during rolling deformation, secant and relaxed upper bound type models generally predict that Copper and S components will be in the stable end positions. As a result, the presence of a Goss/Brass component is intriguing and calls for additional research to be conducted. The texture simulations and microstructural characteristics that are going to be shown in the following two sections provide a detailed explanation for the type of texture evolution that was just described.

FIGURE 5.5: (a) Schematic of ODF keys corresponding to $\varphi_2=0^\circ$, 45° and 65° sections highlighting the important texture component (b-e) ODF ($\varphi_2=0^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 65°) of matrix phase for 30%, 50%, 75% and 90% rolled WHA.

5.2.4 Evolution of microstructure with rolling reduction

The EBSD micrograph of the 30% rolled WHA is shown in Figure 5.6(a). The presence of prominent orientation gradients can be clearly observed in the tungsten particles. This becomes more evident in the grain reference orientation deviation (GROD) shown in Figure 5.6(b). GROD evaluates misorientation of individual pixels within a grain with respect to the average orientation of the grain [167] and hence is ideally suited to depict the presence of orientation gradients. It can be observed that the large gradients in orientation are present at both tungsten-tungsten and tungsten-matrix interface. In addition, large gradients in orientation can also be observed within the tungsten particles. Apart from the orientation gradients another interesting observation is w.r.t the aspect ratio of tungsten particles. It can be observed in Figure 5.6(a) that tungsten particles of 30% rolled sample are fairly equiaxed and do not show any elongation along the rolling direction. This can be attributed to strain partitioning at the microscopic level where the soft f.c.c. matrix phase accommodates most of the imposed deformation compared to the hard b.c.c. tungsten particles.

Upon 50% reduction, it can now be observed that the aspect ratio of the tungsten particles has clearly changed, and the particles are elongated along the rolling direction (Figure 5.6(c)). This can be attributed to the transfer of majority of the imposed strain from the strain hardened f.c.c. matrix to the relatively lesser strain hardened tungsten particles. The aspect ratio (defined as ratio of maximum feret and minimum feret diameter) of tungsten particles was determined to be 3.08 ± 0.21 . The GROD maps shown in Figure 5.6(d) reveal a similar story as shown previously for the 30% rolled sample viz. the presence of orientation gradients.

The microstructure after 70% rolling reduction (Figure 5.7(a-b)) reveals the occurrence of band like features in f.c.c. matrix that are typically observed in heavily rolled materials [168]. These bands can be observed much more clearly in the band contrast map overlapped with phase map. Typically, these bands can be referred as MSBs. The occurrence of MSBs supports our previous argument of strain partitioning between the matrix and tungsten particles where the soft matrix phase accommodates majority of the imposed deformation in the initial stages of deformation compared to the hard tungsten particles. As a result, there is intense dislocation activity in the f.c.c. matrix phase which in turn results in early exhaustion of strain hardening ability. It is well known that the criteria for the commencement of shear banding is when $d\sigma/d\varepsilon = 0$ [169]. In order to determine the orientation of crystallites present within the shear bands, a high magnification EBSD scan

FIGURE 5.6: (a) IPF map of 30% rolled WHA (b) GROD map for 30% rolled WHA (c) IPF map of 50% rolled WHA (d) GROD map of 50% rolled WHA sample.

of the area marked in Figure 5.7(b) was carried out. The high magnification image, Figure 5.7(c) with marked A, B, C, D and E notation shows the presence of MSBs in both matrix and tungsten phases. Figure 5.7(d) shows the partitioned IPF map of matrix having MSBs and its corresponding ODF plots are shown in Figure 5.7(e). The ODF plot shows that most of the crystallites are distributed between Goss and Brass position which is $\{110\} \parallel \text{ND}$. This finding also confirms that the development of Goss and Brass texture is owing to the emergence of MSBs at high strain, which are responsible for the development of Goss and Brass textures.

These MSBs have a significant impact on the formation of texture at the macroscopic level, as will be demonstrated later on through the use of simulations of texture. Regarding the tungsten particles, it is easy to infer that there is further elongation along the rolling direction, which results in an increase in the aspect ratio to 6.42 ± 1.3 . The tungsten particles continue to develop orientation gradients and show evidence of the occurrence of MSBs that are restricted to the $\langle 111 \rangle \parallel \text{ND}$ orientation. Figure 5.8(a-b) displays some

FIGURE 5.7: (a) Band contrast map overlapped with phase map of 75% rolled WHA (b) IPF map of 75% rolled WHA alloy (c) Magnified IPF map showing different region of micro shear band in matrix along with their ODF ($\varphi_2=45^\circ$) (d) IPF map of partitioned matrix phase. (e) ODF of partitioned matrix labelled accordingly.

representative SEM images that were taken after the rolling was performed at a rolling-reduction of 90%. The microstructure reveals the presence of shear bands that traverse multiple tungsten particles and matrix. It can therefore be concluded that the strain hardening ability of the tungsten particles becomes exhausted after a rolling reduction of 90%, which in turn causes macroscopic instability and the appearance of shear bands throughout the entirety of the sample's cross-section. These bands have an inclination of 30° to 35° with respect to the rolling direction. Figure 5.8(c) and (d) shows the IPF map of shear band and region away from the shear band. The micro-texture development within shear bands shows the presence of only rotated Cube texture but the region away from shear band was having $\alpha_{b.c.c.}$ and γ fibers, shown in Figure 5.8(e) and (f), respectively.

5.3 Simulation Results

5.3.1 VPSC Result

As mentioned previously, simulations in the framework of secant model will be carried out to understand texture evolution during rolling of the b.c.c. tungsten particles and the f.c.c. matrix. It is well known that strain compatibility is a much stricter criterion compared to stress compatibility in polycrystalline materials, more so for two-phase materials where compatibility must be additionally maintained at inter-phase boundary apart from the usual grain boundary. Hence, it can be envisioned that secant type deformation pattern will be more appropriate for performing texture simulations compared to the lower bound tangent interaction scheme. In addition, the subtle hints from the experimental texture results also indicated the deformation pattern to be secant type. Based on these ideas, secant interaction in VPSC simulation was performed for the WHA rolled up to 30% and 50% reduction. For tungsten particles, pencil glide on $\{110\}$, $\{112\}$ and $\{123\}$ slip planes containing the common $\langle 111 \rangle$ slip direction was chosen, while for the f.c.c. matrix $\{111\}$ $\langle 110 \rangle$ octahedral slip system was selected. The simulation results in terms of characteristic ODF sections are shown in Figure 5.9(a-b). It can be observed that there is a satisfactory agreement between experimental and simulation results. The main features of b.c.c. tungsten particles that is rotated Cube component and $\{112\}$ $\langle 110 \rangle$ component along the $\alpha_{b.c.c.}$ fiber and the $\{111\}$ $\langle 112 \rangle$ component along the γ fiber are reproduced satisfactorily by the secant interaction model. Similarly, the Copper/Dillamore, S and Brass components observed in the f.c.c. phase are also captured in the simulations. The higher texture intensity at Dillamore compared to Copper position is also predicted by the secant interaction texture simulations.

FIGURE 5.8: (a-b) Secondary electron image of 90% rolled WHA (c) IPF map of shear band. (d) IPF map of region away from shear band (e) ODF of tungsten phase for shear band region (f) ODF of the random region away from the shear band.

Considering the success of secant interaction model for the 30% and 50% rolled sample, it was further extended for the samples which underwent 75% and 90% rolling reduction. The texture of the b.c.c. phase via $\varphi_2 = 45^\circ$ ODF section is shown in Figure 5.10(a). It can be observed that the agreement between experimental and simulated texture deteriorates at higher rolling reductions. Several features observed in the experimental texture such as the rotated Cube component, the complete $\alpha_{b.c.c}$ fiber and the shift in texture maxima from $\{111\} \langle 112 \rangle$ to $\{111\} \langle 110 \rangle$ along the γ fiber are not captured in the simulations. Similar mismatch between experimental and simulated textures was also observed for the

FIGURE 5.9: (a) ODF ($\varphi_2=45^\circ$) of tungsten phase for 30% and 50% rolling reduction (b) ODF ($\varphi_2=0^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 65°) of matrix phase for 30% and 50% rolling reduction.

f.c.c. phase, although it is not shown here for the sake of brevity. The disagreement between experimental and simulated textures can be understood by examining the microstructures at higher rolling reductions, where it can be observed that the grains are flattened and elongated along the rolling direction compared to its relatively equiaxed nature at lower rolling reductions.

In such scenarios, Van Houtte and his coworkers [170] developed a relaxed constraint model where the strict compatibility requirement at the grain boundaries in the full constraint (FC) Taylor model can be relaxed by setting free ε_{13} and ε_{23} shears (Figure 5.10(b)). This allows individual grains to undergo different amount of strain (shape change) compared to the macroscopically imposed strain. However, this would only create small amount of misfits owing to elongated and flattened nature of the grain. These misfits can be accommodated by introducing small amount of geometrically necessary dislocations (GND). The strain matrix for the relaxed constraint or the better-known pancake model can be expressed as

$$\varepsilon_{\text{macroscopic}} = \varepsilon_{\text{zz}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & \text{free} \\ 0 & 0 & \text{free} \\ \text{free} & \text{free} & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5.1)$$

At the slip system level, the relaxation of shears manifests in terms of decrease in the number of average active slip systems (AVACS). As a typical example, AVACS decreases

FIGURE 5.10: (a) ODF $\varphi_2=45^\circ$) of tungsten phase for 75% and 90% rolling reduction by secant model (b) Schematic representation of flat grain in rolled sample showing misfit that can be tolerated in face ‘B’ and ‘C’.

from nearly 5 in the secant interaction model to 3 in the pancake model for f.c.c. materials [171]. We conducted the pancake model simulation after taking all of this information into consideration. Figure 5.11 (a-b) shows the simulated ODF sections of the b.c.c. and f.c.c. phase after 75% and 90% rolling reduction. It can be observed that there is significant improvement in the agreement between experimental and simulated texture. The main characteristic of the b.c.c. tungsten particles after 90% rolling reduction viz. a complete $\alpha_{b.c.c}$ fiber with maxima at rotated Cube and $\{112\} \langle 110 \rangle$ position and the shift in texture maxima along the γ fiber from $\{111\} \langle 112 \rangle$ to $\{111\} \langle 110 \rangle$ is reproduced satisfactorily by the pancake model.

A similar improvement can also be observed for the f.c.c. phase by employing the pancake model (Figure 5.13(c)). The experimentally observed behavior of shift in texture maxima from Dillamore to Copper position in the $\varphi_2 = 45^\circ$ section is captured reasonably. Similarly, the shift in texture maxima towards ideal ‘S’ position in $\varphi_2 = 65^\circ$ section is also predicted by the pancake model. However, the pancake model predicts a stronger Copper and S component compared to Brass/Goss component. The experimental texture illustrated higher intensity at Brass position compared to Copper and S position after 90% rolling reduction. This discrepancy can be understood by examining the microstructure

FIGURE 5.11: (a) Simulated ODF ($\varphi_2=45^\circ$) of tungsten phase for 75% and 90% rolling reduction (b) Simulated ODF ($\varphi_2=0^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 65°) of matrix phase for 75% and 90% rolling reduction.

of f.c.c. matrix where several MSBs can be observed after 75% and 90% rolling deformation. The orientation of crystallites present within the MSBs was observed to be near Brass/Goss position (Figure 5.7(c)). Hence, the experimentally observed higher texture intensity at Brass position can be attributed to the MSBs. Unfortunately, a full-scale texture model which includes the contribution from MSBs is yet to be developed. In this scenario, only a qualitative argument can be made about the presence of Brass and Goss orientations within the MSBs. It is now well established that the Copper orientation is more prone to formation of MSBs compared to other orientations due to asymmetry in slip distribution [172]. Hence, we prepared a synthetic Copper texture (Figure 5.13(a)) using MTEX software with halfwidth of 10° and subjected it to unidirectional shear deformation [173]. Subsequently, the output texture was rotated by 35° about TD (Figure 5.13(b)) to represent the shear texture components in the RD-TD reference frame. Figure 5.12 shows the flow chart for the algorithm of shear consideration. It can be clearly observed that Copper grains subjected to shear deformation and subsequently rotated by 35° result in Brass and Goss orientations.

FIGURE 5.12: Flowchart for the algorithm of shear consideration.

FIGURE 5.13: (a) ODF ($\varphi_2=0^\circ$, 45° and 65°) of synthetic Copper texture with a halfwidth of 10° (b) ODF ($\varphi_2=0^\circ$, 45° and 65°) of unidirectional shear shown in roll frame of reference (c) Schematic of shear after 35° rotation by TD.

5.3.2 CPFFT Simulation

Moulinec and Suquet [174] were the first people to use the spectral method in order to find a solution to the mechanical boundary value problem. The primary benefit of the spectral method is its iterative solution algorithm with the FFT, which is both memory- and time-efficient. Previous research [175, 176, 177] has demonstrated the superior performance of the spectral method over the FEM. The crystal plasticity constitutive model, which incorporates the phenomenological crystal plasticity described by Hutchinson, has been integrated into the open-source simulation framework known as DAMASK.

5.3.2.1 Construction of the RVE based on the EBSD data

The creation of an representative volume element (RVE) is the initial stage of the pre-processing phase for DAMASK simulations. It is not possible to run large-scale texture simulations with almost 10,000 grains using DAMASK because of the high computational cost associated with running these simulations. However, by running DAMASK simulations over an RVE, one can obtain quite a few essential pieces of information regarding the deformation response of the material. The ebsd data were first converted to a *.geom file using the function `ang2geom.py`, which maintained the same grid dimension as the ebsd data during the conversion. In order to decrease the amount of work that needed to be done computationally, the dimension along the “Z-direction” was constrained. Following the completion of the preprocessing phase, the obtained discretized RVE was visualised using the free software Paraview. The generated RVE for simulation based on EBSD is shown in Figure 5.14.

5.3.2.2 Boundary/Loading Conditions

After preparing the RVE, the next step in pre-processing involves defining the elastic and plastic properties as well as the deformation conditions. The various elastic and plastic properties required to run DAMASK simulations are detailed in Table 5.1. The deformation condition was specified by imposing the periodic boundary conditions in plane strain state:

$$\dot{\mathbf{F}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & * \end{bmatrix} \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1} \quad \& \quad \mathbf{P} = \begin{bmatrix} * & * & * \\ * & * & * \\ * & * & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ Pa} \quad (5.2)$$

FIGURE 5.14: Representative volume element for DAMASK simulations prepared from the initial EBSD data.

where “ $\dot{\mathbf{F}}$ ” and “ \mathbf{P} ” refer to the rate of the deformation gradient and the first Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensors, respectively. The complementary conditions are expressed by the coefficients indicated by the symbol “*”.

TABLE 5.1: Phenopower law parameters used for rolling simulation of WHA.

Parameters	Tungsten	Matrix
C_{11}	523.0E9	295.3E9
C_{12}	202.0E9	157.3E9
C_{44}	161.0E9	127.2E9
$\dot{\gamma}_0$	0.001 s^{-1}	0.001 s^{-1}
$1/m$	20	20
τ_0	95E6	62E6
τ_s	212E6	157E6
a	2	2
h_0	983E6	125E6
$q_{\alpha\beta}$ (self and coplanar slip systems)	1.0	1.0
$q_{\alpha\beta}$ (non-coplanar slip systems)	1.4	1.4

The simulations were carried out in a total of 2300 iterative steps, with each step corresponding to an increase in strain of 0.1%. The total cumulative strain was calculated to be equal to 2.7, which corresponds to a rolling reduction of $\sim 91\%$. After the simulations, DREAM 3D, Paraview, and MATLAB were used to carry out the post-processing and data visualisation.

FIGURE 5.15: Split violin plot showing the von Mises strain distribution for tungsten and matrix phase at various strain during cold rolling.

5.3.2.3 Stress-strain distribution

The split violin plot for the strain and stress distribution for both phases at various global strains is shown in Figures 5.15 and 5.16. The box plot and histogram plots are useful for comparing summary statistics, but they are biased due to the bin size. Since the majority of the data do not cluster around the median value, a split violin plot was created. It has been seen that the distribution of stress and strain between the phases is both heterogeneous and distinct from one another at every strain. Tungsten phase has a narrow width and a sharp peak, which means that the majority of the points have a value that is closer to the median, whereas matrix phase has a wider peak and the height is smaller when compared to tungsten phase. At each and every strain condition, the matrix phase has a median value that is consistently greater than the tungsten phase.

FIGURE 5.16: Split violin plot showing the von Mises stress distribution for tungsten and matrix phase at various strain during cold rolling.

5.3.2.4 Simulated IPF maps

Figure 5.17 shows the simulated IPF maps in RD-ND plane at various strain levels. During rolling deformation, it is common knowledge that the individual grains have a tendency to become flatter and more elongated, or pancake-shaped, as the rolling reduction increases. Moreover, the presence of deformation heterogeneity in relation to intragranular orientation gradients is evident in the simulated IPF maps.

Figure 5.18 shows the point-to-point misorientation and point-to-origin misorientation along the arrow in different grains rolled at $\varepsilon_{vm} = 0.82$. Some metastable grains have the potential to fragment into different orientation domains when subjected to cold rolling [178]. This type of grain fragmentation is specified by the terms deformation bands (DB) and transition bands (TB). DB are bands that have a low angle of misorientation, ranging from 5° to 15° , and separate adjacent volumes of homogeneous deformation, whereas TB are found as a transition between adjacent deformation bands and have a high angle of misorientation ($>15^\circ$). TB are characterised by diverging orientation changes of the same

FIGURE 5.17: IPF maps at various strain levels (a) $\epsilon_{vm} = 0.14$ (b) $\epsilon_{vm} = 0.82$ (c) $\epsilon_{vm} = 1.7$ (d) $\epsilon_{vm} = 2.7$ (*Lengths are not to scale*).

original grain into different orientations, while the parent orientation is preserved within. In the tungsten phase, grain (a) of Figure 5.18 develops misorientation up to a maximum of 53° , whereas grains (b) of Figure 5.18 and (c) of Figure 5.18 develop misorientation up to a maximum of 25° . The band in grain (a) corresponds to an orientation $(1\bar{1}4) \langle \bar{1}\bar{2}4 \rangle$ (i.e. Euler angles $345^\circ, 22^\circ, 130^\circ$). The grain (d) fragments clearly and forms a distinct grain boundary with a 45° misorientation. Some of the grains exhibit DB, while others exhibit TB. These DB are believed to have originated as a result of multiple slip systems accommodating the strain [179]. Therefore, different lattice rotations and, consequently, orientations are produced if various regions of a grain undergo deformation using a variety of different combinations of slip systems.

5.3.2.5 Stress-Strain Maps

Different regions and phases can carry varying amounts of strains; however, their net strain will always be equal to the macroscopic strain [165]. Analyzing the spatial distribution of equivalent strain and stress maps, as shown in figures 5.19 and 5.20, can yield additional insights regarding the behaviour of the deformation. Three different regions of strain can

FIGURE 5.18: Misorientation profile for selective grain at $\varepsilon_{vm} = 0.82$ showing deformation bands and transition bands

be identified in maps: (a) strain within the tungsten grains, (b) strain within the matrix phase, and (c) strain at the interface. When strain of 0.14 is applied at the start of the simulation, some of the tungsten-matrix interface is carrying almost four times the strain of the overall applied strain. It is important to note that a fraction of the interface between the tungsten and the matrix has very low strain as well. Additionally, the heterogeneity in the matrix phase varies from 0.12 – 0.35, which is equivalent to 2.5 times the applied strain. The majority of the tungsten phase accommodates very little strain. Thus, it can be stated that in the initial stage, the matrix phase rather than the tungsten phase dominates strain accommodation. The trend essentially remained the same as the applied strain was

FIGURE 5.19: Distribution of von-Mises strain in maps at various strain levels (a) $\varepsilon_{vm} = 0.14$ (b) $\varepsilon_{vm} = 0.82$ (c) $\varepsilon_{vm} = 1.7$ (d) $\varepsilon_{vm} = 2.7$ (*Lengths are not to scale*).

increased further; however, the ratio of strain partitioning among phases decreased. The trend has been clearly depicted in Figure 5.22 (a) and (b). Figure 5.22 (a) shows that tungsten phase is carrying more stress which is in accordance with the strain map. The phase accommodating least strain are in high stress and vice-versa. The strain partitioning is further clearly expressed in terms of plotting the additional strain accommodated by matrix in terms of percentage. Strain minima and strain maxima within the individual grains indicate the influence of kinematic hardness in some portions of the sample [180].

In accordance with the strain map, Figure 5.22 (a) shows that the tungsten phase is carrying more stress than matrix. The phase that can take the least amount of strain is currently experiencing the most stress, and vice versa. The phase with the least strain is under high stress, and vice versa. A further clear expression of the strain partitioning can be found in terms of plotting the additional strain accommodated by matrix (in %), as shown in Figure 5.22 (b).

FIGURE 5.20: Distribution of von-Mises stress in maps at various strain levels (a) $\varepsilon_{vm} = 0.14$ (b) $\varepsilon_{vm} = 0.82$ (c) $\varepsilon_{vm} = 1.7$ (d) $\varepsilon_{vm} = 2.7$ (Lengths are not to scale).

5.3.2.6 T-parameter and AVACS

Further information regarding the deformation behaviour can be obtained by analysing the distribution of shear rates on individual slip systems. A statistical parameter (T) related to the distribution of shear rates [181] can be written as

$$T = \frac{\sum_s (\dot{\gamma}_s)^2}{(\sum_s \dot{\gamma}_s)^2} \quad (5.3)$$

The theoretical maximum of the T parameter is 1, which corresponds to a single slip condition (static model), while the theoretical minimum is 0.125, which corresponds to equal distribution of shear rates on eight slip systems. Table 5.2 summarises the value of the T parameter for equal distribution of the shear rates on two, three, four, five, six, seven and eight slip systems.

For a typical case in which two slip systems are active, but the shear rates are not evenly distributed between the two slip systems, it can be easily envisioned that the T parameter will vary between 0.5 and 1, depending upon the skewness of the distribution. Similarly, the T parameter varies between 0.33 and 0.5 with an unequal distribution of the shear

TABLE 5.2: Values of the T parameter for equal and unequal distribution of shear rate on active slip systems.

Number of slip systems	T parameter for equal distribution of shear rate	T parameter for unequal distribution of shear rate
1	1	1
2	0.5	Between 0.5 and 1
3	0.33	Between 0.33 and 0.5
4	0.25	Between 0.25 and 0.33
5	0.2	Between 0.2 and 0.25
6	0.166	Between 0.166 and 0.2
7	0.142	Between 0.142 and 0.166
8	0.125	Between 0.125 and 0.142

rates on three slip systems. In the case of an unequal distribution of the shear rates on four and five slip systems, a similar analogy can be extended to determine the range of the T parameter (Table 5.2). The advantage of performing DAMASK simulations is that information regarding the spatial distribution of shear rates can be easily obtained at each pixel of the representative volume element. Therefore, the range of the T parameter can be computed, which in turn can give an idea about the number of active slip systems. The evolution of the average T parameter with strain is illustrated in Figure 5.21. It can be observed that the range of the T parameter is between ~ 0.1 and 1 at low strain, viz. unequal distribution of the shear rates on almost all slip systems.

As the applied strain is increased further, the T parameter value begins to consistently decrease, indicating the activation of multiple slip systems. This trend continues until the T parameter value becomes constant for three to four slip systems. The distribution plot shown in Figure 5.21 also reveals that the median value of the T parameter of the matrix is always higher than that of the tungsten phase, which suggests that the tungsten deformation process requires a greater number of slip systems. The median value stays in the range of 0.28 to 0.49 for both phases, which suggests that there is activity from three to four different slip systems. In the initial stages of rolling deformation (up to strain level of 0.14), there is some skewness in the distribution of shear rates, resulting in the T parameter varying around ~ 0.49 . However, after intermediate rolling reductions (strain level of 0.82), the T parameter drops down nearly to 0.32-0.37. With further deformation, the T parameter decreases very slowly and reaches a value of 0.28 in tungsten and 0.37 for matrix phase at a strain level of 2.7. Figure 5.22 (c) shows evolution of average value T parameter as a function of Von-Mises strain for WHA and its phase constituent. This data gives some preliminary idea about the number of active slip systems that are present in the material, which is an important insight that can be gleaned from it. In VPSC a

FIGURE 5.21: Split violin plot showing the T-parameter distribution for tungsten and matrix phase at various strain during cold rolling.

system is considered active if the shear rate it contributes is at least 5% of the maximum shear rate in the grain [182, 183]. The same concept was implemented for the output of the DAMASK for each pixel of the RVE. Figure 5.22(d) illustrates the computed AVACS. The plot demonstrates that the matrix begins to deform at a low strain level with two to three slip systems, whereas the tungsten phase requires three to four slip systems. However, as the applied strain is increased further, both phases come to a common average AVACS of 4.2 to accommodate the imposed deformation. It is not within the purview of this thesis to consider the contribution from each individual slip system.

5.3.2.7 Micro and macro mechanical Taylor factor

The concept of macromechanical Taylor factor (M^{macro}) and micromechanical Taylor factor (M^{micro}) was first introduced by Raabe *et al.* [180]. In contrast to M^{macro} , where the shear rate of slip system is normalised by the global Von Mises strain, M^{micro} normalises the shear rate of slip system by the local Von Mises strain at each integration

point. M^{micro} and M^{macro} can be mathematically expressed as in equation 5.4 and 5.5 respectively.

$$M^{micro} = \frac{\sum \gamma^{local}}{\langle \varepsilon_{vm} \rangle^{local}} \quad (5.4)$$

$$M^{macro} = \frac{\sum \gamma^{local}}{\langle \varepsilon_{vm} \rangle^{global}} \quad (5.5)$$

However, it should be noted that the M^{macro} typically differs from the classical Taylor factor determined by homogenization theory. In classical Taylor–Bishop–Hill-type homogenization theory the Taylor factor is defined by Equation 5.6. The M^{micro} map reveals a distribution that is significantly more homogeneous within the grain, whereas the heterogeneity that exists between grains is still present. Figure 5.24 shows the M^{micro} map, which reveals a distribution that is significantly more homogeneous within the grain while retaining the heterogeneity that exists between grains. Although different grains have different M^{micro} values, still these grains appear homogeneous mechanical entity. This result shows that texture modulates the hardness variations rather than dictating the strain path, and heterogeneity between the grains can be attributed to macroscopic boundary condition.

$$M^{homo} = \frac{\sum \gamma^{global}}{\langle \varepsilon_{vm} \rangle^{global}} \quad (5.6)$$

Within the framework of the crystal plasticity finite element simulation, either crystal plasticity finite element methods (CPFEM) or CPFEM, the local crystal shear at each integration point follows the local boundary conditions rather than the global boundary conditions. As a result, it is prudent to interpret the results using the local shear and strain. The M^{macro} map, in figure 5.23, reveals a very heterogeneous spatial distribution similar as Von-Mises strain map presented in Figure 5.19.

FIGURE 5.22: Graphs that illustrate the various properties and characteristics that change depending on the amount of strain applied to WHA and its phases (a) the von Mises stress (b) the additional strain that the matrix phase undergone relative to the tungsten phase in percentage terms (c) T-parameter (d) AVACS (e) Average macro mechanical Taylor factor (f) Average micro mechanical Taylor factor.

FIGURE 5.23: Map of the macromechanical Taylor factor (M^{macro}) (Lengths are not to scale).

FIGURE 5.24: Map of the micromechanical Taylor factor (M^{micro}) (Lengths are not to scale).

5.4 Summary

The microstructure and texture evolution of liquid phase sintered 90W-7Ni-3Fe tungsten heavy alloys were examined in this chapter in attempt to understand the deformation behavior of the material. The macroscopic shear bands are found to be associated with the formation of crystallographic grain-scale shear bands, also known as MSBs, at an early stage of the deformation process. As the plastic strain increases, the grain-scale shear bands in the matrix phase propagate across the tungsten grains, resulting in the formation of a non-crystallographic macroscopic shear band. It has been demonstrated that these MSBs are orientation-dependent on the initial orientation of the crystals, and these shear bands nucleate on the Copper $\{112\}(111)$ oriented grains. By incorporating the Copper texture into the matrix phase, the onset of MSBs formation can be accelerated. Early shear localisation of the shear band may allow for a minimisation in mushroom head formation and hence improved penetration performance. Lowering the stacking fault energy of the matrix phase by alloying with certain elements can also aid in the early onset of MSBs formation.

The important results of the current study are enumerated below.

1. The development of strong rotated Cube in $\alpha_{b.c.c}$ fiber and the shift of maxima location from $\{111\} \langle 112 \rangle$ to $\{111\} \langle 011 \rangle$ along γ fiber can be explained by incorporating the pancake shape of microstructure and hence relaxing the ε_{13} and ε_{23} components of strain matrix. The rotated Cube orientation promotes in the growth of shear bands across the multiple grains, which can be beneficial to minimize the mushroom head.
2. The occurrence of intensity maxima at the Dillamore position in the matrix phase confirms the upper bound deformation model, and the location of the intensity maxima moves from Dillamore to Copper with greater rolling reduction. The intensity shift was explained by the localization of slip on co-planar slip systems which also acts as precursor for the MSBs.
3. The development of rotated Cube in tungsten and Brass texture in matrix occurs due to onset of MSBs and shear bands after exhaustion of strain hardening. The high intensity texture at the Brass location is due to the unidirectional shear deformation of the Copper grain.

Chapter 6

Uniaxial tensile deformation behavior of matrix alloy

Chapter 4 and 5 of thesis explained the deformation behavior of two phase WHA and it was shown that matrix phase accommodates higher strain than the tungsten phase. It was also shown that the matrix phase plays a crucial role in the onset of shear band formation. In the light of importance of matrix phase a detailed investigation of deformation behavior of matrix phase was required. To assess the characteristics of the alloy, it is reasonable to melt it in the conventional way of ingot metallurgy to a composition comparable to that of the matrix phase. The findings may be effectively used to improve the characteristic of WHA with equivalent matrix compositions. It will provide a deeper insight into the relationship between microstructure, texture, and mechanical characteristics of the Ni-W-Fe. When a matrix phase is investigated in depth in isolation from tungsten particles, it will yield a complete and unambiguous understanding of how the matrix, in this case, a Ni-W-Fe alloy, reacts to mechanical tests.

6.1 Background

The size and valency differences are two key parameters determining the amount of solid solubility of certain components in a solid solution. The differences in size and valency between Fe and Ni are 0.4% and 0.2, respectively, whereas the differences in size and valency between W and Ni are 9.7% and 3.0. As a result, it is anticipated that a significant amount of Fe and W will be soluble in the nickel metal. The difference in atomic size

TABLE 6.1: Composition of matrix determined usnig EPMA.

Elements	Mass, %
Ni	53.9 ± 0.02
W	22.7 ± 0.05
Fe	23.3 ± 0.04

results in a significant increase in the lattice constant of the matrix phase and, therefore, in the mechanical properties of the matrix phase [128]. The composition of the alloy was determined by performing the EPMA on the WHA. Figure 6.1(a) shows a small part of a secondary electron micrograph of WHA. The location marked with an asterisk indicates the site where EPMA was carried out to determine the elemental composition of the matrix. The EPMA was carried out at various locations of matrix phase so that interference from the tungsten phase could be kept to a minimum and the correct composition could be determined. The determined composition of the ternary solid solution is listed in Table 6.1. Elemental powders of nickel, iron, and tungsten were blended in a formulation corresponding to a nominal composition of Ni-24W-22Fe. Blended powders were kept in an alumina crucible, which was placed within the hot zone of a resistance-heated furnace and heated to 1500 °C, and held for 1 h to ensure the effective melting of the ingot. The sample was furnace cooled at an average rate of approximately 20 °C/min in the initial stage. The sample was overturned in the crucible to ensure effective dissolution of elements, and the melting procedure was repeated three times. The as-solidified sample was metallographically prepared for EBSD and orientation imaging microscopy (OIM) was performed as described in Chapter 3.

Figure 6.1(b) shows the IPF map of the cast material characterized by large equiaxed grains with a few annealing twins. Figure 6.1(c) shows the cumulative plot of the grain size of the as-cast matrix alloy with a mean grain size of $145 \pm 18 \mu\text{m}$. To estimate the statistically significant measure of the grain size, the size distribution was determined using eight different microstructure images containing nearly 600 grains. XRD of the sample was collected using PANalytical Empyrean machine. The XRD pattern in Figure 6.1(d) shows very little peak broadening, indicating negligible micro-strain and large crystallite size.

The as-cast samples were hot-rolled at 800 °C for up to 50% rolling reduction viz. von-mises strain (ε_{vm}) of 0.8, to reduce the grain size and eliminate any porosity. Following that, the hot-rolled samples were homogenized for 2 h at 800 °C. The resultant sample was again prepared for microstructural characterization. EDS, using the X-max by Oxford, was used for elemental mapping in conjunction with the EBSD scan. Figure 6.2 shows

FIGURE 6.1: (a) SEM micrograph of tungsten heavy alloy with marked EPMA spot (b) IPF map of as-cast Ni-24W-22Fe alloy (c) Grain size distribution of as-cast alloy (d) X-ray diffraction of the as-cast Ni-24W-22Fe alloy.

the microstructural characterization of the homogenized samples. The image quality (IQ) maps overlaid with grain boundary are shown in Figure 6.2(a). The IQ map suggests that the microstructure contains refined grains and that the quality of the diffraction pattern acquired during the EBSD collection was outstanding. Figure 6.2(b) clearly shows the phase map of the material, which reveals the presence of incoherent small tungsten particles across the grain boundary. Nickel, iron, and tungsten elemental mapping in the alloy are shown in Figure 6.2(c-e). The elemental maps show the homogeneous distribution of the elements within the grains and very small precipitation of tungsten at the grain boundary. The IPF map and the grain size distribution of the homogenized sample is shown in Figure 6.2(f) and 6.2(g) respectively. The average grain size of the homogenized sample decreases from 145 μm to 12 μm as a result of grain refinement. The bulk texture of the sample is shown in Figure 6.2(h) using the ODF, $\varphi_2 = 0^\circ$ section, with a maximum intensity of 6.9 and texture index of 4.3. The “RD rotated Cube” texture corresponds to a typical recrystallization texture of f.c.c. materials where recrystallization is dominated by orientation nucleation [184].

Flat dog-bone-shaped tensile specimens with a gauge length of 10 mm from the recrystallized sample were prepared using electric discharge machining, with the longitudinal axes perpendicular to the recrystallized sample’s rolling direction. The tensile test was

FIGURE 6.2: Initial characterization of Ni-24W-22Fe alloy after hot rolling and homogenization (a) IQ map with grain boundary (b) Phase map showing Ni-24W-22Fe alloy, tungsten precipitate and some unindexed points (c-e) EDS elemental mapping (f) IPF map in parallel to normal of the rolling direction (g) Grain size distribution, and (h) ODF of bulk texture taken by X-ray diffraction.

FIGURE 6.3: XRD profile with observed data and fitted data and the difference plot.

performed at the strain rate of $10^{-3} s^{-1}$ on the universal testing machine. Three samples were tested to ensure the repeatability of the tensile behavior. Bulk texture and insitu EBSD was performed as described in [Chapter 3](#).

6.2 Results and Discussion

6.2.1 Determination of Lattice Parameter

6.2.1.1 Using XRD profile

Following the fitting of profiles to the XRD data, Rietveld analysis was carried out with the assistance of X'Pert HighScore plus. The scan angle for analysis ranges from 35° to 80° with a 0.02° angular step. The observed profile, fitted profile, and difference plot are depicted in [Figure 6.3](#). The difference plot displays a range of values from -600 to 600 counts, which shows that the observed data and the fitted data have a very good correlation with one another. After 200 fitting cycles, the goodness of fit converged to 18.7. The background data were then fitted with a polynomial function, and it was assumed that the profile of the peaks was a pseudo-Voigt function with split-width type asymmetry. The lattice parameter was determined to be 3.6094 \AA after cell refinement.

FIGURE 6.4: Plot showing lattice parameter with temperature from neural networking.

6.2.1.2 Using Computational method

David MacKay was the one who initially developed the program for the neural network to train the materials information [185]. The development of the project had as its primary objective the estimation of the lattice parameters of the nickel-based alloys as a function of both the composition and the temperature [186]. The temperature and compositions based on concentrations of elements such as Ni, Co, Cr, Mo, W, Al, Ti, Nb, Ta, Hf, Rh, V, Fe, Ga, Cu, and Au are the inputs for this program. A large database of experimental results was used to train the network. The composition, a Ni-24W-22Fe alloy, and the temperature range were given as inputs to the training module. Figure 6.4 shows the result. The lattice parameter measured at room temperature was 3.606 Å, which is in close agreement with experimentally determined lattice parameter, 3.594 Å, for 20% dissolved tungsten content by Marschnigg et al. [187].

6.2.2 Determination of SFE

6.2.2.1 From XRD Profile

Paterson [188] proved that stacking faults in the $\langle 111 \rangle$ planes of f.c.c. structures were responsible for the broadening of FWHM and shifting of peak position of the diffraction peaks. Following this, it was found that the probability of stacking faults, also known as

TABLE 6.2: Values of constants that are used in the calculation of the stacking fault energy in f.c.c. structures.

Indices of reflection [HKL]	$\sum_b (\pm)L_0/h_0^2(u+b)$
110	1/4
200	-1/2
220	1/4
311	-1/11
222	-1/8
400	1/4

the sum of the probabilities, is related to the size of the crystallites in the lattice as well as the magnitude of the microstrain present in the lattice. Using XRD, Reed and Schramm [189] derived the relationship between SFE, microstrain, and the probability of stacking faults. The SFE can be calculated using the following equation

$$SFE = \frac{K_{111}\omega_0 G_{111} a_0}{\pi\sqrt{3}} \frac{\langle \varepsilon_{50\text{\AA}}^2 \rangle}{\alpha} A^{-0.37} \quad (6.1)$$

where, K_{111} and ω_0 are lattice and materials parameter. G_{111} and a_0 is shear modulus of the (111) plane and lattice parameter respectively. A is the fitting parameter which compensate the elastic anisotropy of the matrix. The factor

$$\frac{\langle \varepsilon_{50\text{\AA}}^2 \rangle}{\alpha} \quad (6.2)$$

consists of the microstrain of the (111) plane and stacking fault probability (α). The (α) can be again calculate using change in the position of the diffraction lines of the (111) and (200) peak positions using the following equation.

$$\Delta(2\theta_{hkl}) = + \frac{90\sqrt{3}\alpha \tan(\theta_{hkl})}{\pi^2 h_0^2 (u+b)} \sum_b (\pm)L_0 \quad (6.3)$$

$\sum_b (\pm)L_0/h_0^2(u+b)$ is the constant and listed in Table 6.2.

Table 6.3 lists the elastic constants and calculated root mean square strain, lattice parameter obtained from the section 6.2.1. It also lists the observed data that was used during the calculation of SFE with this method.

TABLE 6.3: Constants, observed peak position and microstrain measured during the calculation of SFE.

Variables	Values
C11	295.3 GPa
C12	157.3 GPa
C44	127.2 GPa
Microstrain	0.26
G_{111}	88.4 GPa
$K\omega_{111}$	6.6
a_0	3.60 Å
A	1.843
$2\theta_{200}$ (Cold worked)	50.605°
$2\theta_{111}$ (Cold worked)	43.573°
$2\theta_{200}$ (Annealed)	50.681°
$2\theta_{111}$ (Annealed)	43.598°
$\Delta 2\theta$	-0.0503°
α	5.563E-3
γ	33.23 J/m ²

6.2.2.2 Using Thermodynamics

In an alloy, the mechanical behaviour is significantly influenced by the stacking fault energy. At low SFE, dislocation dissociation into Shockley partials might obstruct dislocation glide, favouring mechanical twinning or phase transformation. When phase transition, twinning, or slip govern the plastic deformation process, the relative values of stacking fault energy are as follows: $\gamma_{\text{SFE}}^{\text{phase trans}} < \gamma_{\text{SFE}}^{\text{Twin}} < \gamma_{\text{SFE}}^{\text{Slip}}$. The SFE was calculated using thermodynamic calculations. When stacking faults emerge in fcc structures, the typical fcc packing sequence (...ABCABCABC...) exhibits a partial hcp structure (...ABCABAB-CAB...). The process for determining stacking fault energy is summarised below, and the details may be found in the paper by Curtze et al [190].

$$\gamma_{sfe} = 2\rho\Delta G^{fcc \rightarrow hcp} + 2\sigma \quad (6.4)$$

Where, γ_{sfe} is the stacking fault energy, σ is the surface energy, and $\Delta G^{fcc \rightarrow hcp}$ is the energy difference between the hcp and fcc, and ρ is the molar surface density of the {111} planes. The ρ can be calculated from the equation below.

$$\rho = \frac{4}{\sqrt{3}a^2N_A} \quad (6.5)$$

FIGURE 6.5: SFE of Ni-24W-22Fe alloy vs temperature.

where a is the lattice parameter of matrix alloy and N_A is the Avogadro number. The Gibbs free energy change for phase transition is given as

$$\Delta G^{fcc \rightarrow bcc} = \sum_i X_i \Delta G_i^{fcc \rightarrow bcc} + \sum_{ij} X_i X_j \Omega_{ij}^{fcc \rightarrow bcc} + \Delta G_{magnetic}^{fcc \rightarrow bcc} \quad (6.6)$$

Where, X_i is the molar fraction of a pure metals, $\Delta G_i^{fcc \rightarrow bcc}$ is the free energy contribution term, $\Omega_{ij}^{fcc \rightarrow bcc}$ is the excess energy or regular solution parameter and $\Delta G_{magnetic}^{fcc \rightarrow bcc}$ is the magnetic contribution to free energy. These parameters for the fcc crystal system have been provided by Bellefon *et al.* [191].

With the given data, Specific heat enthalpy of the alloy was calculated to be 45.9 J/g and SFE was calculated to be 32 mJ/m² at room temperature. Because the SFE is more than 30 mJ/m², the microstructure may include annealing twins, however it is predicted that dislocation slip will dominate the plastic deformation.

TABLE 6.4: Summary table of section 6.2.1 and section 6.2.2.

Variables	XRD profile	Computational Method
Lattice Parameter (Å)	3.6094	3.606
SFE mJ/m ²	33.23	32.0

6.2.3 Strain hardening behavior

Figure 6.6 shows the representative tensile behavior of the samples obtained from the tensile test. The engineering stress-strain curve is shown in Figure 6.6(a), the YS and UTS were found to be 324 MPa and 710 MPa, respectively. The high YS to UTS ratio (~ 0.46) suggests that the sample has been undergone a significant amount of strain hardening. Figure 6.6(b) shows the true stress – true strain plot. The strain-hardening exponent, which is computed using Hollomon’s equation [192], can be used to determine the work hardening capability of the sample.

$$\sigma = K\varepsilon^n \quad (6.7)$$

Where, σ is the true stress; ε is the true strain; K is the strength coefficient and n is the strain-hardening exponent, and it is a measure of the strain hardening ability. In logarithmic form, Equation 6.7 can be written as follows [192].

$$\log \sigma = \log K + n \log \varepsilon \quad (6.8)$$

Figure 6.6(c) shows the linear fit plot between $\log \sigma$ and $\log \varepsilon$ to determine the K and n parameters. The strain hardening exponent of 0.53 was determined and which indicates good strain hardening potential in Ni-24W-22Fe alloy. However, it can be noted from Figure 6.6(c) that Hollomon’s equation does not accurately describe the entire stress-strain curve, particularly in the early stages of plastic deformation. It was observed that a significant number of data points in the beginning and at the end were outliers of this model. A normal probability plot of residuals is shown in Figure 6.6(d), indicating the existence of heavy-tailed residuals, i.e., residuals that are not normally distributed and an excessive amount of highly positive and negative residuals are present. Although Hollomon’s equation can provide some information about strain hardening behavior, it is still an empirical model and bears no resemblance to the microstructure. Therefore, considering the competition between dislocation storage and annihilation, the physics-based classical Kocks-Mecking

plot was constructed (Figure 6.6(e-f)). Several unique features can be observed from the Kocks-Mecking plot; first, the strain hardening rate monotonically decreases up to the true strain of 0.15, followed by the recovery of the strain hardening rate, which manifests itself in the form of a hump in the Kocks-Mecking plot. Finally, in the later stages of plastic deformation, the strain hardening rate decreases again until the onset of necking. The high tensile ductility observed in Figure 6.6(a) can be attributed to the recovery of strain hardening rate, which compensates for the decrease in load-bearing cross-section.

In general, the recovery of the strain hardening rate was observed in a few selected materials, namely (twinning induced plasticity (TWIP)) steels, transformation induced plasticity (TRIP) steels and some h.c.p. alloys [193]. For this class of materials, additional deformation mechanisms apart from dislocation slip contribute to imparting recovery in strain hardening [193]. In TWIP steels and h.c.p. alloys, extensive twinning provides dynamic Hall-Petch strength contribution, leading to a reduction in the mean free path of the mobile dislocations [194]. Similarly, stress-induced martensitic transformation in TRIP steels causes dynamic refinement of the microstructure. The dislocation density evolution from the classical Kocks-Mecking relation can be written as [195]:

$$\frac{d\rho}{d\varepsilon} = M \left(\frac{1}{bl} - K_2\rho \right) \quad (6.9)$$

Here, ρ is the dislocation density, K_2 is the annihilation parameter and l is the dislocation mean free path.

From the above equation, it can be envisioned that reducing the mean free path of dislocation accentuates the dislocation storage capacity, resulting in an increased strain hardening rate. The restoration of the strain hardening rate observed in TWIP and TRIP steels can be attributed to the reduction in mean free path due to additional operative deformation mechanisms. However, the band contrast and IPF maps shown in Figure 6.7(a-d) do not indicate any additional phase transformation or deformation mechanisms operating during deformation of the Ni-W-Fe ternary alloy. The only noticeable observation is that equiaxed grains become elongated and distorted as a result of deformation; additionally, the presence of MSBs at an angle of 30° to the Loading direction (LD) can also be observed. The IQ has also deteriorated, and the number of unindexed points has increased, which could be due to distortion in the Kikuchi pattern caused by lattice distortion.

Recently, an interesting observation was made by Yang *et al.* [196], where the restoration of the strain hardening rate was attributed to the transition of the slip behavior from single

FIGURE 6.6: (a) Engineering stress-strain plot (b) True stress vs plastic strain curve (c) Linear fitting of Hollomon's equation on Plot of $\ln(\sigma)$ vs $\ln(\epsilon)$ (d) Normal Probability Plot of the Residuals of $\ln(\sigma)$ (e) strain hardening with plastic strain plot, and (f) Strain hardening with $(\sigma - \sigma_0)$ plot.

slip to multiple slips. The transition in slip behavior can be seen as a possible explanation for the observed hump in the Kocks-Mecking plot. It should be noted that the Ni-W-Fe is a concentrated solid solution with the possibility of SRO. The occurrence of SRO has previously been observed in several concentrated ternary solid solutions [135, 196, 197, 198]. The following paragraph outlines the role of SRO in causing the transition in slip behavior. Considering that the tensile axis of most of the grains in a polycrystalline material lies within the stereographic triangle, the activation of one slip system is favorably influenced compared to other slip systems [199]. The mobile dislocation gliding on the active slip system will destroy the local SRO, causing softening of the glide plane and easy passage of subsequent mobile dislocations. This leads to a localization of slip, which is often referred to as planar slip in the literature [200]. The dislocation locks are very weak in the planar slip mode, resulting in a large dislocation mean free path. This causes a sharp decrease in strain hardening rate in the initial stages of plastic deformation [196].

With a subsequent increase in plastic strain due to planar glide, the slip bands will impinge the grain boundaries, causing stress concentration. In addition, at higher strains, the compatibility requirement at the grain boundaries also becomes the dominant factor [201]. It should be noted that strain compatibility is a much more essential criterion than stress compatibility [202]. Therefore, multiple slip systems are activated during later stages of deformation to maintain compatibility and relieve the stress concentration at the grain boundary due to slip bands. Upon activation of multiple slip systems, stronger dislocation locks such as Lomer – Cottrell lock, Hirth lock, etc. form, which in turn causes a significant decrease in the mean free path of the dislocation [203]. As explained in the previous paragraph, reducing the mean free path of the dislocation causes an increase in the dislocation storage rate and consequently the restoration of the strain hardening capacity. The large grain size of the matrix alloy is also a significant factor that plays an important role in influencing the deformation behavior of alloys. Dislocations can move freely over a large distance and only rarely interfere with one another at the beginning of the plastic deformation process. This resulted in the development of a reciprocal relationship between grain size and dislocation density, referred to as the Hall-Petch relation. Even though dislocations of different grain sizes glide in the same mode, i.e. planar slip mode, the larger the grain sized alloy requires a fewer dislocation systems to achieve the same strain level. As these large-grained material undergoes dislocation in a planar-slip mode, an activation of secondary slip system plunges the mean free path of dislocation.

6.2.4 Influence of planar slip and multiple slips on texture evolution

In order to experimentally verify the transition from single slip to multiple slips, bulk texture measurement was performed. Texture carries the signature of the operative deformation mechanisms, which can help in identifying the nature of slip that occurred to accommodate the plastic deformation. Figures 6.7(a) and 6.7(b) show the IPF parallel to the tensile axis before and after the tensile test, respectively. The initial texture can be characterized by $\langle 001 \rangle$ fiber parallel to the tensile axis, while the final texture has a $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber parallel to the tensile axis with spread towards $\langle 112 \rangle$. This is a unique observation because $\langle 001 \rangle$ fiber parallel to the tensile axis is generally considered as stable texture in uniaxial deformation, but $\langle 100 \rangle$ fiber deteriorates and there is a concomitant increase in the strengthening of the $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber.

When performing VPSC simulation, experimental IPF can be reproduced using a secant scheme if the deformation has multiple slip modes and a tangent scheme if the deformation is planar [204]. The simulated IPF for these two cases is shown in figure 6.8. It can be observed that tangent scheme fails completely to reproduce the experimental texture and the secant scheme has a very high intensity for $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber. Under both circumstances, none of the IPF agrees well with the experimental IPF.

With the help of the insights gained from strain hardening analysis (section 6.2.3), texture simulation was carried out in a staggered manner: for the first 15% of the deformation, the simulation was carried out according to the tangent scheme, and for the remaining 55% of the deformation, the simulation was carried out according to the secant scheme. Figure 6.9 shows the IPF of the simulated texture. This particular case provides a good match between the simulated and the experimental texture. It can be observed that when planar slip mode operates during deformation, the $\langle 100 \rangle$ fiber shifts toward $\langle 112 \rangle$. Upon subsequent activation of multiple slip systems, the texture fiber shifts towards $\langle 111 \rangle$. Figure 6.9(c) represents the AVACS that are activated during the simulation of a tension test. The AVACS value is the mean number of activated slip systems across all grains. Up to a strain of 0.15, a maximum of two slip systems are activated, but the AVACS increases from two to more than five as the strain exceeds 0.15. Hence, the transition from single to multiple slips can be captured successfully using the staggered approach where the transition is modelled using a series of tangent and secant scheme for single and multiple slip respectively.

FIGURE 6.7: (a) IQ map of before tensile test (b) IQ map after tensile test (c) IPF map of the sample before tensile test (d) IPF map of sample after tensile test (e) IPF before test taken from X-ray diffraction (f) IPF after test taken from X-ray diffraction near the neck.

FIGURE 6.8: IPF after VPSC simulation till strain (ε) of 0.7 using (a) tangent scheme (b) secant scheme.

FIGURE 6.9: IPF from simulation (a) using tangent scheme till true strain of 0.15 (b) using secant scheme till true strain of 0.7 (c) Average number of active slip system with strain.

FIGURE 6.10: Schematic of *in-situ* tensile test sample (in inset) and the position at which EBSD data was collected.

6.2.5 Experimental Validation by *in-situ* tensile test

To further clinch the transition of single slip to multiple slips experimentally, *in-situ* EBSD test was performed. Figure 6.10 shows the strains at which movement of the jaw was halted during the *in-situ* tensile test and EBSD data collection was performed. The tensile test was halted at 5%, 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40% elongation. The computer-aided design (CAD) drawing of the *in-situ* specimen is shown in the inset of Figure 6.10.

Figure 6.11 shows the IPF maps parallel to the tensile direction. In order to investigate further, grains with orientation lying inside the stereographic triangle were identified, and the rotation path of those grains was tracked to understand the nature of slip as a function of imposed tensile strain. Figure 6.11 also shows the selection of four different grains labeled G-1 to G-4 on the IPF map. The corresponding rotation path of each of these grains is shown in Figure 6.12.

If only single slip mode deformation is assumed, the grain will move toward the $\langle 112 \rangle$ direction [205], which is a stable end orientation for single slip condition. It can be observed that grain 1, which has starting orientation at the center of the stereographic triangle,

FIGURE 6.11: IPF maps of the *in-situ* tensile test at different strains with four chosen grains for rotation path analysis.

rotates toward $\langle 112 \rangle$ during the tensile deformation. Therefore, it can be unambiguously confirmed that grain 1 majorly deforms by single slip mode. Grain-2 also illustrates a similar rotation path although it does not reach the $\langle 112 \rangle$ orientation exactly. For the similar starting orientation, grain-3 shows the completely distinct and different rotation path compared to grain 1 and 2. It rotates toward the upper corner of the stereographic triangle and so it can clearly be said that grain 3 has multiple slips activated during deformation while grains 1 and 2 were deforming through a single slip. Grain 4 also follows the rotation path, characteristically similar to grains 1 and 2, but the final orientation is far from $\langle 112 \rangle$. It should be noted that the grains are deforming heterogeneously, but for the sake of brevity, a single average orientation for the grains was plotted.

From the above discussion, it can be observed that in the present material, we have a distribution of orientation of grains where some grain has single slip mode while other have already transitioned from single to multiple slips mode. This is causing the grains of similar orientation to follow the different rotation paths. The behavior of the grains is mostly determined by their neighbours. These orientations have an equal likelihood of travelling in either the $\langle 111 \rangle$ or $\langle 112 \rangle$ direction due to the strategic selection of the grains. Under conditions when the contribution of neighbours on plastic deformation is minimal, grains can undergo plastic deformation based on their intrinsic orientation. Under conditions when the local environment plays a significant role, grains must activate

FIGURE 6.12: IPF map chosen from the *in-situ* experiment showing different deformation path.

multiple slip systems in order to maintain compatibility; as a result, they suffer a different rotation path than intrinsic behavior.

6.2.6 CPFFT Simulation

Figure 6.13 shows the IPF maps before and after the CPFFT simulation. Figure 6.13 (a) shows the RVE of the simulation which was converted from experimental EBSD data containing bimodal grain size. The details regarding the conversion of EBSD data to RVE has been given in section 5.3.2.1.

6.2.6.1 Boundary/Loading Condition

The elastic and plastic properties and other parameters have been already mentioned in Table 5.1 and the same parameters for matrix was taken to simulate the tensile loading. The deformation gradient tensor \mathbf{F} and the Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor \mathbf{P} were defined in CPFFT as follows:

$$\dot{\mathbf{F}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & * & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & * \end{bmatrix} \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1} \quad \& \quad \mathbf{P} = \begin{bmatrix} * & * & * \\ * & 0 & * \\ * & * & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ Pa} \quad (6.10)$$

where “ $\dot{\mathbf{F}}$ ” and “ \mathbf{P} ” refer to the rate of the deformation gradient and the first Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensors, respectively. The complementary conditions are expressed by the coefficients indicated by the symbol “*”.

The RVE shown in Figure 6.13 (a) was subjected to a tension load along x up to a displacement gradient of 0.40, which corresponds to a 40% tensile deformation. Only the octahedral slip system was considered during the simulation. After running the tensile simulation, the IPF maps for 5%, 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40% are shown in Figure 6.13(b-f), respectively. In order to compare the change in crystal orientation pixel-by-pixel in the EBSD map, the simulation-induced shape change of grains has been suppressed in IPF plotting. A few notable observations can be seen in the simulated IPF maps, including (i) the development of an orientation gradient in the simulated IPF maps; (ii) the appearance of DB in the large grains; and (iii) similar orientation grains having different rotation paths during the deformation.

FIGURE 6.13: (a) IPF map of Input RVE for the CPFFT simulation (b-f) IPF map of deformed samples after 5%, 10%, 20%, 30% and 40% tensile loading.

Crystal plasticity simulations suggest a large-scale heterogeneity in strain distribution among individual grains for a given macroscopic strain, along with strong influence of the local neighbourhood on deformation response of individual orientations. To capture the deformation response from local neighbourhood during deformation *in-situ* experiment was complemented with CPFFT simulation and grain-to-grain comparison is shown in Figure 6.14. The grains which are oriented near the vertices of the IPF were selected for examination. Figure 6.14 (a-c) shows the $\langle 011 \rangle \parallel \text{LD}$ viz. euler angle of $(58^\circ, 90^\circ, 309^\circ)$, $(90^\circ, 135^\circ, 2^\circ)$, $(49^\circ, 94^\circ, 315^\circ)$ marked as “A”, “B” and “C”, respectively. These grains with $\langle 011 \rangle \parallel \text{LD}$ are known to be unstable during uniaxial deformation and tend to rotate toward $\langle 111 \rangle$ at higher uniaxial deformation. It can be observed that grain “A” has no significant orientation gradient during the deformation till 40% and it’s orientation remain unchanged i.e. grain remained uninteractive during the deformation and similar behavior was captured with the CPFFT simulation. On the other hand, grain “B” and “C” form deformation band and orientation gradient, respectively, during deformation which was satisfactorily reproduced with CPFFT. Therefore, similarly oriented grains, $\langle 011 \rangle \parallel \text{LD}$, can take different rotation path depending on the local neighbourhood and these rotation paths were satisfactorily reproduced using the CPFFT.

The grain “D” in Figure 6.14 represents $\langle 111 \rangle \parallel \text{LD}$ and it is an stable orientation viz. orientation remain unchanged during the deformation. Both experimental as well as CPFFT

FIGURE 6.14: IPF map chosen from the *in-situ* experiment showing different deformation path.

simulation were able to reproduce the stable nature of $\langle 111 \rangle \parallel$ LD oriented grains. Grain “E” and “F” of Figure 6.14 are near $\langle 001 \rangle \parallel$ LD with orientations $(94^\circ, 91^\circ, 265^\circ)$ and $(53^\circ, 86^\circ, 276^\circ)$, respectively. $\langle 001 \rangle \parallel$ LD are known to be relatively stable orientation (less stable than $\langle 111 \rangle \parallel$ LD orientation) and the stability of $\langle 001 \rangle \parallel$ LD deteriorate with increasing deviation from ideal orientation. Therefore, Grains “E” and “F” shown in Figure 6.14 shows the development of orientation gradient as these are away from ideal orientation. Thus interacting and non-interacting grains during deformation were predicted using CPFDD simulation.

6.3 Summary

In the present work, uniaxial tensile deformation was carried out to understand the deformation behavior of the Ni-24W-22Fe alloy. The most important findings of the present work are summarized below.

1. The strain hardening obtained from the tensile deformation illustrates a characteristic hump that can be attributed to single slip to multiple slips. The transition from single slip to multiple slips is due to the initial short-range ordering present in the concentrated ternary solid solution.
2. Bulk texture evolution shows that $\langle 001 \rangle$ fiber present in the material deteriorates with increasing tensile deformation, leading to strong $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber evolution. The experimental and simulated texture results are in good agreement using a combinatorial approach of initial tangent simulation combined with secant simulation.
3. The *in-situ* EBSD result shows that grains with the same initial position in the stereographic triangle follow different rotation paths, i.e., some grains rotate towards $\langle 112 \rangle$ while some grains rotate towards $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction.
4. CPFDD simulation revealed that metastable $\langle 011 \rangle$ grains highly dependent on its neighborhood and $\langle 001 \rangle$ grains are stable but interacting whereas $\langle 111 \rangle$ is stable and non-interacting.

Chapter 7

Texture and microstructure evolution during plane-strain compression of Ni-24W-22Fe matrix alloy

7.1 Background

In the previous chapter, we examined the tensile deformation behavior of matrix alloy Ni-24W-22Fe. The most important findings from the previous chapter were the recovery of work hardening and the formation of MSBs. When a material is subjected to tensile loading, it is difficult to achieve a large plastic strain due to the onset of necking and the development of triaxial stress. Therefore, plane strain deformation was applied in order to understand the behavior of this alloy under large strain. In this regard, the matrix alloy was cold rolled up to 95% rolling reduction viz. $\varepsilon_{vm} = 3.46$, with intermediate samples held at 30%, 50%, 75%, and 90%, corresponding to ε_{vm} values of 0.41, 0.80, 1.60, 2.66, and 3.46, respectively.

7.2 Results

7.2.1 Line profile analysis of XRD

Modern experimental techniques allow for the measurement of X-ray line profiles with sufficient precision to infer strain/stress distributions. The XRD pattern contains a vast amount of information regarding the microstructure of the material, including crystallite size, lattice strain, and dislocation density. These information can be extracted using the Line profile analysis (LPA) of the diffraction peaks. There are a few different models for LPA, including the Warren–Averbach method [206], Groma’s method [207], the Williamson–Smallman approach [208], and the Convolution Multiple Whole Profile Fitting (CMWP) fitting method [209], which can be used to obtain these details. In this thesis, the CMWP fitting method was used to perform LPA analysis. Following section is a brief explanation of the fundamental concepts underlying CMWP fitting. The instrumental profile function was measured using a well-annealed matrix alloy as a standard reference. Figure 7.1 shows the diffraction pattern for rolled samples. The peak position of the diffraction sample remain almost constant (vary in the range of 0.08°) while broadening in FWHM was noticeable. The analysis of line broadening was performed using CMWP with reasonable initial parameters in the fitting procedures to minimize the weighted sums of squared residuals.

7.2.1.1 Convolution Multiple Whole Profile Fitting

This more recent method of LPA took into account both the elastic anisotropy and the entire measured intensity pattern, unlike other methods where each peak profile is fitted individually. The authors of CMWP assumed that a given peak’s broadening is due to the dislocations’ strain fields and FWHM can be expressed as

$$\Delta K \cong \left(\frac{0.9}{D}\right) + \left(\frac{\pi M^2 b^2}{2}\right) \rho^{1/2} (K^2 \bar{C}) + O(K^4 \bar{C}) \quad (7.1)$$

where, $K = 2 \sin \theta_B / \lambda$ and $\Delta K = 2 \cos \theta_B (\Delta \theta) / \lambda$. D , ρ , b , C , M , θ_B , λ is the crystallite size, dislocation density, Burgers vector, contrast factor, constant relying on outer cut-off radius of dislocations, Bragg angle and wavelength of XRD, respectively. O represents the high order terms as function of $(K^4 \bar{C})$. The diffraction pattern is then expressed in term of Fourier series in reciprocal lattice space to consider the FWHM broadening due each

FIGURE 7.1: X-ray diffraction pattern of the rolled matrix alloy.

individual slip system. Hence, Fourier coefficients result from a convolution product over all active slip-systems, known as Wilkens function $f(\eta)$. The broadening due mean square lattice strain in terms of $f(\eta)$ is expressed as:

$$\langle e_{g,L}^2 \rangle = (b/2\pi)^2 \pi \rho_{int} \bar{C} f(\eta) \quad (7.2)$$

where, the factor \bar{C} that determines the average dislocation contrast can be expressed as follows: where, \bar{C} is the average dislocation contrast factor which can be expressed as follow:

$$\bar{C} = \bar{C}_{h00} \left\{ 1 - q \left[\frac{h^2 k^2 + k^2 |l|^2 + l^2 h^2}{(h^2 + h^2 + h^2)^2} \right] \right\} \quad (7.3)$$

The dislocation density was evaluated using Equation 7.2 and other microstructural feature was obtained by fitting profile fitting. Figure 7.2 shows the variation of the crystallite size, also known as coherently scattering domain, lattice strain and dislocation density as a function of rolling reduction. The LPA shows that crystallite size decreased from 708 Å to

FIGURE 7.2: The variation of crystallite size, lattice strain and dislocation density as a function of rolling reduction

394 Å while lattice strain and dislocation density (ρ) increased from 0.2% to 0.4% and $3.8 \times 10^{14} m^{-2}$ to $1.37 \times 10^{15} m^{-2}$, respectively.

7.2.2 Vickers Hardness of rolled sample

The rolled samples after different rolling reductions were tested for Vickers hardness testing. The preliminary characterization of hardness test helps in characterizing the evolution of mechanical property. Figure 7.3 shows the evolution of hardness with rolling reduction. As strain increases from 0% to 90% rolling reduction ($\varepsilon_{vm} = 0$ to $\varepsilon_{vm} = 2.66$), the hardness of the sample increases from 339 HV_{0.05} to 449 HV_{0.05}. The variation in mean hardness value between 75%, 90% and 95% rolled samples is only 1.8%, however, the standard deviation (S.D.) of the mean hardness increases from 5.3% to 11.8% then decreases to 4.7%. An increase in S.D. can be attributed to the presence of heterogeneous deformation. Subsequently, a decrease in the S.D. can be attributed to the presence of uniform distribution of strain at higher strain. The hardness and their standard distribution values are listed in Table 7.1.

FIGURE 7.3: The variation of hardness with different rolling reduction (a typical Vickers indent on the sample is shown in inset).

TABLE 7.1: Standard deviation in hardness of as-cast and rolled samples (in %)

Von-Mises Strain	Hardness	Standard deviation
0	339	5.3
0.41	401	6.2
0.8	413	9.7
1.6	441	11.8
2.66	449	8.5
3.46	448	4.7

7.2.3 Bulk texture using XRD

Figure 7.4 shows the ODF sections for $\phi_2 = 0^\circ$, 45° and 65° that were collected using XRD. Figure 7.4(a) shows the ideal orientations of rolling textures for f.c.c. polycrystals. As deformation progress, from 30% to 50% rolling reduction texture intensity increases and a maximum intensity of 10 mrd can be observed at Copper-Dillamore position in $\phi_2 = 45^\circ$ section (Figure 7.4(c)). Upon further rolling reduction from 50% to 75%, texture intensity at Copper-Dillamore position decreases significantly (Figure 7.4(d)), whilst strengthening of texture can be noticed at near Goss orientation. With further increase in rolling

reduction, the intensity of the texture near the Copper-Dillamore position deteriorate consistently, however the α -fibre becomes stronger and homogeneous as its intensity spreads from Goss to Brass position. In 95% rolled sample, the presence of a much stronger Goss/Brass component as compared to Copper and S is quite evident from $\phi_2 = 45^\circ$, and 65° section (Figure 7.4(f)). Thus the texture evolution of the matrix alloy shows the Copper to Goss/Brass transition as deformation proceeds from 50% to 75% rolling reduction.

Understanding the evolution of the texture during rolling deformation can be expanded further by conducting an analysis of the variation in texture intensity along important fibres such as α , β , and τ fibre. At 50% rolling deformation, both β and τ fibres exhibit a predominant Copper component. When the rolling deformation is increased further, it can be observed, in the β and τ fibres, that the Copper component gradually becomes weaker while the Goss/Brass component simultaneously becomes stronger. Additionally, the α fibre also shows the strengthening of texture intensity between the Goss and Brass positions, reaching its maximum intensity at the Euler angle of ($\phi_1 = 20^\circ$, $\phi = 45^\circ$, and $\phi_2 = 0^\circ$). The volume fraction of the various components is shown in Figure 7.5(d) to illustrate and quantify the experimental observation of the transition from a Copper type texture to a Brass type texture. From the bar charts, it is evident that the volume fraction of Brass component increases with rolling reduction, while the volume fraction of Copper component decreases. It should also be noted that there was no significant change in bulk texture from 90% to 95% rolling reduction that can cause decrease in the hardness of the sample.

7.2.4 Evolution of microstructure

In order to comprehend the mechanisms underlying texture transition and decrease in hardness at high strain, light microscopy and EBSD were used to conduct a comprehensive microstructural characterization. The optical micrograph taken after rolling reduction of 30% reveals that there is a predominant slip-based deformation with flattening and elongation of grains along the rolling direction. Studies using EBSD provide additional evidence in support of these observations. The optical micrograph, band contrast, IPF map, and GROD map after 30% rolling reduction are shown in Figure 7.6. The development of orientation gradients that highlight the heterogeneous plastic deformation can be evidently observed from both the IPF and the GROD maps. Most grains have a mean misorientation of approximately 10° to 15° . At some locations, even higher misorientations, close to near 30° , can be observed near some grain boundaries, which suggests the development of

FIGURE 7.4: (a) Schematic of ODF keys corresponding to $\phi_2=0^\circ$, 45° and 65° sections highlighting the important texture component, (b-f) ODF ($\phi_2=0^\circ$, 45° and 65° sections) of rolled matrix alloy for 30%, 50%, 75%, 90%, 95% rolling reductions.

FIGURE 7.5: (a-c) Intensities of α , β and τ fibers for matrix alloy at 30%, 50%, 75%, 90% and 95% rolling reductions (d) Variation of volume fraction of rolling texture components as a function of rolling reduction measured by XRD.

Grain boundary affected zone (GBAZ). The development of GBAZ is shown in Figure 7.7 via a point to origin misorientation chart.

The grains become even more elongated when the rolling reduction increases to 50% , and the onset of MSBs can also be observed in some of the grains at this stage. As can be seen in Figure 7.8 (a), optical micrographs of rolled samples reveal the presence of MSBs in some of the grains, which have been highlighted with an arrow. The band contrast map at higher magnification supports the argument even more, and arrows in the figure show the presence of MSBs. The IPF map and GROD map, as shown in Figures 7.8 (c) and (d), exhibit behaviour that is comparable to that of samples with 30% rolling reduction. The GROD map (shown in 7.8(d)) reveals the grains with misorientation occurring inside the grain up to 50° . Grain with $\langle 011 \rangle \parallel \text{ND}$ has high GROD value indicate that heterogeneous plastic deformation occurred significantly higher in these grains.

FIGURE 7.6: Different microstructural characteristics of 30% rolled sample (a) Optical microstructure (b) Band contrast map (c) IPF map plotted in normal direction (d) GROD map.

FIGURE 7.7: Point-to-point misorientation plot for selected grains.

FIGURE 7.8: Different microstructural characteristics of 50% rolled sample (a) Optical microstructure (b) Band contrast map (c) IPF map plotted in normal direction (d) GROD map.

At rolling reduction of 75%, extensive amount of MSBs were observed in the optical micrograph shown in Figure 7.9. Localized deformation caused by MSBs are usually oriented at a shear angle of 30° to 35° to the rolling plane. These MSBs are sparsely distributed and heterogeneous in nature. The obtained microstructure is composed of two types of grains/regions: (a) Grain with MSBs and (b) Grains almost free from any MSBs. The measured shear band angle was 30° or 150° relative to rolling plane. According to the image analysis performed on the optical microstructure, 78% of the area fraction exhibited the formation of MSBs. The sample was further investigated using EBSD data.

The IPF and GROD maps are shown in Figure 7.10 (a) and (b). The IPF map shows five different elongated grain with grain fragmentation and parallel MSBs forming at an angle of 30° about rolling plane. Out of all these grain, one of the grain with Euler angle ($\phi_1 =$

FIGURE 7.9: Optical micrograph of 75% rolled matrix alloy.

35° , $\phi = 90^\circ$, $\phi = 45^\circ$) at the mid thickness has been elongated without any formation of MSBs. To understand this behaviour ODF of all these grains are plotted in Figure 7.11.

Figure 7.11(a) shows the presence of MSBs and grain fragmentation in Goss/Brass oriented grain. Figure 7.11(b) and (c) shows the unconventional grain in which shear band forms in the pattern of fish bone structure and parallel MSBs, respectively. Figure 7.11(d) shows the rotated Copper oriented grain with parallel MSBs. It is interesting to note that grain 7.11(e) do not form any MSBs and even orientation gradient is also minimal in this grain.

The MSBs are known to have ultrafine (sub)grains formation within these bands. To gain a better insight of the MSBs formed in the grain, 7.10(a) was magnified and EBSD data was collected for these regions. The magnification was increased systematically and EBSD was collected. Figure 7.10(c), (e) and (g) shows the IPF map for collected data and its corresponding GROD maps are shown in Figure 7.10(d), (f) and (h). These maps are able to resolve the unindexed points in earlier map and the formation of subgrain of $3\text{-}5\ \mu\text{m}$ can be observed inside the shear band. To have a better understanding of these shear bands a similar EBSD was collected at different region of the sample and their IPF map is shown in Figure 7.10 (i) and its corresponding GROD map is shown in Figure 7.10(j).

The orientations of subgrains inside the MSBs and the parent grain, of Figure 7.10 (e) and (i), were partitioned out and their ODF were plotted to get a comprehensive representation

FIGURE 7.10: Different microstructural characteristics of 75% rolled sample (a) Optical microstructure (b) Band contrast map (c) IPF map plotted in normal direction (d) GROD map.

FIGURE 7.11: ODF of individual grain deformed at 75% rolling reduction.

of the texture within the MSBs. Figure 7.12 (a-b) shows the orientation of the parent grain and their ODF plot, and Figure 7.12 (c-d) shows the partitioned orientation of MSBs and their ODF plot. It is evident that parent grain is near Brass oriented but the MSBs formed inside these grains are RD rotated Cube with grains size of 3-5 μm . Subgrain of $(\bar{1}3\bar{1})\langle 41\bar{1} \rangle$ and $(20\bar{1})\langle 0\bar{1}0 \rangle$ orientations was observed inside the MSBs with Euler angle of $(\phi_1 = 344^\circ, \phi = 112^\circ, \phi_2 = 340^\circ)$ and $(\phi_1 = 0^\circ, \phi = 112.3^\circ, \phi_2 = 85.9^\circ)$, respectively. Nevertheless, the shear band that is present in the different regions reveals a completely distinct texture inside the shear band. This is a unique finding since the orientations in the shear band are crucial in influencing the recrystallization texture.

The partitioning that was carried out on the micrograph shown in Figure 7.10(i) can be seen in Figure 7.13. Figure 7.13 (a) and (b) show the IPF map of the parent grain and its ODF, respectively, while Figure 7.13 (c) and (d) show the orientations inside the MSBs and ODF, respectively. The parent grain has maximum texture intensity of 19 mrd at Euler angle $(\phi_1 = 7.5^\circ, \phi = 62.5^\circ, \phi_2 = 0^\circ)$ which is equivalent to crystallographic texture of $\{021\}\langle 100 \rangle$. On the other hand, the maximum texture intensity of subgrains inside the MSBs is 30 mrd at Euler angle of $(\phi_1 = 50^\circ, \phi = 90^\circ, \phi_2 = 45^\circ)$ with crystallographic texture of $\{110\}\langle 1\bar{1}2 \rangle$.

FIGURE 7.12: (a) Partitioned IPF map of parent grain having shear band (b) ODF corresponding to parent grain (c) IPF of partitioned shear band (d) ODF of partitioned shear band

When the alloy was further deformed to a rolling reduction of 90%, it was discovered that there were grain scale shear bands present throughout the microstructure and volume of MSBs has increased significantly. These Grain scale shear bands are formed as a result of a combination of SRO assisted partial slip and planar slip, which also contributes to the formation of Goss/Brass type deformation texture.

7.3 Micro-Shear Band on Copper Grain

The experimental bulk texture showed the transition of Copper orientation to Goss/Brass orientation. Several researchers, notably Dillamore and Roberts [210] and Smallman and Green [211], have theorized that the difference in the ability of gliding dislocations to cross-slip is responsible for the transition from a metal-type texture to alloy-type texture.

FIGURE 7.13: (a) Partitioned IPF map of parent grain having shear band at different region (b) ODF corresponding to parent grain of (a) (c) IPF of partitioned shear band (d) ODF of partitioned shear band of (c)

FIGURE 7.14: IPF maps of (a) 90% rolled sample (b) GROD map of 90% rolled sample (c) 95% rolled sample (d) GROD map of 95% rolled sample

For rolling deformation, Dillamore and Roberts [210] concluded that planar dislocation glides on both primary and conjugate slip systems will reorient most grains toward the Brass orientation, with other minor components such as Cube, Goss, and Copper appearing. Brass, in particular, was considered stable in all of these orientations. Consequently, all f.c.c. metals, when rolled at room temperature or below, tend to produce Brass texture early in the rolling process. Previous research [212, 213] has shown that the initial texture development is the same in both classes of materials (low and high SFE metals) until they deviate at higher rolling reductions. Since no quantitative analysis was available, these previous studies need to be carefully reviewed. The cross-slip hypothesis is based on how quickly the stable Brass orientation shifts to Copper. Factors that increase the activation energy for cross-slipping reduce the probability of gliding dislocations cross-slipping, increasing the stability of the Brass orientation. Since dislocations can only cross-slip to other slip planes if two slip systems share the same Burgers vector ($b = \frac{1}{2} \langle 110 \rangle$), lowering the activation barrier for cross-slipping, such as by increasing the temperature, will cause the Brass orientation to be destroyed more quickly due to the abundance of dislocation cross-slipping. Cross-slip theory appears to be consistent with both the composition and temperature-dependent properties of texture transitions. The cross-slip hypothesis is called into question by Kuhlmann-Wilsdorf's observations of cross-slipping in α -Brass [214]. The theory provided by Dillamore and Roberts [210], depends on activation of cross-slips to realign Brass to Copper, has a serious flaw. The available cross-slip plane for Brass is perpendicular to the TD, suggesting that the biaxial stresses, as considered by the authors are unable to generate the stress required to activate slip on the cross-slip plane.

In order to increase the intensity of Brass-type texture, Leffers [215] introduced a modified cross-slip theory that necessitates the grain interior to deform by a single slip in order to improve texture intensity. This model requirement contradicts experimental observations of polyslip within grain interiors, notably those on α Brass. In addition, in contrast to the sluggish experimental Brass-type texture growth, this hypothesis showed quick rotations towards the Brass texture in metals that do not cross-slip. The activation energy for f.c.c. rolling texture transition was recently estimated by Leffers and Pedersen [216], and the results were found to be similar to the theoretical predictions of the activation energy for cross-slip texture transition [217]. The sole criticism of the indirect estimation of the texture transition activation energy is that it was calculated using two independent observations: (a) strain rate dependence on texture [218] and (b) texture's dependence on temperature. The correlation between strain rate and temperature and deformation texture is well understood. It is preferred to increase the strain rate for the Brass-type

texture, but it is better to increase the deformation temperature for the Copper-type texture. It is possible to argue that cross-slip is the mechanism that governs both types of tests. The texture transition, on the other hand, is evident in a single metallic system during room temperature rolling, even though the strain rate is not changed. Typically, for any class of f.c.c. metal (depending on the stacking fault energy), the transitory between the Brass-type and Copper-type textures does not occur within a restricted range of applied deformation. At very large rolling reductions (90%), the material enters a higher state of stress, and texture changes towards the Copper-end are common. It is assumed in the calculations of Leffer and Pedersen [216] that cross-slip is the mechanism that contributes to the texture transition. In summary, cross-slip theory appears to be partially true when applied to polycrystalline deformation, particularly when explaining the texture transition, but it should not be regarded as a stand-alone theory due to the flaws previously highlighted. In order to investigate the onset of MSBs and appearance of Brass orientation

7.4 CPFFT simulation of Copper grain

To comprehend the onset of this transition, a $64 \times 64 \times 64$ grid-sized 3D RVE microstructure with Copper orientation and a 5° spread was created. The list of orientations were generated using MTEX in matlab. The three dimensional microstructure was generated by placing the 100 random seed in a Cube of $(0, 0, 0) - (1, 1, 1)$. The orientations of these random seed were replaced with Copper orientation generated by MTEX. Using the voronoi tessellation scheme the seeds are converted to microstructure with every grid point assigned as grain identification number. The generated microstructure from paraview is shown in Figure 7.15.

The boundary condition for rolling has already been mention in section 5.3.2.2 and the parameter for phenopower law have already been mentioned in Table 5.1. The slip system is activated once the CRSS is reached by the shear stress component in the slip plane. The activation of the slip systems is characterized by the shear rate on each slip system. In the Table 7.2, the slip-systems of f.c.c. are presented using the Schmid-Boas notation. The slip direction is indicated by the number, and the normal of the slip plane is indicated by the capital letter in this notation.

Figure 7.16 shows the activation of co-directional C5 and B5 slip systems during the deformation of Copper orientation. The boundary traces are produced as a result of a co-directional slip system. These boundary traces form a crystallographic boundary plane

FIGURE 7.15: RVE input with 100 grains with Copper orientation with spread of 5° , Each grain is represented in different colour

TABLE 7.2: Schmid and Boas notation for slip systems in FCC lattice

	Number	Schmid and Boas notation	Slip system
Primary system	1	B4	$(111)[\bar{1}01]$
	2	B5	$(111)[\bar{1}10]$
	3	B2	$(111)[0\bar{1}1]$
Conjugate system	4	C1	$(\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1})[011]$
	5	C5	$(\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1})[\bar{1}10]$
	6	C3	$(\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1})[101]$
Cross-glide system	7	D4	$(\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1})[\bar{1}01]$
	8	D1	$(\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1})[011]$
	9	D6	$(\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1})[110]$
Critical system	10	A3	$(\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1})[\bar{1}01]$
	11	A6	$(\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1})[110]$
	12	A2	$(\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1})[0\bar{1}1]$

that is the sum of both slip planes weighted by their respective Schmid factor. At the start of deformation, coplanar or codirectional slips are active in different parts of the grain. At the border between these two areas, the two kinds of slips will interact. Interactions between coplanar and codirectional slip systems produce the strongest barriers in Lomer-Cottrell sessile junctions.

FIGURE 7.16: Shear rate of of all slip system as a function of Von-Mises strain from CPFPT

7.4.1 Role of Shear band

Metals and alloys deform in a highly localized manner, despite the fact that their structure changes uniformly on a global scale. The localization is mostly related to the complex local interactions of several deformation mechanisms that are required to match the external strain continuity. The assumption of homogeneous dislocation gliding on active slip planes is valid in multiaxial stress or strain studies. However, following a limited deformation, the dislocations rearrange into more non-uniform structures in the form of MSBs and shear bands. A significant difference between MSBs and shear band is that the latter frequently create new orientations within the band regions and alter local textures. The shear band usually start out small, forming MSBs within specific orientations of grains at modest reductions of 30%-40%, and then grow into macro shear band that traverse a few grains at higher reductions. Shear bands are defined geometrically as bands of a few hundred micrometers width that are inclined at a $\beta \sim 35^\circ$ angle to the rolling plane and parallel to the TD. Other values of β in the $20^\circ - 40^\circ$ range have been reported, but the value of 35° is the most common. The appearance of shear bands in the deformed structure as a result of slip inhibition on the available octahedral slip planes results in a highly unstable structure

where severe macroscopic shearing on the shear band plane in the direction of the bands occurs. The shear bands continue to grow in their longitudinal direction, and are referred to as active Shear Bands until they are no longer active. Wagner *et al.* [219] measured a notable shear strain across the bands by scratching the longitudinal face of a $\{112\}\langle 111 \rangle$ Al-8% Cu specimen that had been reduced to 80% of its original thickness. As a result, shear bands clearly show a macroscopic shearing process that is highly inhomogeneous. In this thesis, the propagation of shear bands across grain boundaries in polycrystalline materials to form MSBs is beyond the scope, because this is a completely different subject with its own characteristics. Single crystal experiments reveal a strong tendency for shear band formation in orientations that are close to the Copper orientation, such as $\{112\}\langle 111 \rangle$. Shear bands can be classified into two types: Copper-type shear bands, which are formed in metals with high and medium SFE, and Brass-type Shear bands, which are formed in metals and alloys with low SFE. Another distinction must be made in the case of metals, where Copper-type shear bands are expected to appear in the deformed structure. Metals with high SFE, such as Al, do not form shear bands when deformed at room or elevated temperatures. Nonetheless, their proclivity for forming shear bands at high reductions (over 95%) should not be overlooked. While Copper-type shear band formation is a significant mechanism of deformation, its contribution to global texture evolution is negligible, as it accounts for less than 5% of the deformation structure. As a result, the deformation textures of Cu and Al are similar, except that the texture of Al is slightly sharper. The appearance of high angle boundaries between the bands, as well as their orientation relationship to the matrix, should be carefully examined. It is possible that high angle mobile boundaries between the matrix and bands will grow, influencing the texture of the recrystallization texture.

The Copper orientation is a typical orientation that favors the formation of the shear band structure. In this non-symmetrical orientation, the $\{111\}$ slip planes are nonsymmetrically inclined to the RD, which results in a non-symmetrical orientation. The Copper orientation is a typical orientation that favors the formation of the shear bands structure. It is a non-symmetrical orientation in which the $\{111\}$ slip planes are inclined nonsymmetrically to the RD. Two pairs of slip systems are activated at the beginning of deformation under Tucker's biaxial state of stress for rolling, or Taylor's plane strain condition; namely, a coplanar pair: $(111)[\bar{1}01] + (111)[0\bar{1}1]$ and a co-directional pair: $(\bar{1}11)[110] + (\bar{1}\bar{1}1)[110]$. As shown schematically in Figure 7.17, the coplanar system is initially inclined at an angle of $+19.4^\circ$ with respect to RD. The development of a macroscopic shear strain (γ_{xz}) in RD is supplemented by an equal amount of dislocation gliding on these two active slip system pairs, which helps to maintain the Copper orientation stability. Nevertheless, as

FIGURE 7.17: Schematic diagram of the shear band geometry on longitudinal showing the shear plane in Copper and Goss orientation. Horizontal direction is RD and vertical direction is ND.

Wagner *et al.* [219] have pointed out, up to a reduction of 30% in CuAl and Cu-8% Al, the suppression of shear will continuously rotate Copper towards Dillamore, which is achieved by preferential activation of the co-directional pair over the Coplanar pair. Wagner *et al.* [219] proposed that the initial appearance of shear bands on the Coplanar slip plane would occur at this value of reduction. Increased band reduction will result in rotations about TD that are both positive and negative in nature, resulting in orientation scattering inside the bands. A -35° TD rotation will result in an orientation of [110], whereas a -55° TD rotation will result in an orientation of [001], Goss orientation. The presence of both of these texture components, as well as an intermediate position that is close to the [112] orientation, -20° TD, has been reported in the literature. There is little known about the mechanism of formation of these orientations within the narrow bands. For example, to explain the -55° TD rotation from Copper to Goss, crystallographically large amounts of shear are required.

While the above-mentioned shear banding observations have been reported in the literature, the mechanism by which the shear bands are formed is less clear. Morii *et al.* [220] established the efficacy of lamellar dislocation structures in the formation of shear bands using rolling experiments in Copper and Goss oriented single crystals of high purity Al, pre-twinned Cu, and Al-3% Mg. A hypothesis has been proposed that MSBs serve as a precursor to the nucleation of shear bands. Due to the fact that MSBs tend to form on the {111} slip planes, the crystallographic relationship between MSBs and the matrix is well understood. MSBs are typically visible against a background of diffused dislocation structure when the true strain is less than 0.5. The MSBs will group together as clusters with increasing strain and then rotate and fragment to form shear bands as the strain increases [221]. This hypothesis is supported by the fact that the slip partition is

biased in favor of higher activation of coplanar systems. In other words, if coplanar systems behave as more favored slip systems (prior to the nucleation of shear bands) in the Copper orientation, this would result in a rotation of the coplanar slip plane towards the compression plane, with the inclination angle (β) decreasing continuously from a starting value of 19.4° for Copper orientation to a final value of 18.9° for Copper orientation. Shear bands, on the other hand, are inclined at an angle ($\beta \sim 35^\circ$) to the compression plane and rotate in the opposite direction around TD in the majority of cases. However, the presence of shear bands in microstructures with layered structures (such as mechanical twin lamellae and elongated dislocation walls) and in the presence of solute atoms indicates the “absence” of a thermally activated process that rearranges the dislocation structures into a minimum energy state, such as dynamic recovery. When to pure Cu deformation at room temperature, the absence of shear bands in $\{112\}\langle 111 \rangle$ oriented high purity aluminium crystals rolled at room temperature can be attributed primarily to the absence of elongated dislocation structures, as Al tends to form equiaxed cell structures at higher homologous temperatures. In a single-crystal $\{112\}\langle 111 \rangle$ oriented high purity Al single crystal compressed at 77 K, Paul *et al.* [222] observed two nearly symmetrical shear bands and observed orientation scattering, which is common in Copper-type shear bands e.g. $\{001\}\langle 110 \rangle$, $\{110\}\langle 001 \rangle$ and $\{110\}\langle 001 \rangle$.

Korbel *et al.* [223] proposed that the formation of shear bands is caused by local microstructural instability in polycrystalline Al-4.8 wt.% Mg, and that shear bands appear to be volumes in which dynamic recovery and local accelerated strain occur at the same time in their investigation. As a result, they suggested that shear bands in deformed microstructures can appear without the need for the presence of lamellar dislocation structures, as had previously been proposed by Morii *et al.* [220] With the exception of the fact that Korbel *et al.* [223] studied a polycrystalline sample with an average grain size of $50 \mu\text{m}$ and Morii *et al.* [220] studied a single crystal with an orientation of $\{112\}\langle 111 \rangle$, there appears to be a significant discrepancy in the explanation of the deformation structure in a very similar Al-Mg alloy which was studied by both groups. Morii *et al.* [220] proposed that the suppression of dynamic recovery was caused by the pinning of dislocations at Mg-solute atoms, resulting in the formation of a non-cellular structure, as opposed to the cellular structure found in pure Al. Korbel and colleagues [223] proposed that the pinned dislocations be broken away at some nucleating points, allowing them to multiply and move cooperatively to form a dynamically recovered (softened) material state as a result. There was no explanation provided by the authors for the formation of high angle boundaries within the bands of unidirectional avalanche slip, which was observed within the bands.

Alternatively, a Taylor-type hardening equation for the macroscopic plastic instability condition has been used by several authors to model shear band formation during rolling.

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\varepsilon} \leq 0 \quad (7.4)$$

where $d\sigma$ and $d\varepsilon$ are the macroscopic stress and strain increment, respectively, together define the work conjugate of the system. Taylor type work hardening is assumed as

$$\sigma = M\tau_c(\Gamma) \quad (7.5)$$

where τ_c is the shear resistance of an active slip system (assumed constant for all the slip systems active simultaneously) which is a function of the total amount of shearing (Γ) at any given applied strain. M is the Taylor factor defined as $\frac{d\Gamma}{d\varepsilon}$. Solving equations 7.4 and 7.5, the macroscopic work hardening behavior can be written as

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\varepsilon} = \tau_c \frac{dM}{d\varepsilon} + M^2 \frac{d\tau_c}{d\Gamma} \quad (7.6)$$

Thus, the geometrical approach indicates that the evolution of the structure is largely determined by two competing parameters: work hardening ($d\tau_c/d\Gamma$) and texture softening (or hardening) ($dM/d\varepsilon$). It is realized that the above relationship provides the tendency of orientations to form shear bands from a purely textural softening consideration to overcome the positive ($d\tau_c/d\Gamma$) of metals, which is a result of the textural softening consideration alone. Shear bands appear in orientations where the Taylor factor decreases sharply with increasing deformation (Stage III or IV), which occurs when ($d\tau_c/d\Gamma$) decreases to near zero, shear bands appear in orientations with a sharp decrease in the Taylor factor. As illustrated in Figure 7.18, the Copper orientation at ($\Phi = 35.25^\circ$) has the highest Taylor factor, $M = 3.674$, under the full constraint condition, and the Taylor factor rapidly decreases as the orientation of the τ fibre changes. The observation of shear bands in the Copper orientation of most metals lends support to the texture softening hypothesis; however, additional microstructural explanations are required to explain the absence of shear bands in the Copper orientation of high SFE metals, for example, Al.

Several researchers have argued that after the shear bands are produced, the applied strain becomes more localised inside the shear bands, and subsequent deformation induces severe shearing on the plane and along the shear band direction, while the texture of the materials

FIGURE 7.18: Taylor factor calculated for the orientations on τ -fiber based on the full constraint (FC) model.

outside of the shear bands remains constant. Moreover, it has been found that local strain compatibility across the shear band and matrix will have a significant impact on texture of the matrix immediately close to the SB. Figure 7.19 shows a schematic representation of the shear band rotation ($\Delta\beta$) in the direction of the compression plane. The formation of any non-crystallographic angle of shear (β) can only be explained by the rotation of a rigid body, which is induced by the accumulation of reaction stresses (τ_{sb}) from the roll contacts or channel tool contacts. Though the oversimplified textural softening model predicts shear band angles that are near to experimental data, it fails to provide any microstructural explanation for the textural changes inside the shear bands because it treats the shear band independently of the matrix. Wagner *et al.* proposed that the shear bands are composed of a group of narrowly spaced microscopic shear bands that are acted upon by alternating shear stresses $+\tau_{SB}$ and $-\tau_{SB}$, resulting in opposite shears $\pm\gamma_{SB}$ in the shear band coordinate. This proposed model accounted for the observation of both large (+)TD rotations and large (-)TD rotations inside the shear band forming $\{112\}\langle 111\rangle$

FIGURE 7.19: Rigid body rotation of a Macro Shear Band due to the action of reaction stress, τ_{sb} , from tool contacts.

orientations. Though Wagner *et al.* improved postulations on the development of shear bands necessitate a lower level of strain compatibility across the matrix/SB interface than in a situation where a single MSB is operating, it still has to explain the activation of a different set of slip systems inside individual MSBs. Because textural softening theories are based on reaction stresses from tool contacts, it is crucial to understand the feasibility of the development of shear bands in polycrystalline samples where an interior grain interacts with its surrounding neighbours and so experiences varying reaction stresses. The shear band forming tendency of a Copper oriented grain in a polycrystalline sample is of particular importance, because the texture softening component ($dM/d\bar{\epsilon}$) declines at a slower rate in an interacting environment than in a single crystal test. Once again, the definition of the Taylor factor in a polycrystal situation must be modified to a M^{micro} . Precise studies with the Copper orientation surrounded by other known orientations and subjected to the plane strain compression test can indicate its local propensity to create shear bands.

The features of Brass-type shear bands are not significantly different from those of Copper-type shear bands, a regular distinction is established on the basis of the Brass-type shear bands' proclivity to form Goss orientations inside them. Also, unlike the Copper-type shear bands, the rotated Cube component $\{001\}\langle 110 \rangle$ is frequently missing here. Figure 7.12 and 7.13 shows the presence of non-crystallographic shear banding in two different grains. The former grain shows the formation of RD-rotated Cube while the latter grains shows the formation of Brass orientation. The Parent grain before deformation are not a part of popular known orientation component.

7.5 Summary

In the present work, large strain deformation was given via plane strain compression understand the deformation behavior of the Ni-24W-22Fe alloy. The most important findings of the present work are summarized below.

1. Line profile analysis on XRD profile of deformed samples shows that lattice strain and dislocation density of the alloy saturates after 50% rolling reduction viz. Von-Mises strain of 0.80. The hardness measurement of deformed samples also showed the similar trend and also the S.D. of hardness value first increased then decreased.
2. Bulk texture evolution showed the development of Copper orientation till 50% rolling reduction and after further rolling reduction Copper weakens and Goss/Brass texture component strengthens. The behaviour was elegantly shown in β fiber plot and by estimation of volume fraction .
3. The microstructure evolution by EBSD showed than in low strain regime, Von-Mises strain of 0.41, slipping mechanism accommodates the strain and as the Von-Mises strain in alloy rises to 0.81, onset of micro-shear bands was evident in optical and orientation imaging microscopy. At higher rolling reduction viz. Von-Mises strain of 1.6, extensive amount of micro shear bands were formed and volume of these micro shear bands increases further on increasing the rolling reduction.
4. CPFIT simulation revealed the activation of co-directional slip systems in Copper orientation which are know to form crystallographic boundary plane acting as the precursor for the micro shear band formation.

Chapter 8

Conclusions and future work

8.1 Conclusions

The primary objective of this dissertation was to develop a comprehensive study for processing - microstructure - texture - mechanical behaviour paradigm for the two-phase tungsten heavy alloy (90W-7Ni-3Fe) and its matrix alloy (Ni-22Fe-24W) under various strain levels and strain paths such as uniaxial compression, tension and cold-rolling. This work makes a significant contribution to the development of a fundamental understanding of the deformation micromechanics and the evolution of texture. A variety of characterization techniques have been used to investigate the deformation behaviour of alloys, beginning with alloy fabrication and experimental investigation of deformed specimens using XRD, SEM, EBSD, and indentation, as well as crystal plasticity simulation using VPSC (mean field simulation) and DAMASK (Full field simulation with fast Fourier transformation). The most important takeaways from this study can be broken down into the following categories for each of two distinct alloys:

Tungsten heavy alloys

1. When WHAs are deformed at low to moderate strains up to $\varepsilon = 0.5$, the deformation is accommodated solely by slip in both phases. The crystallographic texture evolution in tungsten lead to the formation of double fiber texture ($\langle 111 \rangle$ and $\langle 100 \rangle$) but matrix phase evolves to form $\langle 110 \rangle$ fiber texture. It was also established that tungsten content also plays an important role in the relative proportion of these double fiber texture. With the help of mean field simulation the deformation was

categorised as secant type deformation with the lattice co-rotation scheme to include the effect of connectivity of the tungsten particles.

2. When the WHA is subjected to a large strain, MSBs are observed in both the phases at true strain 1.7 and shear bands are observed across multiple grain at strain 2.3. The precursor for MSBs was confirmed by the texture intensity shift from Dillamore position to Copper position which implies the localization of slip on coplanar slip systems. The resultant microstructure resembles the pancake shapes and when these pancake configuration is taken into consideration, development of strong rotated Cube in tungsten phase was explained. It was also shown that the presence of these rotated Cube promotes the formation of macro shear band. The unidirectional shear deformation of Copper grain was shown to develop the Brass texture transition.
3. CPFPT simulation quantified the stress and strain distribution, partitioning of strain between phases and development of orientation gradient in the microstructure. The possible hotspot are also evident in stress strain maps and micro mechanical taylor factor map. The number of active slip system per pixel also helped in identifying the deformation mechanism.

Matrix alloy

1. When matrix phase alloy i.e. Ni-24W-22Fe alloy is deformed at low to moderate strain 0.4, a restoration of work hardening was confirmed due to hump formation in work hardening curve. The hump formation was reasoned with transition from single slip to multi-slip due to high probability of occurrence of SRO. The transition was further clinched with the bulk texture measurement and *in-situ* EBSD analysis. Bulk texture showed the transition from $\langle 001 \rangle$ fiber to $\langle 111 \rangle$ fiber and mean field simulation proved such transition is possible only if single slip to multi slip system is taken under consideration. The *in-situ* EBSD at low strain was able to capture the rotation path toward $\langle 112 \rangle$ which happens due to single slip system. The deformation banding and orientation gradient was elegantly captured with CPFPT simulation. Metastable orientation $\langle 011 \rangle$ showed the inactivity of grain, heterogeneous deformation in large grain and band formations during deformation. This behaviour was also elegantly captured. The behaviour of $\langle 001 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ was nicely captured in the simulation.
2. When the matrix is deformed to high strain, the formation of extensive MSBs formation were evident at strain of 1.7 and the volume of MSBs increased at strain

of 2.3. The presence of these bands lead to the evolution of Brass/Goss texture in the alloy which was confirmed by the evolution of β texture and increased volume fraction of Goss and Brass component. Two different type of MSBs were evident in EBSD analysis. Evolution of Brass component in Copper grain was explained using rigid body rotation.

8.2 Scope for future work

The primary goal of the research being done on tungsten heavy alloy is to gain an understanding of the deformation behavior that occurs during the ballistic impact and to work toward improving the performance of the material's penetration. Because of the large number of variables that are involved in a ballistic impact, such as high temperature, adiabatic shear banding, and high strain, it was essential to comprehend it in a methodical manner; as a result, the high strain effect and the temperature effect were not taken into account in this study. The deformation, however, was studied up to a strain of 2.3. The following are a few future directions that could be pursued following the completion of this thesis work. Some of these issues are listed:

1. The evolution of microstructure and texture at high temperature (> 800 °C) for moderate and high strain and high strain rate tests.
2. To understand the evolution of RD rotated Cube texture appeared in the deformation of matrix alloy.
3. A transmission electron microscopy (TEM) observation of these deformed samples would provide additional information regarding the origin of these microshear bands. The origin of the micro shear bands in these samples remains unexamined.

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